

Quantum Computing Logistics

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Newspapers and websites are reporting with strong emphasis the successes of quantum computing, obtained by the new quantum machines. It is therefore natural to ask ourselves some questions about these machines, in particular how do they operate, where are they physically and what is needed for their running. Actually, we must ask ourselves such questions because the news headlines – sometime bombastic - could lead us to understand quantum machines as actually existing supercomputers, able of solving in a few seconds some calculation problems that classical computers would take millennia to process. To answer questions, this work is proposing a review of existing Quantum Computers. In the panorama of Quantum Computing, we intend to investigate how the future of their infrastructures will be, such as the related basic algorithms. We will try to understand what their logistics will be, where logistics is understood as a new quantum "art of computing". Specific attention will be paid to the quantum advantage, the medium-term strategy related to design algorithms for the next generations of quantum computers. Such algorithms are required by a wide range of strategic applications. Currently, they are mainly simulation algorithms of quantum physics and chemistry, but also algorithms related to quadratic unconstrained binary optimization exist. Here we will illustrate in particular two methods: one based on adiabatic quantum computation, which is obtained through quantum annealing (D-Wave systems), the other based on arrays of quantum gates (IBM, Google and others). We will see, in greater detail, the simulations concerning the Variational Quantum Eigensolver method. Some notions related to qubits, quantum gates and their Hamiltonians will be proposed too. Besides talking of qubits, we will also report about qumodes. In fact, the art of quantum computing has two faces, one based on qubits, the other based on qumodes. Xanadu's Borealis quantum computer is an example of qumode computer. It is capable of developing a hybrid system, with GKP-type qubit emulation along with squeezed light. SpinQ's first three qubits desktop will also be mentioned. A hint of quantum communication will also be provided.

Keywords: Qubit, Qumode, Qudit, Hamiltonian, Schrödinger Equation, Quantum Information, Logistics, NISQ, Quantum Computing, Quantum Processing Unit, Josephson Junction, rf-SQUID, Majorana Particle, Quantum Dots, Teleportation, Hadamard Gate, CNOT Gate, Controlled Gates, Flying Photon, Quantum Communication.

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Logistics and News

Logistics

The word “logistics” is coming from Greek λογιστική (τέχνη), which means exactly the «art of computing». However, if we consider the verb λογίζομαι, we can find several meanings: to count, calculate, ascribe, recognize, compute, ponder, consider, understand, conclude and even infer. This verb is perfect for what we want to do now. We want to consider - in the sense of the several actions described by verb λογίζομαι - the quantum computer and related computer science. We aim to analyze how are today quantum computers and quantum algorithms: this is logistics, because logistics is naturally the practice related to the running of a new computation model (hardware and software) and new specific applications. In fact, the quantum computer and quantum computing seem to lead us, in general, towards a new logistics of computing. We can find this approach clearly exposed in the statement: "Let the computer itself be built of quantum mechanical elements which obey quantum mechanical laws", enunciated by Richard

Feynman in 1982 in relation to simulations of quantum systems. It could be paraphrased in a "use a similar system to simulate another system".

“Quantum computing is a beautiful fusion of quantum physics and computer science, incorporating some of the most stunning ideas from twentieth-century physics into an entirely new way of thinking about computation.”

From the overview of
“Quantum Computing for Everyone” by Chris Bernhardt
<https://mitpress.mit.edu/books/quantum-computing-everyone>

“Think quantum”

<https://www.rigetti.com>

The new quantum logizomai is perfectly condensed into the “Think Quantum” by Rigetti.com. Besides a specifically interest concerning the physics of the subject, the need for quantum computer analysis arises from recent emphatic news (June 2022) on quantum computing.

News

News headlines regarding quantum computers are often very appealing. In Italy we read recently: “Debutta Borealis, il primo computer quantistico 'supremo'. Supera anche i più potenti supercomputer tradizionali”, that is Borealis is the 'supreme' quantum computer, which surpasses even the most powerful traditional supercomputers. News on June 10 , 2022, by Leonardo De Cosmo [Notizia ANSA](#) ([Archive](#)).

ANSA News article tells that for the first time, a 'supreme' quantum computer, capable of surpassing even the most powerful traditional supercomputer, is publicly available by means of a cloud service. It is Borealis, the programmable photonic computer made by Canadian company Xanadu, now accessible to researchers and companies through Braket, the quantum Amazon Web Services (AWS). According to ANSA, having become the first programmable quantum computer using particles of light (photons) to surpass any other traditional supercomputer, Borealis also earns the distinction of being the first quantum computer to go to the cloud, in the very small club of quantum computers that have reached the milestone of quantum supremacy.

Reading this first part of ANSA article, it seems that Borealis can be accessed from the cloud, and programmed for some specific calculation desired by the user, as if it were an existing supercomputer. More than a supercomputer indeed, since the article says that Xanadu's computer solved in 36 microseconds a calculation that would take 9,000 years to be performed by a non-quantum supercomputer (the same told by [sito informazione.it](#), [Archive](#)).

The result has been achieved in a very specific case, but it remains significant in the long road leading to a *universal* quantum computer, able of performing calculations, otherwise impossible to be made by classical computers [ANSA]. The problem solved by the “new chips” is really a difficult problem, known as Gaussian Boson Sampling, which takes a long time to be solved by

traditional computers that are not based on quantum physics, according to the director of Quantum Computing Amazon Web Services AWS, Simone Severini. Italian broadcaster RAI also announced the success of Borealis. ANSA article and RAI news may lead a reader or viewer to suppose the existence of quantum computers that, in some very difficult applications, are extremely faster than computers we are using today (including supercomputers). This is true but it is necessary to consider that the application must be specific for the machine.

Let's take a step back in time of a few months and read from Il Sole 24 Ore the article "From supremacy to quantum advantage: quantum computing goes on the market" by Luca Tremolada, 23 January 2022 ("Dalla supremazia al vantaggio quantistico: il quantum computing va sul mercato", link [Sole24Ore](#) (archived [Archive](#))). This title is appealing too, but please note that what is going on the market is the quantum computing, not only the computer.

Here we meet again Simone Severini. Severini tells: «*Ma se mi chiedi quando il computer quantistico avrà un impatto commerciale ti dico subito che nessuno lo sa. L'unica certezza che abbiamo è che a differenza dei computer di oggi governati dalla fisica newtoniana quelle quantistiche saranno macchine capaci di risolvere problemi che mai ci siamo posti. ...*» [Sole24Ore]. If you ask me [Severini] when quantum computers will have a commercial impact, I'll tell you right now that no one knows. The only certainty we have is that, unlike today's computers governed by *Newtonian physics*, quantum machines will be machines capable of solving problems that we have never set ourselves ... ". The article from Sole 24 Ore adds that scientists have been working on the development of quantum computers since the 1980s, becoming the quantum computing revolution the most heralded ever. Two years ago Google had claimed that it had achieved quantum supremacy, that is the ability of a quantum processor to solve a calculation that a traditional computer would complete in years or in any case in unreasonable times. "La corsa continua a colpi di pubblicazioni scientifiche *ma negli ultimi 24 mesi qualcosa è cambiato*. Molti ricercatori hanno spostato la loro attenzione su qualcosa di meno ambizioso della costruzione di una informatica alternativa al silicio. Le aziende si stanno dando da fare per essere le prime a trovare un'applicazione pratica per i computer quantistici". The race continues, supported by scientific publications, but in the last 24 months something has changed. Many researchers have turned their attention to something less ambitious than building a computer science which is alternative to the silicon-based one. Companies are working hard to be the first to find a practical application for quantum computers. That is, the strategy passed from supremacy to quantum advantage.

The strategy, as explained by Severini, goes in two directions. The first is a long-term one and is that of building quantum computers that solve problems which can be useful, far beyond scientific research. The second approach is that of offering cloud computing services, where it is possible of experiencing with quantum computing and understand what today can or cannot be done with quantum algorithms. You can learn to code and explore potential applications. You can design quantum algorithms starting from scratch or choosing from a series of predefined existing algorithms. [Sole24Ore]

In this framework, [Amazon Braket](#) is a cloud service for quantum computing, aiming to support a faster scientific research concerning the development of quantum calculation. Binary computers are used to simulate the quantum computing. By means of such simulators, you can

perform tests on quantum algorithms at a lower cost than using quantum hardware and without having to wait to access specific machines [Sole24Ore].

The Sole 24 Ore article ends with sentences which contain the logistics of quantum computing in a nutshell. The writer tells that we could say we are working on a quantum computer even without having a quantum computer, which is a bit like starting to build roads and traffic lights waiting for the car. First the ICT logistics - the art of quantum computing and related algorithms - and then the device. Also note that the cloud, for a quantum computer, will be the choice by default.

The article in the Sole 24 Ore talks about the building of a computer science alternative to the silicon one. This statement requires a comment. There is a line of research where quantum computation is based on "quantum dots" which are silicon elements. Furthermore, any quantum computer will necessarily have to include an interface with a classical computer. If the winning road to the universal quantum computer is the one based on the quantum dot, then this will be the natural evolution of silicon research.

Simone Severini talks about the *fisica newtoniana* governing the classical computers that we use today. In fact, to govern our computer is the solid state physics, which is not a newtonian physics (we will discuss this point further in a specific section about design and fabrication). Let us say that simulations implemented on classical computers are not inherently quantum simulations. In the quantum computer, on the other hand, we have the quantum simulation, exactly as thought by Richard Feynman. It is the computer itself that has the quantum logistics for quantum computing.

Let us consider again ANSA News June 2022 article; one might think that the success of Borealis, June 2022, has upset the strategy. No, the strategy remains the same.

“Xanadu launches first public cloud-deployed computer with quantum computational *advantage*”, News provided by Xanadu, Jun 01, 2022, [web site prnewswire](#) ([Archive](#)).

“Borealis is accessible to anyone with an internet connection over Xanadu Cloud, and will also be available via Amazon Braket, the fully managed quantum computing service from AWS. "With Borealis on Amazon Braket, for the first time, any researcher or developer will be able to validate a claim of *quantum advantage* and evaluate how *photonic quantum computing* may eventually expand their choice of compute technologies, enabling them to innovate more quickly," said Richard Moulds, General Manager of Amazon Braket at AWS”.

Link to [Xanadu Cloud](#) , web page <https://www.xanadu.ai/products/borealis/>

Once again, we move from supremacy to advantage. Supremacy was the race to have the fastest computer ever; the advantage is to have a new calculation, at least better defined, that spurs hardware development. As said by Il Sole 24 Ore, companies are working hard to be the first to find a practical application for quantum computers and thus effectively move from quantum supremacy to quantum advantage, that is to design algorithms to be carried out by the quantum computers of the future.

Borealis, as a cloud programmable quantum computer, in the common sense that we can give to these words, that is thinking of it as a cloud supercomputer, does not exist. So let's try to understand what existing quantum computers are. But first, let's say a few words about the IBM cloud.

IBM Quantum Experience

We have read in ANSA article, that “Borealis guadagna anche il primato di essere il primo ad andare sul cloud, nella ristrettissima cerchia di computer quantistici che hanno raggiunto il traguardo della supremazia quantistica” [ANSA] (Borealis also earns the distinction of being the first quantum computer to go to the cloud, in the very small club of quantum computers that have reached the milestone of quantum supremacy).

Quantum supremacy aside, let's talk about quantum computing cloud availabilities. Borealis is the first photonic computer to go to the cloud, but not the first quantum computer, as it was the IBM qubit computer.

Let's see what the IBM cloud proposes.

From https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_Quantum_Experience

“The IBM Quantum Composer and the IBM Quantum Lab (previously known collectively as the IBM Quantum Experience) form an online platform allowing public and premium access to cloud-based quantum computing services provided by IBM Quantum. This includes access to a set of IBM's prototype quantum processors, a set of tutorials on quantum computation, and access to an interactive textbook. As of February 2021, there are over 20 devices on the service, six of which are freely available for the public. This service can be used to run algorithms and experiments, and explore tutorials and simulations around what might be possible with quantum computing.”

Therefore, a cloud service for quantum computing already existed as of 2016. It was a cloud service based on qubits; Xanadu's is based on qumodes. They are two different logistics.

“IBM scientists have built a quantum processor that users can access through a first-of-a-kind quantum computing platform delivered via the IBM Cloud onto any desktop or mobile device. IBM believes quantum computing is the future of computing and has the potential to solve certain problems that are impossible to solve on today's supercomputers” (May 2016, [web site prnewswire](#)). Wikipedia tells also that “IBM's quantum processors are made up of superconducting transmon qubits, located in dilution refrigerators at the IBM Research headquarters at the Thomas J. Watson”. Users interact with a quantum processor unit (QPU) through quantum circuit models. These circuits are created by means of Quantum Composer or the Quantum Lab's Jupyter notebook.

In 2016, IBM QPU had 5 qubits. From [prnewswire](#) , it appears that this QPU was “the leading approach **towards** building a **universal quantum computer**. A universal quantum computer can be programmed to perform any computing task and will be exponentially faster than classical computers for a number of important applications for science and business". The article in Prnewswire stresses that a universal quantum computer does not exist today, "but IBM envisions medium-sized quantum processors of 50-100 qubits to be possible in the next decade. With a quantum computer built of just 50 qubits, none of today's TOP500 supercomputers could successfully emulate it, reflecting the tremendous potential of this technology. The community of quantum computer scientists and theorists is working to harness this power, and applications in optimization and chemistry will likely be the first to demonstrate quantum speed-up”.

Moreover, “Quantum computers are very different from today's computers, not only in what

they look like and are made of, but more importantly in what they can do.”

IBM's strategy, by giving access to its experimental quantum systems, aims to facilitate the scientific community in accelerating innovation towards new applications of quantum computing technology. IBM is pursuing, besides the increase of the qubit number, the expansion of applications through the "advantage" mentioned by Il Sole 24 Ore. The strategy is to find valid applications, in order to stimulate the demand for new processors.

“Hope (and hype) and reality are not the same thing.” [Jack Krupansky, 2018]

Universal quantum computer

Italian ANSA article is mentioning the “computer quantistico universale”.

This terminology, what does it mean and when was it first proposed?

From “What Is a Universal Quantum Computer?” by Jack Krupansky. Sep 1, 2018

<https://jackkrupansky.medium.com/what-is-a-universal-quantum-computer-db183fd1f15a>
(Archive).

“First the bad news: The term Universal Quantum Computer has been reduced to mere marketing hype. What was it supposed to mean before the marketing hysteresis entered the scene? ... The essence of a universal quantum computer is that it combines the full power of a classical computer with the power of a quantum computer, and enables simulation of physics, including and especially quantum mechanics. Current and near-term quantum computers tackle only the quantum portion of the full vision, leaving out all of the conceptual power of a Turing machine. How to get there from where we are today is the subject of the rest of this [Krupansky’s] paper”.

The article goes on with the use of terminology.

“**Feynman** didn’t appear to use this specific term, including in his **1982** paper, **Simulating Physics with Computers**, although he did make reference to universal computer and universal quantum simulator. His focus then was primarily on the capacity to simulate physics, notably quantum mechanics, and a focus on the quantum aspects of the simulation”. It could be argued that Feynman meant a computer capable of performing both classical and quantum computations, “but he doesn’t reach the point of a crisp definition for the term”. [Krupansky] “**Deutsch** does explicitly refer to the term in this **1985** paper, [entitled] *Quantum theory, the Church-Turing principle and the universal quantum computer*, but like Feynman he doesn’t offer a crisp definition for the term. ... Now that several vendors are actually able to make their quantum computers available online or remote execution of quantum programs, people are getting much more excited. Especially the marketing people. But excitement frequently does not align strictly with reason and technical correctness”.

The terminology "universal computer" would therefore go back to Richard Feynman's 1982 article and the "universal quantum computer" to David Deutsch's 1985 article. Richard Feynman was awarded the Nobel Prize for Physics (1965), for the elaboration of quantum electrodynamics, based on diagrams which are today known as Feynman diagrams. The 1982

article is entitled "Simulating physics with computers." David Deutsch is a physicist who works at the University of Oxford, a pioneer in the study of quantum computation. He was awarded Dirac Prize in 1998, for his formulation of the quantum Turing machine.

Glossary

Jack Krupansky is the author of a considerable glossary. See please his “Quantum Computing Glossary — Introduction”, <https://jackkrupansky.medium.com/quantum-computing-glossary-introduction-2414aa510854> ([Archive](#)).

“A computer is generally considered to be a universal computational device; i.e., it is believed able to simulate any physical computational device with a increase in computation time of at most a polynomial factor. It is not clear whether this is still true when quantum mechanics is taken into consideration.”

Peter Shor, 1994

Feynman (1981)

In the article entitled "Simulating Physics with Computers", submitted to the journal on May 7, 1981, there is not only a series of general statements. There is also, and it will become clear in the following discussion, the starting point of any quantum calculation, related to the transition from the system Hamiltonian to the Pauli strings, a fundamental step for any quantum simulation. Feynman tells: “Suppose that we try the following guess: that every finite quantum mechanical system can be described exactly, imitated exactly, by supposing that we have another system such that at each point in space-time this system has only two possible base states. Either that point is occupied, or unoccupied - those are the two states. The mathematics of the quantum mechanical operators associated with that point would be very simple.”

Operators are creation and annihilation operators:

$$a = \text{annihilate} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_x - i\sigma_y) \quad ; \quad a^* = \text{create} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_x + i\sigma_y)$$

$$n = \text{number} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = a^* a = \frac{1}{2}(1 + i\sigma_z) \quad ; \quad 1 = \text{identity} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

“There would be an operator a which annihilates if the point is occupied - it changes it to unoccupied. There is a conjugate operator a^* which does the opposite: if it's unoccupied, it occupies it. There's another operator n called the number to ask. Is something there? The little matrices tell you what they do. If it's there, n gets a one and leaves it alone, if it's not there, nothing happens. That's mathematically equivalent to the product of the other two, as a matter of fact. And then there's the identity, which we always have to put in there to complete our mathematics - it doesn't do a damn thing!”

And here we can find the basic algebra, with creation and annihilation operators a^*, a and Pauli

matrices $\sigma_z, \sigma_x, \sigma_y$.

Feynman adds also “The question is, if we wrote a Hamiltonian which involved only these operators, locally coupled to corresponding operators on the other space-time points, could we imitate every quantum mechanical system which is discrete and has a finite number of degrees of freedom? I know, almost certainly, that we could do that for any quantum mechanical system which involves Bose particles. I'm not sure whether Fermi particles could be described by such a system. So I leave that open. Well, that's an example of what I meant by a general quantum mechanical simulator. I'm not sure that it's sufficient, because I'm not sure that it takes care of Fermi particles.”

When we will analyze simulations with fermions, we will see that there are Hamiltonians written in first quantization, reformulated in second quantization, and then, with the Jordan-Wigner transformation, rendered into Pauli strings. However, a specific approach is needed that takes into account the fermionic antisymmetry.

Benioff and the computer as a physical system (1979)

In August 1979, it had been published an article entitled *The computer as a physical system: A microscopic quantum mechanical Hamiltonian model of computers as represented by Turing machines*, by **Paul Benioff** (Journal of statistical physics, 22(5), 563-591, 1979).

From [Wikipedia](#): “In the 1970s, Benioff began to research the theoretical feasibility of quantum computing. His early research culminated in a paper, [the reference given above] published in 1980, that described a quantum mechanical model of Turing Machines. This work was based on a classical description in 1973 of reversible Turing machines by physicist Charles H. Bennett. Benioff's model of a quantum computer was reversible and did not dissipate energy. At the time, there were several papers arguing that the creation of a reversible model of quantum computing was impossible. Benioff's paper was the first to show that reversible quantum computing was theoretically possible, which in turn showed the possibility of quantum computing in general. This work, along with later work by several other authors (including David Deutsch, Richard Feynman, and Peter Shor), initiated the field of quantum computing. In a paper published in 1982, Benioff further developed his original model of quantum mechanical Turing machines. This work put quantum computers on a solid theoretical foundation. Richard Feynman then produced a universal quantum simulator. [the reference given by Wikipedia is Feynman's article previously discussed, and Feynman himself is not sure that the schematized model is really universal] Building on the work of Benioff and Feynman, Deutsch proposed that quantum mechanics can be used to solve computational problems faster than classical computers, and in 1994, Shor described a factoring algorithm that is considered to have an exponential speedup over classical computers.”

Let us consider Benioff's article, where a microscopic quantum mechanical model of computers, as represented by Turing machines, is constructed. The article shows that "for each number N and Turing machine Q there exists a Hamiltonian H_N^Q and a class of appropriate initial states such that if $\psi_Q^N(0)$ is such an initial state, then

$\psi_Q^N(t) = \exp(-iH_N^Q t) \psi_Q^N(0)$ correctly describes at times t_3, t_6, \dots, t_{3N} model states that correspond to the completion of the first, second, \dots , N -th computation step of Q . The model parameters can be adjusted so that for an arbitrary time interval Δ around t_3, t_6, \dots, t_{3N} , the "machine" part of $\psi_Q^N(t)$ is stationary."

Benioff defines the Turing Machine in the following manner.

"A Turing machine consists of a machine and an infinite tape divided into cells. Each cell of the tape may be blank or it may contain one of a finite number of symbols. The finite symbol string present on the tape at any time is called the tape expression. The machine scans one tape cell at a time and can either change the tape symbol or print one if the cell is blank, or shift one cell to the right, or one cell to the left, or do nothing. The machine can assume any one of a finite number of states called "internal states." An elementary Turing machine operation consists of the machine in an internal state carrying out one of the above operations on the tape cell it is scanning and then going to some other internal state."

After some discussion, we can find the quantum model of Turing machine.

"The tape is represented here by a **lattice of quantum spin systems** of finite length. The tape alphabet, which is the set of possible symbols, blank included, that can appear in any cell, is assumed to be in one-one correspondence with the set of possible spin projections that each of the spin systems is capable of assuming. Thus an expression (as a symbol string) of length n corresponds to a length- n lattice system in a product state in which the j -th system is in a spin projection eigenstate which corresponds to the j -th symbol of the expression." In the abstract of Benioff's article, we can find a factor three for times: "for ease and clarity of exposition, three record tapes, as three quantum spin lattices, will be added. The reason is that it is necessary to record, for each calculation step. the machine internal state, the symbol in the cell being scanned, and the position of the computation head."

In the text and in the Appendix of Benioff's article we can find the Hamiltonian of the system (first quantization) and the unitary operators and propagators, which are the basic elements of quantum computing. We do not find the second quantization, which is a further element of this computation. We can find it in the Feynman's work.

Propagators

When we will discuss the simulations made by quantum computers, we will see how to pass from the propagator, related to Schrödinger equation, to the quantum circuit (in the case that we use a computer based on a qubit array of quantum gates). The propagator contains the Hamiltonian of the system that we have to simulate. The Hamiltonian, given by the first quantization, is represented in the second quantization formalism, containing creation and annihilation operators. Then, this system Hamiltonian must be translated into the simulator Hamiltonian, made by strings of Pauli matrices. Let us stress that the simulator is a quantum artificial system made by qubits or qumodes in the case of optical machines.

To illustrate the passage from quantum system to quantum simulator, let us add the following scheme.

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Quantum system} \quad |\phi(0)\rangle \xrightarrow{U} |\phi(t)\rangle \\ \text{Quantum simulation} \quad |\psi(0)\rangle \xrightarrow{U'} |\psi(t)\rangle \end{array}$$

We have a quantum system to be simulated that, from the initial state $|\phi(0)\rangle$, by means of operator U (propagator) becomes the state $|\phi(t)\rangle$. This is true for the system; the simulator has another wave function, another Hamiltonian and a different propagator. From the initial state $|\psi(0)\rangle$, by means of operator U' , the simulator reaches the final state $|\psi(t)\rangle$. For this reason, it is necessary to transfer the Hamiltonian of the system, in second quantization, into a Hamiltonian that can be understood by the set of qubits that are composing the simulator. The Hamiltonian of the simulator contains the Pauli matrices. The resulting propagator is then described, in the case of a quantum gate simulator, by a circuit where the Pauli matrices are the representative elements of the quantum gates.

For the quantum system, we have the Schrödinger equation, with operator \hat{H} of the Hamiltonian:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} |\phi(t)\rangle = \hat{H} |\phi(t)\rangle,$$

the solution is:

$$|\phi(t)\rangle = e^{-i\hat{H}(t-t_0)/\hbar} |\phi(t_0)\rangle = U |\phi(t_0)\rangle$$

where $|\phi(t_0)\rangle$ is the initial state at time t_0 . For the simulator, we have:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} |\psi(t)\rangle = \hat{H}' |\psi(t)\rangle$$

with operator \hat{H}' , and solution:

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = e^{-i\hat{H}'(t-t_0)/\hbar} |\psi(t_0)\rangle = U' |\psi(t_0)\rangle.$$

NISQ era and encryption

Let's go back to the quantum computers.

From the article “Per computer quantistici serve tempo, ancora troppi errori”, link [ANSA](#), June 17, 2022, that is "Quantum computers need time, still too many errors". Physicist Pasquale Calabrese, SISSA, Trieste, says that the first NISQ (Noisy intermediate-scale quantum) computers already exist. They are built by some of the main players of ICT industry worldwide, but these computers with a hundred qubits are still too noisy, that is, they still make too many errors to trust the result. Calabrese adds that the era of NISQ computers will end when we will

have an object with about 10,000 qubits, with enough fault-tolerance. According to an optimistic point of view, it takes about ten years to have such computers, but Calabrese tends to move the time horizon forward, definitely forward.

“In the noisy intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) era the leading quantum processors contain about 50 to a few hundred qubits, but are not advanced enough to reach fault-tolerance nor large enough to profit sustainably from quantum supremacy. The term [NISQ] was coined by **John Preskill** in 2018. [Preskill is an American theoretical physicist and the Richard P. Feynman Professor of Theoretical Physics at the California Institute of Technology, where he is also the Director of the Institute for Quantum Information and Matter]. It is used to describe the current state of the art in the fabrication of quantum processors. The term 'noisy' refers to the fact that quantum processors are very sensitive to the environment and may lose their quantum state due to quantum decoherence. In the NISQ era, the quantum processors are not sophisticated enough to continuously implement quantum error correction. The term 'intermediate-scale' refers to the quantum volume related to the not-so-large number of qubits and moderate gate fidelity”. From item https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Noisy_intermediate-scale_quantum_era

A computer with tens of thousands of qubits and fault-tolerance would eventually end the NISQ era. These future devices would be able, for example, to implement the Shor's algorithm, for very large numbers and break the RSA encryption.

RSA (Rivest–Shamir–Adleman) refers to a widely used public-key encryption system. RSA is based on two large, random prime numbers P and Q . P and Q are multiplied to get a number M , which becomes part of the public key. If you know P and Q , you can decrypt the messages. RSA works if it is impossible to factor M into P and Q in a reasonable time. If you have a fast factorizing algorithm, then RSA becomes useless for encryption. Peter Shor (1994) found a partly classical and partly quantum algorithm of this kind. **Peter Williston Shor** is professor of applied mathematics at MIT, known for his work on quantum computation, in particular for the Shor's algorithm, the quantum algorithm for factoring which is exponentially faster than the best algorithms running on a classical computer.

The NISQ era will end the first time the RSA encryption will be broken.

Not the whole field

NISQ computers are qubit computers (we will soon describe them in detail). However, we have started our discussion from an article about a computer (Borealis) that has a different physical basis, different from that of an IBM quantum computer for instance. Computers are so different that Borealis runs at room temperature, while IBM requires very low temperatures. Borealis works with light, while IBM uses superconductivity. Borealis does not have the "qubits" that an IBM computer possesses, which are "superconducting charge qubits". Borealis has a hybrid chip, containing both GKP states and squeezed states of light, as we will discuss in detail in the part of the discussion entitled "The Boreal Light".

Then, “the NISQ concept does not capture the whole field”, as told by Olivier Pfister, in his *Continuous-variable quantum computing in the quantum optical frequency comb*, 2020.

Pfister explains that “Another line of experimental research has placed scalability at the forefront, relying on the remarkable ability of optical parametric oscillators (OPOs) to produce

very large numbers of entangled quantum fields. Experimental results confirmed this with thousands and a million of entangled quantum modes—a.k.a. qumodes — respectively in the frequency and temporal domains” [see please references given by Pfister].

The difference between NISQ and OPO systems lies in the fact that the latter uses continuous-variable quantum computing (CVQC), proposed at the end of the last century. There are therefore two great families of quantum computers: those with qubits and those with qumodes. The logistics of quantum computing therefore has two faces, one based on qubits and one based on qumodes. Note that Pfister points out that OPOs produce a large number of entangled states and entangled states are critical for making a computer to work as a quantum computer. As previously told, we will return later to Borealis and the states of light it uses for the calculation.

Qubits and quantum gates

Qubits

Let's now introduce some basic notions.

The term "bit" is used to define the basic unit of information in computer science and digital communication. The name is a fusion of two terms: "binary" and "digit". In computer science it is a digit of the binary number system, 0 and 1. In information theory it is the minimum amount of information needed to distinguish between two equiprobable events. To define the qubit, it is essential to introduce the concept of quantum of information. Just as the bit is the quantum of information of classical computation, so quantum computation is based on an analogous concept: the quantum bit (qubit). Like the bit, the qubit is a mathematical object with given properties. The advantage of treating qubits as mathematical entities leads to the possibility of building a theory of quantum computation that does not depend on the specific systems used for its realization. Therefore, a qubit is represented by a unit vector in a Hilbert space. As the bit possesses two states 0 and 1, the same happens for qubit. By analogy with the classical case we will call these two states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$.

Due to the superposition principle, it exists the combination $\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$. Then, the quantum state of a qubit is given by a unit vector in a two-dimensional Hilbert space, with basis $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. This is known as the computational basis. In the classical case, it is always possible to examine the state of the system, and determine it as 0 or 1. In the quantum case, it is impossible to determine the state of the qubit by means of a single measurement, obtaining coefficients α and β . When we measure the qubit in the computational basis, the measure gives $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$. After the measurement the qubit has been collapsed in one of the state of the basis. If we prepare N times the qubit in the same initial state $\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$ and make N times the measurement, we obtain the statistics about α, β coefficients.

Bloch sphere

From <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qubit> . A pure qubit state is a **coherent** superposition of the basis states. This means that a single qubit can be described by a linear combination of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$:

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$$

where α and β are the probability amplitudes, that are both complex numbers. When we measure this qubit in the standard basis, according to the Born rule, the probability of outcome $|0\rangle$ with value "0" is $|\alpha|^2$ and the probability of outcome $|1\rangle$ with value "1" is $|\beta|^2$. Because the absolute squares of the amplitudes equate to probabilities, it follows that:

$$|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$$

The probability amplitudes encode more than just the probabilities of the outcomes of a measurement; the relative phase between α and β is for example responsible for quantum interference.

The possible quantum states for a single qubit can be visualised using a Bloch sphere (see picture). The "North Pole" and the "South Pole" can be used to represent $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ respectively. This particular choice of the polar axis is arbitrary, however. A pure qubit state can be represented by any point on the surface. For example, the pure qubit state $(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$ would lie on the equator of the sphere at the positive x-axis. Let us stress that the surface of the Bloch sphere is a two-dimensional space, which represents the observable state space of the pure qubit states. This state space has two local degrees of freedom, which can be represented by the two angles in the figure.

Bloch sphere representation of a qubit. The probability amplitudes for the superposition state, $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$, are given by $\alpha = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$ and $\beta = e^{i\varphi} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$

Image courtesy Smite-Meister - Own work for Wikipedia.

Let us continue the discussion about the Bloch sphere, also known as Poincaré-Bloch sphere.

The previous image is adapted according to notation in *Quantum Information, An Overview*, Gregg Jaeger, 2007, ISBN: 9780387369440, 0387369449, Publisher: Springer New York. In the book is it stressed that the "pure qubit states, $P(|\psi(\theta, \phi)\rangle)$ lie on the periphery, known as the Poincaré-Bloch sphere. The, $\rho(r, \theta, \phi)$ mixed qubit states, lie in the interior and are weighted convex combinations of pure states."

"The pure states of the qubit can be represented by vectors in the two-dimensional complex Hilbert space, $H=C^2$. Any orthonormal basis for this space can be put in correspondence with two bit values, 0 and 1, in order to act as the single-qubit computational basis, sometimes also called rectilinear basis, and written $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ ".

The superposition principle implies that any complex linear combination of qubit basis states, $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$, with $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$ is also a physical state of a qubit and also a pure state. The scalar coefficients are referred as quantum probability, amplitudes.

$|\alpha|^2, |\beta|^2$ are the probabilities to find, after a measurement, states $|0\rangle, |1\rangle$ respectively. In the figure we can find represented, besides the computational basis, the diagonal basis and the circular basis:

$$\begin{aligned} |\nearrow\rangle &\equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle) & |\searrow\rangle &\equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle) \\ |r\rangle &\equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + i|1\rangle) & |l\rangle &\equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - i|1\rangle) \end{aligned}$$

Algebra (one or two qubits)

For the algebra of qubits, see for instance the lessons about Quantum Computing, 2006-07, by Anuj Dawar, University of Cambridge, link

<https://www.cl.cam.ac.uk/teaching/2006/QuantComp/> or [Archive](#).

Let us assume qubit state $|i\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$. We can act on it by means of the matrices:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & i \\ -i & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

For instance: $X|i\rangle = X(\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle) = \beta|0\rangle + \alpha|1\rangle = |f\rangle$ and so on.

Matrices X , Y and Z are the Pauli matrices, also written as $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$. We can find them in Schrödinger–Pauli equations for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles. In quantum computing, the Pauli matrices become quantum gates operating on single qubit. X operator is the *NOT* gate.

The Hadamard operator is given by: $H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$. It is also known as $\sqrt{\text{NOT}}$ gate.

Phase shift operator is: $R_\theta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{2\pi i \theta} \end{bmatrix}$, with phase shift θ .

Then, we have rotations:

$$R_x(\theta) = \exp(-iX\theta/2) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) & -i\sin(\theta/2) \\ -i\sin(\theta/2) & \cos(\theta/2) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_y(\theta) = \exp(-iY\theta/2) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) & -\sin(\theta/2) \\ \sin(\theta/2) & \cos(\theta/2) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_z(\theta) = \exp(-iZ\theta/2) = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(-i\theta/2) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp(i\theta/2) \end{bmatrix}$$

Let us consider two qubits.

From <https://docs.microsoft.com/it-it/azure/quantum/concepts-multiple-qubits>

The computational basis of the states of two qubits is given by tensor products:

$$00 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad 01 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$10 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad 11 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The basis can be given also by the ket notation, $|00\rangle$, $|01\rangle$, $|10\rangle$, $|11\rangle$, as in the following example:

$$|00\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

In “Quantum Computing”, Appunti delle lezioni di Alessandra Di Pierro <http://groups.di.unipi.it/~dipierro/Didattica/QC05/LezioniQC-05.pdf>, the basis is also written as $|x, y\rangle$, which means $|x\rangle \otimes |y\rangle$, tensor product of $|x\rangle$ and $|y\rangle$.
A quantum register is given by:

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha_{00}|00\rangle + \alpha_{01}|01\rangle + \alpha_{10}|10\rangle + \alpha_{11}|11\rangle,$$

normalized to 1.

Let us consider the initial state:

$$|i\rangle = \alpha|00\rangle + \beta|01\rangle + \gamma|10\rangle + \delta|11\rangle.$$

On it, we can apply CNOT matrix given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore:

$$CNOT|i\rangle = CNOT(\alpha|00\rangle + \beta|01\rangle + \gamma|10\rangle + \delta|11\rangle) = \alpha|00\rangle + \beta|01\rangle + \delta|10\rangle + \gamma|11\rangle$$

CNOT means controlled-NOT (https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Porta_NOT_controllata).

The SWAP gate is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

If we have two qubits and we want to apply the gate on just one of them, we use the property:

$$(M \otimes N)(v \otimes w) = (Mv) \otimes (Nw) \quad ,$$

where M, N are operators and v, w vectors.

Let us consider the identity, so that $M = I$:

$$(I \otimes N)(v \otimes w) = (Iv) \otimes (Nw) = v \otimes (Nw)$$

In the case $N = I$:

$$(M \otimes I)(v \otimes w) = (Mv) \otimes (Iw) = (Mv) \otimes w \quad .$$

Bell states

Bell states are four states for a system made by two qubits, given by:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle) \quad ; \quad |\Phi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle - |11\rangle) \\ |\Psi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|01\rangle + |10\rangle) \quad ; \quad |\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|01\rangle - |10\rangle) \end{aligned}$$

To have Bell states from quantum circuits, it is used the Hadamard operator and a CNOT gate. Let us start from state $|00\rangle$, and apply H to the first qubit. We have:

$$\frac{(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)|0\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

By applying $CNOT$, we have:

$$\frac{(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}} \quad ,$$

which is the $|\Phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$ state.

Product states

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_entanglement#Pure_states

Let us consider two arbitrary quantum systems A and B , with their respective Hilbert spaces H_A and H_B . The Hilbert space of the composite system is the tensor product

$H_A \otimes H_B$. If we have $|\psi_A\rangle$ and $|\psi_B\rangle$ states, then the system is in the state:

$$|\psi_A\rangle \otimes |\psi_B\rangle .$$

The states of the composite system which can be represented in this form are called separable states, or product states. Let us note that not all states are separable states (and thus product states).

Entanglement

In “Quantum Computing”, Appunti delle lezioni di Alessandra Di Piero

<http://groups.di.unipi.it/~dipierro/Didattica/QC05/LezioniQC-05.pdf> we can find that an entangled state cannot be written as a direct tensor product. In an example, it is considered the state $|00\rangle + |11\rangle$, that cannot be factorized. Then:

$$|00\rangle + |11\rangle \neq (a_1|0\rangle + b_1|1\rangle) \otimes (a_2|0\rangle + b_2|1\rangle)$$

Controlled operators

Let U be a unitary operator: $U = \begin{bmatrix} x_{00} & x_{01} \\ x_{10} & x_{11} \end{bmatrix}$.

A “controlled-U gate” is a gate working on two qubits. One of them is the control:

$$CU = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_{00} & x_{01} \\ 0 & 0 & x_{10} & x_{11} \end{bmatrix}$$

An uncontrolled operator is $I \otimes U$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{00} & x_{01} & 0 & 0 \\ x_{10} & x_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_{00} & x_{01} \\ 0 & 0 & x_{10} & x_{11} \end{bmatrix}$$

Many qubits

From <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/quantum/concepts-multiple-qubits> ([Archive](#)).

For a many-qubit system we can follow exactly “the same patterns explored in the two-qubit case to build many-qubit quantum states from smaller systems. Such states are built by forming tensor products of smaller states. For example, consider encoding the bit string 1011001 in a quantum computer”. We can encode this as for instance:

$$1011001 \equiv \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Quantum gates work in exactly the same way. For example, if we wish to apply the X gate to the first qubit and then perform a CNOT between the second and third qubits, we can write:

$$(X \otimes CNOT_{23} \otimes I \otimes I \otimes I \otimes I) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \equiv 0011001$$

X acts on the first vector, $CNOT_{23}$ on the second and third vectors.

Quantum circuit diagrams (Azure Quantum)

From <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/quantum/concepts-circuits>

"This article covers conventions for quantum circuit diagrams. Some quantum algorithms are easier to understand in a circuit diagram than in the equivalent written matrix representation once you understand the visual conventions. With Azure Quantum, you can use the azure-quantum Python package to submit quantum circuits with Qiskit, Cirq, and also provider-specific formatted circuits."

Here some information.

"In a circuit diagram, each solid line depicts a qubit, or more generally, a qubit register. By convention, the top line is qubit register 0 and the remainder qubits are labeled sequentially. Operations are represented by quantum gates. The term quantum gate is analogous to classical logic gates. Gates acting on one or more qubit registers are denoted as a box. For example, the symbol

is a Hadamard operation acting on a single-qubit register."

"In a quantum circuit, time flows from left to right. Quantum gates are ordered in chronological order with the left-most gate as the gate first applied to the qubits. In other words, if you picture the wires as holding the quantum state, the wires bring the quantum state through each of the gates in the diagram from left to right."

Quantum Inspire

See also Quantum Inspire, <https://www.quantum-inspire.com>

“Quantum Inspire (QI) is a quantum computing platform designed and built by QuTech. The goal of Quantum Inspire is to provide users access to various technologies to perform quantum computations and insights in principles of quantum computing and access to the community. Quantum Inspire (QI) is initiated by QuTech the advanced research center for quantum computing and quantum internet founded by TU Delft and TNO.” [archive](#)

Hadamard gate at <https://www.quantum-inspire.com/kbase/hadamard/>

The Hadamard gate is a single-qubit operation that maps the basis state $|0\rangle$ to $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $|1\rangle$ to $\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$, thus creating an equal superposition of the two basis states.

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let us note that $H^2|\psi\rangle = H H|\psi\rangle = I|\psi\rangle = |\psi\rangle$.

Examples:

```
1 H q[0] # execute Hadamard gate on qubit 0
2 H q[1:2,5] # execute Hadamard gate on qubits 1,2 and 5
```

CNOT symbol is:

CNOT gate is represented by a vertical line between the control qubit (\bullet) and the target qubit (\oplus).

In <https://www.quantum-inspire.com/kbase/cnot/> we can find the two-qubit entanglement command.

```
1 version 1.0
2 qubits 2
3 H q[0] # execute Hadamard gate on qubit 0 to create a superposition
4 CNOT q[0], q[1] # entangle both qubits using CNOT gate
```

Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger state

It is an “entangled quantum state that involves at least three subsystems (particle states, or qubits). It was first studied by Daniel Greenberger, Michael Horne and Anton Zeilinger in 1989”. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger_state .

With three qubits: $|GZH\rangle = \frac{|000\rangle + |111\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$,

Courtesy image Ommissiahs hierophant - LaTeX qcircuit script

GHZ state example

From <https://quantum-computing.ibm.com/composer/docs/iqx/example-circuits#ghz-state-example> . This circuit creates a GHZ state and then measures all qubits in the standard basis. The measured results should be half 000 and half 111.

“The measured results should be half 000 and half 111”. “Results”, not “result”. Before the measurements of qubits, the system is in the state:

$$|GZH\rangle = \frac{|000\rangle + |111\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

When we make the measurement, the system collapses into state 000 or state 111. We cannot

make just one measurement. It is not possible to make a few measurements; at least a hundred tests are required. And then, it is necessary that the initial state of the three qubits is always the same (in a reasonable manner), and that the state of the qubits lives long enough to be able to apply operations given in the figure.

We are ready for DiVincenzo's criteria.

DiVincenzo's criteria

The “DiVincenzo's criteria” are conditions necessary for constructing a quantum computer. These conditions had been proposed in 2000 by the theoretical physicist David P. DiVincenzo, in *The Physical Implementation of Quantum Computation*, Fortschritte der Physik. 48 (9–11): 771–783 (see also arXiv:quant-ph/0002077). There are seven criteria, but here only the five related to quantum computation are considered. The other two concern to quantum communication.

Let's take the criteria as formulated by DiVincenzo in his 2000 work.

- 1) A scalable physical system with well-characterized qubit
- 2) The ability to initialize the state of the qubits to a simple fiducial state, such as $|000\dots\rangle$
- 3) Long relevant decoherence times, much longer than the gate operation time
- 4) A "universal" set of quantum gates
- 5) A qubit-specific measurement capability

The first condition says that we must have qubits, created by means of a physical system, which are clearly defined through physical characterizations. The qubit number can be scalable, in the sense that it is possible to create systems having increasing computing capacity. The second point, like the third, is important. Since we have to repeat the calculation many times (see the previous example), the initial state is prepared many times. The initial state, for example $|000\dots\rangle$, must always be the same, within a certain level of trust. The third point says that the state must live long enough to be able to apply an operator on it. With a set of operators, the quantum gates, we can act on the initial state to obtain the final state. The last step concerns the measurement. The final result is a set of bits and therefore a measurement is needed to transform quantum information into binary information.

In 4), there is the adjective "universal". Let us recall what was initially said about the simulation of a physical system. The Hamiltonian of the physical system must be translated into another Hamiltonian, suitable to be used with the system of qubits.

“In all the physical implementations discussed in this volume, - DiVincenzo tells - only particular sorts of Hamiltonians can be turned on and off; in most cases, for example, only two-body (two-qubit) interactions are considered. This immediately poses a problem for a quantum computation specified with three-qubit unitary transformations; fortunately, of course, these can always be re-expressed in terms of sequences of one- and two-body interactions, and the two-body interactions can be of just one type, the “quantum XOR” or “CNOT”. There are some implementations in which multi-qubit gates can be implemented directly” [DiVincenzo].

“In many cases it is impossible to turn on the desired interaction between a pair of qubits; for

instance, in the ion-trap scheme, no direct interaction is available between the ion-level qubits. In this and in other cases, a special quantum subsystem (sometimes referred to as a “bus qubit”) is used which can interact with each of the qubits in turn and mediate the desired interaction: for the ion trap, this is envisioned to be the vibrational state of the ion chain in the trap; in other cases it is a cavity photon whose wavefunction overlaps all the qubits. Unfortunately, this auxiliary quantum system introduces new channels for the environment to couple to the system and cause decoherence, and indeed the decoherence occurring during gate operation is of concern in the iontrap and cavity-quantum electrodynamics schemes.” [DiVincenzo]

Can we always translate a Hamiltonian into a set of quantum gate operations, so that the computation by means of qubits is sustainable? This is a question related to the "universality".

Teleportation

Considering again the quantum circuits, let's see the example of teleportation circuit, assuming it as given in <https://docs.microsoft.com/it-it/azure/quantum/concepts-circuits>

From Baur, M., et al. (2012). *Benchmarking a quantum teleportation protocol in superconducting circuits using tomography and an entanglement witness*, Physical Review Letters, 108(4), 040502. “In the standard protocol, teleportation is performed using non-local quantum correlations combined with classical communication. In this scheme, the sender is in possession of qubit A in an arbitrary state $|\psi_A\rangle$. In the first step (I), a maximally entangled pair is generated, e.g. using a Hadamard (H) gate followed by a controlled-not (CNOT) gate, and shared between the sender (qubit B) and the receiver (qubit C). In the second step (II) the sender applies a CNOT gate on his two qubits followed by a H gate on qubit A generating an entangled three-qubit state $|\tilde{\Phi}\rangle$. In step III, the sender performs a measurement on his two qubits, which combined with step II is equivalent to a measurement performed in the Bell basis. He then sends the digital results to the receiver over a classical communication channel. Depending on these results, the receiver applies one of four unitary operations to his qubit to transform the state $|\psi_C\rangle$ of qubit C into the state $|\psi_A\rangle$ completing the teleportation.”

Here in the following the circuit as proposed by Microsoft (numbers and operators are added to the circuit):

Also in [stackexchange](#) ([Archive](#)) the circuit is discussed. The web page is giving a series of operations. The first is H applied to qubit 2.

Then:

$$I \otimes H_2 \otimes I \left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \left(H_2 \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We apply CNOT to qubits 2 and 3:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} I \otimes C_{2,3} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes C_{2,3} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Then CNOT on 1 and 2: $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \alpha \\ \beta \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$, and rewriting:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} &+ \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

H is applied on 1:

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\beta}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\alpha}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ + \frac{\beta}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

so that:

$$\frac{\alpha}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\alpha}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\alpha}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\alpha}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ + \frac{\beta}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \frac{\beta}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\beta}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} - \frac{\beta}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The final vector is therefore:

$$= \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \beta \\ \alpha \\ -\beta \\ -\beta \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} = |\psi\rangle$$

And this is the result we can find in [stackexchange](#) . In ket notation:

$$|\psi\rangle = (\alpha/2) |000\rangle + (\alpha/2) |100\rangle + (\alpha/2) |011\rangle + (\alpha/2) |111\rangle + (\beta/2) |010\rangle \\ - (\beta/2) |110\rangle + (\beta/2) |001\rangle - (\beta/2) |101\rangle$$

Let us assume qubits “1” and “2” possessed by Alice, and qubit “3” possessed by Bob. We can write $|\psi\rangle$ as:

$$|\psi\rangle = 1/2 (|00\rangle(\alpha|0\rangle+\beta|1\rangle) + |01\rangle(\alpha|1\rangle+\beta|0\rangle) + |10\rangle(\alpha|0\rangle-\beta|1\rangle) + |11\rangle(\alpha|1\rangle-\beta|0\rangle))$$

Alice measures her two qubits and send information to Bob via classical bits. Bob has his qubit. Alice's measurements give one of the states $|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle$. After the measure, the state of Bob qubit turns into:

$$|00\rangle \rightarrow (\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle) \quad ; \quad |01\rangle \rightarrow (\alpha|1\rangle + \beta|0\rangle) \\ |10\rangle \rightarrow (\alpha|0\rangle - \beta|1\rangle) \quad ; \quad |11\rangle \rightarrow (\alpha|1\rangle - \beta|0\rangle)$$

Then, if Alice obtains from the measurement 00, Bob's qubit turns into $\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$. Since Alice and Bob know the classical bits, by applying the proper gates, Bob can obtain the initial Alice's qubit.

Bob's State	Bits Received	Gate Applied
$(\alpha 0\rangle + \beta 1\rangle)$	00	I
$(\alpha 1\rangle + \beta 0\rangle)$	01	X
$(\alpha 0\rangle - \beta 1\rangle)$	10	Z
$(\alpha 1\rangle - \beta 0\rangle)$	11	ZX

<https://qiskit.org/textbook/ch-algorithms/teleportation.html>

Let us consider again the circuit:

The single lines represent quantum registers (qubits). The double lines represent classical bits. The symbol used for the measure is intuitive. If the bit is 0, the operator X or Z is not applied, if the bit is 1 the operator is applied to the register. In this manner, we have the table given above.

Entangling photons

In the previous teleportation example, we used Hadamard and CNOT gates acting on the three registers. It is therefore a question of using a device with three physical qubits and related physical operations on them. One can rely, for example, on an IBM quantum computer. But the entanglement of qubits is not the only possible one. We can use photons. In 1997, experimental photon teleportation tests were carried out. Two research groups presented their research in *Experimental Realization of Teleporting an Unknown Pure Quantum State via Dual Classical and Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen Channels*, D. Boschi et al., published in Physical Review Letters, 80(6), 1121. arXiv:quant-ph/9710013, and *Experimental quantum teleportation*, Dik Bouwmeester et al., Nature, 390(6660), 575-579, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1901.11004>. The abstract of the latter article tells: “Quantum teleportation – the transmission and reconstruction over arbitrary distances of the state of a quantum system – is demonstrated

experimentally. During teleportation, an initial photon which carries the polarization that is to be transferred and one of a pair of entangled photons are subjected to a measurement such that the second photon of the entangled pair acquires the polarization of the initial photon. This latter photon can be arbitrarily far away from the initial one. Quantum teleportation will be a critical ingredient for quantum computation networks.”

Figure 1, in the article by Dik Bouwmeester et al., gives a scheme for experiment and its set-up. About the set-up, authors tell that “A pulse of ultraviolet radiation passing through a nonlinear crystal creates the ancillary pair of photons 2 and 3. After retroreflection during its second passage through the crystal the ultraviolet pulse creates another pair of photons, one of which will be prepared in the initial state of photon 1 to be teleported, the other one serving as a trigger indicating that a photon to be teleported is under way. Alice then looks for coincidences after a beam splitter BS where the initial photon and one of the ancillaries are superposed. Bob, after receiving the classical information that Alice obtained a coincidence count in detectors f1 and f2 identifying the $|\psi^-\rangle_{12}$ Bell state, knows that his photon 3 is in the initial state of photon 1 which he then can check using polarization analysis with the polarizing beam splitter PBS and the detectors d1 and d2. The detector p provides the information that photon 1 is under way.”

The entangled state is: $|\psi^-\rangle_{12} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H_1\rangle|V_2\rangle - |V_1\rangle|H_2\rangle)$, according to the base of

horizontally and vertically polarized states. The article by Dik Bouwmeester et al., in Nature, does not provide detail about the non-linear crystal, but mentions article by Kwiat, P. G., et al., *New high-intensity source of polarization-entangled photon pairs*, Physical Review Letters.

“The desired polarization-entangled state is produced directly out of a single nonlinear crystal [BBO (beta-barium borate) in our experiment], with no need for extra beam splitters or mirrors and no requirement of discarding detected pairs to observe nonlocal correlations. Verifying the correlations produced by the novel source, we have observed strong violations of Bell's inequalities (modulo the typical auxiliary assumptions), in some cases by more than 100 standard deviations. Using two extra birefringent elements, one can easily produce any of the four orthogonal "EPR-Bell states".” It is mentioned the article by Braunstein, S. L. et al., *Maximal violation of Bell inequalities for mixed states*.

The four states are:

$$|\psi^\pm\rangle_{12} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H_1\rangle|V_2\rangle \pm |V_1\rangle|H_2\rangle)$$

$$|\phi^\pm\rangle_{12} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H_1\rangle|H_2\rangle \pm |V_1\rangle|V_2\rangle)$$

Optics and satellites

“Per la prima volta, il teletrasporto quantistico ‘viaggia’ attraverso la fibra ottica. Due differenti studi sono riusciti a trasmettere dati criptati attraverso la fibra ottica rendendo sempre più accessibile il teletrasporto quantistico”, Zeina Ayache, 20 settembre 2016. Fanpage,

<https://archive.ph/1K9Sh> . “Due differenti esperimenti hanno dimostrato che è possibile inviare dati criptati, codificati in particelle di luce, attraverso la rete di fibre ottiche “di casa”: insomma, il teletrasporto quantistico di cui si parla dagli anni '90 potrebbe essere finalmente realtà e l'attuare trasmissione di dati potrebbe prepararsi ad una svolta. I due studi in questione sono comparsi su Nature Photonics sotto il titolo di “Quantum teleportation with independent sources and prior entanglement distribution over a network”, della University of Science and Technology of China, e “Quantum teleportation across a metropolitan fibre network”, dell'Institute for Quantum Science and Technology, and Department of Physics & Astronomy della University of Calgary. ... il “passaggio di informazioni è criptato e dipende dalle leggi dei quanti che impediscono agli hacker di intervenire senza modificare il messaggio stesso, che quindi o cambia o si autodistrugge. Se a questa tipologia di comunicazione accostiamo l'utilizzo della fibra ottica, otteniamo una modalità di trasmissione sicura, ma anche estremamente rapida. ... Nel frattempo, sempre in Cina, procedono i test sulla comunicazione quantistica via satellite che dovrebbero fornirci la possibilità di un sistema di trasmissione inviolabile entro il 2020.”

Here the translation of the passages from the article published in 2016.

For the first time, quantum teleportation 'travels' through a fiber-optic network. Two different studies have managed to transmit encrypted data through it, making quantum teleportation more accessible. Two different experiments have shown that it is possible to send encrypted data, encoded in particles of light, through the fiber-optic network: in short, the quantum teleportation could finally be a reality and such implementing of data transmission is ready for a breakthrough. The two mentioned studies appeared in Nature Photonics under the title of "Quantum teleportation with independent sources and prior entanglement distribution over a network", University of Science and Technology of China, and "Quantum teleportation across a metropolitan fiber network", Institute for Quantum Science and Technology, and Department of Physics & Astronomy of the University of Calgary. The information is encrypted and depends on quantum laws that prevent hackers from intervening without modifying the message itself, which therefore is either changed or destroyed. If we combine the use of the fiber-optical network with this type of communication, we obtain a secure and extremely fast transmission method. Meanwhile, in China, tests are proceeding on quantum communication via satellite which should provide us with the possibility of an inviolable transmission system by **2020**.

We can find information in “Chinese Scientists Just Set the Record for the Farthest Quantum Teleportation”, Jesse Emspak, published July 15, **2017**, Space.com. <https://archive.ph/GPZUU> . The researchers “sent a packet of information from Tibet to a satellite in orbit, up to 870 miles (1,400 kilometers) above the Earth's surface. More specifically, the scientists beamed the quantum state of a photon (information about how it is polarized) into orbit. Not only did the team set a record for quantum teleportation distance, they also showed that one can build a practical system for long-distance quantum communications. Such a communication system would be impossible to eavesdrop on without alerting the users, which would make online communications much more secure”.

Toffoli Gate

Let us consider again the quantum gates.

Da https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Toffoli_gate

“In logic circuits, the Toffoli gate (also CCNOT gate), invented by Tommaso Toffoli, is a universal reversible logic gate, which means that any classical reversible circuit can be constructed from Toffoli gates. It is also known as the "controlled-controlled-not" gate, which describes its action. It has 3-bit inputs and outputs; if the first two bits are both set to 1, it inverts the third bit, otherwise all bits stay the same.”

The image is courtesy by Geek3 - Own work Created in LaTeX using Q-circuit.

“Quantum circuit diagram constructing a Toffoli gate from single-qubit operations and six controlled NOT (CNOT) gates. This is the minimum number of CNOTs required to build a Toffoli.” It is mentioned the Technical Report MIT/LCS/TM-151 (1980) and an adapted and condensed version: Toffoli, Tommaso (1980). J. W. de Bakker and J. van Leeuwen (ed.). Reversible computing. Automata, Languages and Programming, Seventh Colloquium. Noordwijkerhout, Netherlands: Springer Verlag. pp. 632–644. doi:10.1007/3-540-10003-2_104. ISBN 3-540-10003-2.

Qubit Computers

Qubits are handled by quantum computers, which are therefore sets of qubits that evolve in a quantum way, when they are in conditions of negligible external influence. A quantum algorithm is needed to operate. Theoretically, the quantum computer can perform some calculations, such as the factorization of integers into prime numbers, much faster than any classical computer, being able to use algorithms such as Shor's factorization. The speed-up of the calculation is said to be "exponential".

Currently, the main problem of the quantum computer is the errors caused by external effects, that is by the “decoherence”. It is impossible to eliminate decoherence completely. Quantum error correction is used to control decoherence with the encoding of qubits in spaces with a larger dimension. As in the classic case, therefore, redundancy is used.

Qumodes

Let us now turn to quantum computing with a continuous variable. The CVQC calculation was proposed in 1999 by Lloyd and Braunstein. In its optical implementation, the quantum variables are the amplitude and phase of the electromagnetic field. Pfister defines them as:

$$Q = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(a + a^\dagger) \quad , \quad P = \frac{1}{i\sqrt{2}}(a - a^\dagger)$$

Here we can see immediately the quantum oscillator, with creation and annihilation operators. The variables are in quadrature.

A correspondence between qubits and qumodes is given by Pfister in a table, a part of which is here reproduced.

Qubit-based	Qumode-based
<i>Computational basis</i>	
$\{ 0\rangle, 1\rangle\}$ $\langle k \ell \rangle = \delta_{k\ell}, k, \ell \in \{0, 1\}$ $ \psi\rangle = \psi_0 0\rangle + \psi_1 1\rangle$	$\{ q\rangle\}_{q \in \mathbb{R}}$ $\langle q q' \rangle = \delta(q - q'), q, q' \in \mathbb{R}$ $ \psi\rangle = \int dq \psi(q) q\rangle$
<i>Conjugate basis</i>	
Hadamard transformed $ \pm\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0\rangle \pm 1\rangle)$	Fourier transformed $ p\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int e^{ipq} q\rangle dq, \quad p \in \mathbb{R}$

Qumodes vs Qubits

From “Qumodes vs. Qubits explained, part I”, di Jelmer Renema, 3 November 2020, [quixquantum-medium](#) (archiviato [Archive](#)). The question most often asked Renema is to explain how QuiX (which is a photonic computer) works with respect to a qubit system. The short answer is that QuiX uses and manipulates qumodes.

“To make the difference clear, I [Renema] need to introduce the notion of an encoding. An encoding is some way of taking information from the outside world and representing it in the hardware of your computer”. In a classical computer, the memory consists of n bits, which can be 0 or 1. Then it is possible to memorize binary numbers from 0 to $2^n - 1$. In this manner, we represent an external mode (a number) into the computer.

“It is important to note that such an encoding is not unique ... However, you are not completely free, because the limitations of your computer system limit what you can encode. ... So in summary, what we’ve learned from considering this simple classical case is that you can encode

things into a computer in different ways, but that the number of things you can encode is limited by the state space of the computer. Next, we'll consider what happens when you add quantum to the story.”

By means of qubits, it is true that a qubit has an infinite number of possible states, but what we need is the basis of the space of states. For a qubit the basis is made up of two states: let's say them up and down. Let us continue with the use of the classical analogy: “each qubit therefore has 2 ‘possible assignments’, and you have n of them, so by the arguments presented above, there are 2^n unique states. Because we are doing quantum mechanics, superpositions of these states are also allowed, but that doesn't change the picture: the dimensionality of the system is still 2^n .”

“For qumodes, the picture is a bit more complicated.” Changing a little bit Renema' argument: a qumode is the state of a “quantum-mechanical harmonic oscillator”. Limiting the dimensions of an oscillator, we pass from the continuum to the discrete state-space. “It is these quantum states which we will use to encode our information”. QuiX uses light, the electromagnetic field quantized. The field becomes a set of quanta, known as photons.

“For the case of light, the states of the harmonic oscillator can also be thought of as corresponding to a given number of photons, which are (loosely said) particles of light". The quantum-mechanical dynamics is described by means of the number distribution of photons. And “there is the possibility of superposition, and if you think about more than one optical mode, there is also the possibility of entanglement. The way to think about qumodes is that they are the world in which the photons live.”

“Things get really interesting if you start considering systems of more than one qumode. ... If you bring two qumodes in contact with each other, then photons can jump from one qumode to the other. ... If there are photons in both qumodes, then generally such an interaction results in entanglement, i.e. in a joint state between the two qumodes”.

Let us also stress that, “Unlike qubits, the basis of a single qumode contains infinitely many states, since the qumode can contain an arbitrary number of photons. However in practice, a photonic processor will always be run with some states with a finite energy, meaning that there is a limit on the number photons that can be present (because making a photon costs energy)”.

Let us we have a finite number n of photons. If we consider N qumodes, then:

$$\binom{N+n-1}{n}$$

This is the number of modes in which we can have the distribution. “This is a very different answer than the one we got in the qubit case. This highlights an important difference between qumodes and qubits: the way their state spaces are structured is completely different. A simple counting argument shows that there isn't a one-to-one equivalence between qumodes and qubits”.

Qubit computers

Models of quantum computation

Quantum computing is theoretically given by an algebra, but how can it be physically achieved? Quantum computation models are as follows, according to David Vitali, 2018.

- 1) Arrays of logic gates with a few qubits
- 2) One-way quantum computer
- 3) Adiabatic quantum computer or “Quantum annealing”
- 4) Topological quantum computer (braiding of anyons in a bidimensional system)

Here some details about the four models mentioned by Vitali.

1) Arrays of gates with two or more qubits. Any quantum circuit can always be decomposed efficiently and with arbitrary precision into a finite number of elements of a universal set (for example, a universal two-qubit gate CNOT).

From the Quantum Computing Tutorial TIM, link [gruppotim](#), 2020 ([Archive](#)).

“Il computer quantistico basato su modello Quantum Gate Array (QGA) è caratterizzato dall’esecuzione di operazioni sotto forma di porte quantistiche - una sorta di estensione al qubit della progettazione logica dell’elettronica digitale classica - con le quali è possibile approssimare tutte le possibili evoluzioni unitarie di un sistema quantistico ... Questo modello assume dal punto di vista hardware che l’unità di esecuzione costituisca l’unica sezione prettamente quantistica del calcolatore. A differenza delle porte logiche classiche, che possono essere progettate con un opportuno circuito a transistor, le porte quantistiche sono implementate da campi elettromagnetici oscillanti ad una frequenza di risonanza caratteristica di ciascun qubit costituente l’hardware e il cui valore assoluto dipende dalla tecnologia di fabbricazione (per esempio per i qubit superconduttivi nella banda delle microonde, per gli ioni intrappolati nella stessa banda o addirittura in banda ottica)”. The quantum computer based on the Quantum Gate Array (QGA) model is characterized by the execution of operations in the form of quantum gates - a sort of extension to qubits of the logical design of classical digital electronics - by means of which it is possible to approximate all possible evolutions of a quantum system... From hardware point of view, this model assumes that the processing unit is a pure quantum part of the computer. Unlike the classical logic gates, which can be designed with a suitable transistor circuit, the quantum gates are implemented by electromagnetic fields oscillating at a resonant frequency, specific of each qubit, and depending on the manufacturing technology. For example, in the case of superconducting qubits, the frequency is in the microwave band, for trapped ions it is in the same band or even in the optical band.

2) One-way QC (or measurement-based QC). It works using states of a graph or cluster, subjected to sequences of single qubit measurements (generally conditioned by the result of the

previous measurements). The program is the sequence of measures: the “resource” is the initial "graph state", prepared as highly “entangled”.

See please https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/One-way_quantum_computer

We find that an implementation of this type of computer is possible through "Linear optical quantum computing" or "Linear optics quantum computation" (LOQC), a quantum computation paradigm, which uses photons with linear optical elements and photon detectors. The reference is Daniel E. Browne, Terry Rudolph (2005). *Resource-efficient linear optical quantum computation*. Physical Review Letters. 95 (1): 010501.

3) Adiabatic quantum computation or Quantum annealing. The calculation takes place through the evolution from the initial state to the desired final state, carried out as an adiabatic process in the minimum energy state of the processor (Fahri et al., 2000, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.quant-ph/0001106>). The computers are the D-Wave systems.

4) Topological quantum computer. The gate is a "braid" between two "anyons", particles in a 2D system. It is a robust system with respect to decoherence, because the gate depends only on the topological properties of the braid and not on perturbations. It can be made by 2D GaAs semiconductors in magnetic field. This model is pursued by Microsoft (Majorana Fermions).

Qubits (array) and qubits (annealing)

There are qubit systems where the evolution of the calculation occurs through an array of quantum gates (such as IBM) and there are qubit computers where the calculation takes place with Quantum Annealing. The first qubit systems, which evolve through an array of quantum gates, are certainly the best known systems. In Quantum Annealing the evolution of the quantum system occurs from the ground state of one Hamiltonian to a ground state of another Hamiltonian. The latter state is the one that represents the solution to the problem. The transition takes place through the application of bias and couplers (as in the D-Wave systems). There are therefore two different strategies.

As summarized by Vitali, in the case of a quantum annealing, the calculation is the evolution from an initial state to a final desired state, realized as an adiabatic evolution, always in the equilibrium state at minimum energy of the processor (adiabatic theorem) (Fahri-Goldston, 2000). L' “evoluzione da stato iniziale a stato finale desiderato, realizzato come evoluzione adiabatica sempre nello stato di equilibrio ad energia minima del processore (teorema adiabatico) (Fahri-Goldston, 2000)”.

Calculus with D-Wave computers is available through CINECA.

<https://www.quantumcomputinglab.cineca.it/en/2021/05/12/collaboration-agreement-between-cineca-and-d-wave-for-the-distribution-in-italy-of-quantum-computing-resources/> “CINECA and D-Wave Systems Inc. today announced an agreement to offer free extended access to quantum computing technology and resources to Italian universities, researchers and developers.”

Quest for qubits

Let us see what has been told in the *Quest for qubits: How small startups are vying with corporate behemoths for quantum supremacy*, by Gabriel Popkin, *Science*, 2 Dec 2016, Vol 354, Issue 6316, pp. 1090-1093, DOI: 10.1126/science.354.6316.1090

“Qubits outmuscle classical computer bits thanks to two uniquely quantum effects: superposition and entanglement. Superposition allows a qubit to have a value of not just 0 or 1, but both states at the same time, enabling simultaneous computation. Entanglement enables one qubit to share its state with others separated in space, creating a sort of super-superposition, whereby processing capability doubles with every qubit. An algorithm using, say, five entangled qubits can effectively do 25, or 32, computations at once, whereas a classical computer would have to do those 32 computations in succession. As few as 300 fully entangled qubits could, theoretically, sustain more parallel computations than there are atoms in the universe” [Popkin]. In this brief explanation it is clearly stated where the quantum advantage is: it is mainly in the entanglement. And the preponderant role of the CNOT gate is also clear.

“This massive parallelism would not help with many tasks—nobody thinks quantum computers will revolutionize word processing or email. But it could dramatically speed up algorithms designed to explore vast numbers of different paths simultaneously, and solve problems that include searching through large data sets, discovering new chemical catalysts, and factoring large numbers used to encrypt data. Quantum computers may even find a role simulating black holes and other phenomena in physics” [Popkin].

However, this huge computing power is not easy to obtain.

“There is a major catch, however. Quantum superpositions and entangled states are exquisitely fragile. They can be destroyed by slight perturbations from the environment—or by attempts to measure them. A quantum computer needs protection from what **Robert Schoelkopf**, a physicist at Yale University, calls “a sea of classical chaos.” Though theoretical ideas started appearing in the early 1980s, experimental quantum computing got going only in 1995, after **Peter Shor**, a mathematician at Bell Labs in Murray Hill, New Jersey, showed that a quantum computer could quickly factor large numbers—a capability that would render much of modern cryptography obsolete. Shor and others also showed that it was theoretically possible to keep fragile qubits stable indefinitely by using neighboring qubits to correct their errors” [Popkin].

The error correction, fundamental to keep the qubit system stable, becomes theoretically possible and therefore - Popkin explains - physicists and their financiers have a reason to build a quantum machine, without it dissolving in a cascade of errors.

“**David Wineland**, a Nobel Prize-winning physicist at a National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) laboratory in Boulder, Colorado, had already pioneered methods to use lasers to cool ions and control their internal quantum states”. [Popkin]

David J. Wineland, with a **Serge Haroche**, received in 2012 Nobel Prize for Physics "for ground-breaking experimental methods that enable measuring and manipulation of individual quantum systems." [NobelPrize](#)

“Within a year of Shor's discoveries, **Wineland and Monroe**, a NIST staff scientist at the time, built the first quantum mechanical logic gate, using lasers to manipulate electron states in a beryllium ion. Because of Wineland's experience with ions, the chance to seize the lead in early

quantum computing experiments “fell in our laps,” Monroe says” [Popkin]. Monroe is Christopher Roy Monroe, “an American physicist and engineer in the areas of atomic, molecular, and optical physics and quantum information science, especially quantum computing”. [Wikipedia]

Popkin continues the chronological analysis of quantum computing until 2016, of course. The article also features an illustration showing five models.

“In the race to build a quantum computer, companies are pursuing many types of quantum bits,” and each type has pro and cons. Types are:

1) Superconducting loops. “A resistance-free current oscillates back and forth around a circuit loop. An injected microwave signal excites the current into super-position states.” (Company support: Google, IBM, Quantum Circuits). [Let us add D-Wave to the companies mentioned by Popkin]

2) Trapped ions: “Electrically charged atoms, or ions, have quantum energies that depend on the location of electrons. Tuned lasers cool and trap the ions, and put them in superposition states.” (Company support: IonQ)

3) Silicon quantum dots: “These “artificial atoms” are made by adding an electron to a small piece of pure silicon, Microwaves control the electron’s quantum state.” (Company support: Intel)

4) Topological qubits: “Quasiparticle can be seen in the behaviour of electrons channeled through semiconductor structures. Their braided paths can encode quantum information.” (Company support: Microsoft, Bell Labs)

5) Diamond vacancies: “A nitrogen atom and a vacancy add an electron to a diamond lattice. Its quantum spin state, along with those of nearby carbon nuclei, can be controlled by light.” (Company support: Quantum Diamond Technologies)

Pro and cons are listed in a figure of the “Quest for qubits” by Pokin. Optical computers are not considered by the author. We return to the subject when we see the Borealis chip in detail.

D-Wave

“Quest for qubits” (2016) spoke of the Canadian company D-Wave in this manner. In 2007, D-Wave “surprised just about everybody by announcing that it had built a quantum computer, with 16 superconducting qubits. D-Wave's machine didn't entangle all the qubits, and it couldn't be programmed qubit by qubit. Instead, it relied on a technique called quantum annealing, in which qubits are entangled only with near neighbors and interact to produce not a set of parallel computations, but a single overall quantum state. ... Almost instantly critics cried foul: D-Wave did not even attempt to do certain things that many thought essential to quantum computing, such as error correction. But several companies, including Google and Lockheed Martin, bought

and tested D-Wave devices. A tentative consensus emerged: They did something quantum, and, for certain specialized tasks, they might perform faster than a conventional computer. Quantum or not, D-Wave jolted the private sector awake”. Six years have passed and the D-Wave machines have undergone a remarkable evolution.

Let us then begin to see the annealing system of the D-wave.

D-Wave Systems is a quantum computing company headquartered in Burnaby, British Columbia, Canada. As mentioned in https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/D-Wave_Systems, in 2007, February 13, D-Wave shows the Orion computer applied to three computations at the Computer History Museum in Mountain View, California. An application was a Sudoku puzzle.

Of 2009 it is the publication *Compound Josephson-junction coupler for flux qubits with minimal crosstalk*, by Harris et al., Physical Review B. “An improved tunable coupling element for building networks of coupled rf-superconducting quantum interference device (rf-SQUID) flux qubits has been experimentally demonstrated. This new form of coupler, based on the compound Josephson-junction rf-SQUID, provides a sign and magnitude tunable mutual inductance between qubits with minimal nonlinear crosstalk from the coupler tuning parameter into the qubits”.

In 2011, D-Wave announced the creation of the D-Wave One quantum computer, described as an adiabatic quantum computer that uses quantum annealing to solve optimization problems with a 128 qubit chipset. As noted in Popkin's article, D-Wave announced in May 2013 that NASA and Google had ordered a 512-qubit D-Wave Two. In February 2019 D-Wave announced its next generation "Pegasus" quantum processor chip, with more than 5000 qubits and reduced noise.

Let us add that “The company name [D-wave] refers to their first qubit designs, which used d-wave superconductors.” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/D-Wave_Systems

News of June 2022. “D-Wave launches a first prototype of its next-gen annealing quantum computer”, article by Frederic Lardinois, June 16, 2022, [Techcrunch](#) (archiviato [Archive](#)). “D-Wave made a name for itself with its early annealing quantum computers and even though the company recently announced its efforts to also build a superconducting gate-model quantum computer, it’s not abandoning its quantum annealing technology. Case in point: The company today made the first prototype of its next-gen Advantage2 annealing quantum computer available in its cloud. This is not the full system, which will feature 7,000 qubits when it launches in 2023 or 2024, but a small 500+ qubit version that is meant to showcase the company’s new qubit design and its Zephyr topology ([PDF](#)) with 20-way inter-qubit connectivity”.

From https://docs.dwavesys.com/docs/latest/c_gs_2.html ([Archive](#)). In D-wave, “quantum bits —also known as qubits—are the lowest energy states of the superconducting loops that make up the D-Wave QPU [quantum processing unit]. These states have a circulating current and a corresponding magnetic field. As with classical bits, a qubit can be in state of 0 or 1. *But because the qubit is a quantum object, it can also be in a superposition of the 0 state and the 1 state at the same time.* At the end of the quantum annealing process, each qubit collapses from a superposition state into either 0 or 1 (a classical state).”

“A qubit’s state is implemented as a circulating current, shown clockwise for 0 and counter clockwise for 1, with a corresponding magnetic field.”

“The physics of this process can be shown (visualized) with an energy diagram as in Figure. This diagram changes over time, as shown in (a), (b), and (c). To begin, there is just one valley (a), with a single minimum. The quantum annealing process runs, the barrier is raised, and this turns the energy diagram into what is known as a double-well potential (b). Here, the low point of the left valley corresponds to the 0 state, and the low point of the right valley corresponds to the 1 state. The qubit ends up in one of these valleys at the end of the anneal”.

Applying a magnetic field, the qubit falls in the state 0 or 1 (in the figure in 1). The programmable quantity that controls the external magnetic field is called the “bias”. “The bias term alone is not useful, however. The real power of the qubits comes when you link them together so they can influence each other. This is done with a device called a coupler. A *coupler* can make two qubits tend to end up in the same state—both 0 or both 1—or it can make them tend to be in opposite states. Like a qubit bias, the correlation weights between coupled qubits can be programmed by setting a coupling strength. ... When you use a coupler, you are using another phenomenon of quantum physics called *entanglement*. When two qubits are entangled, they can be thought of as a single object with four possible states. " Actually you can have a potential with four states, each corresponding to a different combination of the two qubits: (0,0), (0,1), (1,1), and (1,0), and so on.

“In summary, the systems starts with a set of qubits, each in a superposition state of 0 and 1. They are not yet coupled. When they undergo quantum annealing, the couplers and biases are introduced and the qubits become entangled. At this point, the system is in an entangled state of many possible answers. By the end of the anneal, each qubit is in a *classical state* that represents the minimum energy state of the problem, or one very close to it. All of this happens in D-Wave quantum computers in a matter of microseconds.”

https://docs.dwavesys.com/docs/latest/c_gs_2.html

“Classical state”. The site is also telling that “At the end of the anneal, the Hamiltonian contains the only B(s) term [we will see in the following that it is an Ising Hamiltonian]. It is a classical Hamiltonian where every possible classical bitstring (that is, list of qubit states that are either 0 or 1) corresponds to an eigenstate and the eigenenergy is the classical energy objective function you have input into the system”.

An application: King, A.D., Suzuki, S., Raymond, J., Zucca, A., Lanting, T., Altomare, F., Berkley, A.J., Ejtemaee, S., Hoskinson, E., Huang, S. and Ladizinsky, E., 2022. *Coherent quantum annealing in a programmable 2000-qubit Ising chain*. ArXiv:2202.05847. DOI <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.05847>

D-Wave Systems

From https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/D-Wave_Systems we have some data.

	D-Wave One	D-Wave Two	D-Wave 2X	D-Wave 2000Q ^{[58][59]}	Advantage ^{[60][61]}	Advantage 2 ^{[62][63]}
Release date	May 2011	May 2013	August 2015	January 2017	2020	2023-2024
Topology				Chimera	Pegasus	Zephyr
Code-name	Rainier	Vesuvius	W1K	W2K	Pegasus P16	
Qubits	128	512	1152	2048	5640	7000+ (7440)

Josephson junctions	24,000	?	128,000	128,472 ^[61]	1,030,000	
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Operating temperature (K)	?	0.02	0.015	0.015	<0.015	
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D-Wave Two coupling

From the thesis *Solving NP-Hard Problems on an Adiabatic Quantum Computer*, October 2014, by Dan Padilha.

“The D-Wave Two quantum computer is a device capable of performing adiabatic quantum computation on a set of 512 qubits. ... To ensure quantum coherence, the D-Wave Two system is housed in a controlled environment, being magnetically shielded from external sources, and cooled to temperatures as low as 20 mK to minimise thermal noise (as well as for the operation of the superconducting qubits).”

A figure in Radilha's thesis shows “A qubit and its couplings as represented on a D-Wave Two. Qubits are represented as superconducting loops such that the resulting direction of the electric current in the loops defines the qubit’s state or “spin”. In essence, during computation the direction of the electric current is unknown (in a probabilistic state), but when the system

decoheres (due to observation or noise), the current spins either one way or the other (“up” or “down”). In order to perform useful computations, it is necessary to carefully control the probability distribution of the qubit’s spin (in other words, which direction it is most likely to end up spinning). This is achieved by programming the *bias and couplings* of each qubit. The **bias is a programmable magnetic field applied to the qubit’s loop**, such that its presence and strength slightly nudges the current spin in a desired direction. Each qubit is also connected to other qubits using **programmable ferromagnetic/antiferromagnetic couplings**, which force qubits to spin in either the same or opposite direction of qubits they are connected to”.

So let's see what these couplers are like. We find them mentioned in a community page, archived at the link [Archive](#). “D-Wave uses superconducting flux qubits, specifically rf superconducting quantum–interference device (rf-SQUID) qubits. We use compound Josephson junctions (CCJJ) rf-SQUID for the couplers. They are described in this paper.” And there we find the already mentioned article by Harris, R. et al., *Compound Josephson-junction coupler for flux qubits with minimal crosstalk*, Physical Review B 80, no. 5 (2009): 052506.

Jülich Center in Germany

From “Europe’s First Quantum Computer with More Than 5K Qubits Launched at Jülich, January 18, 2022. Link [Hpcwire](#) (archiviato [Archive](#)). The 5000 qubits D-Wave system found a home in Jülich, North Rhine-Westphalia, at the Supercomputing Center (JSC). Thus, the first D-Wave cloud outside of North America was established. This annealing quantum computer joins the Jülich Unified Infrastructure for Quantum computing (JUNIQ), a center that was created in the fall of 2019 to provide researchers in Germany and Europe with access to various quantum systems.

“Forschungszentrum Jülich has set itself the goal of establishing a leading development and user community from industry and science for quantum computing applications in Germany and throughout Europe”. “To achieve this goal, we established JUNIQ as a user facility for open innovations at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre in 2019. It provides users with a uniform quantum computing platform as a service and also offers them the relevant expertise for user support and joint software development,” as told by Wolfgang Marquardt, President of the Board of directors of the Forschungszentrum Jülich. Marquardt is professor of Process System Engineering, at Aachen University.

Turning to the quantum computer market, the Hpcwire article underlines: “Given the extent to which companies and research institutions are identifying important problems that require investments in quantum computing, the marketing potential for quantum computing will grow at a faster rate than ever before, says Alan Baratz, CEO at D-Wave Systems. This particularly applies to Europe, where we are seeing increasing interest from companies, universities, and even government institutions. We look forward to combining Jülich’s expertise in the field of deep computing with D-Wave’s ability to scale and commercialize transformative technologies.”

It is also told that “*The quantum annealer is a quantum computer that has been developed with a view to industrial applications*. It also has a number of special features that users of the JUNIQ infrastructure can access, such as the new Advantage performance update, incorporating

the highly connected Pegasus topology, and unprecedented high performance in a commercial quantum system”. Pegasus requires a special infrastructure.

“A new building, which was also officially opened today [18 Gennaio 2022], was erected for the operation of the annealing quantum computer. Quantum computing systems require a special, vibration-free location. The building’s two machine halls therefore feature special vibration-damping foundations to absorb tremors. Alongside the D-Wave system, the building will host an additional quantum computer as of next year”. “The building’s two machine halls therefore feature special vibration-damping foundations to absorb tremors”.

Phonons

To use D-Wave Pegasus, we need the control of vibrations.

About vibrations, but special vibrations, somebody has guessed to use them for quantum computing. “Weird vibrations poised to control quantum computers”. 14 March 2018, di Adrian Cho, Science. <https://www.science.org/content/article/weird-vibrations-poised-control-quantum-computers> , doi: 10.1126/science.aat5858

“To control or read out a superconducting qubit, researchers make it interact with a microwave resonator—typically a strip of metal on the qubit chip or a finger-size cavity surrounding it—which rings with microwave photons the way an organ pipe rings with sound. By adjusting the energy of the qubit, researchers can shuttle its quantum states into the resonator, so that a zero-and-one state of the qubit can be stored as a state of the resonator in which a photon is both present and absent. But some physicists see advantages to replacing the microwave resonator with a mechanical one that rings with quantized vibrations, or phonons. That effort may seem daft, as such vibrations constitute heat, which obliterates delicate quantum states. But when working at temperatures near absolute zero, a well-designed acoustic resonator could ring longer than a microwave one does, enabling it to act as a sort of quantum memory, says Robert Schoelkopf, a physicist at Yale University. The vibrations also have wavelengths less than a thousandth as long as microwaves of the same frequency, so the resonators can be far more compact, he says”.

Quantum speedup

In the past, the D-Wave system has been questioned. It was in 2014, and the system was D-Wave 2, previous to D-Wave 2000Q (2017). We can find observations in “Quantum or not, controversial computer runs no faster than a normal one. D-Wave machine produces no "quantum speedup" but company says test is flawed". 19 June 2014, by Adrian Cho. Science. News.

<https://www.science.org/content/article/quantum-or-not-controversial-computer-runs-no-faster-normal-one>

Adrian Cho is mentioning Rønnow et al. (2014), *Defining and detecting quantum speedup*, Science, 345(6195), 420-424, that analyzed D-Wave Two (503 qubits). However authors tell in the abstract: “Our results do not rule out the possibility of speedup for other classes of problems and illustrate the subtle nature of the quantum speedup question.”

In 2016, Chris Lee wrote “Is D-Wave’s quantum processor really 10^8 times faster than a normal computer? Short answer: Yes, but it's more complicated than that.” <https://arstechnica.com/science/2016/02/is-d-waves-quantum-processor-really-10⁸-times-faster-than-a-normal-computer/> (archiviata [Archive](#)). See please in the article the discussion about **annealing and tunneling**. In the conclusions, it is told that “The engineers are hoping to design a new, improved D-Wave processor that has the connectivity of a ten-dimensional cubic lattice. Although details are limited, it seems that the plan is to use highly interconnected clusters that have more limited connectivity between clusters. The advantage is that the increased connection density within clusters—and the increasing connectedness between clusters—should allow larger problem sets to be more efficiently implemented. This is highly promising.” Today we have the Pegasus system. In 2023, we will have Zephyr system.

From Wikipedia: “In February 2019 D-Wave announced their next-generation Pegasus quantum processor chip, announcing that it would be “the world’s most connected commercial quantum system,” with 15 connections per qubit instead of 6; that the next-generation system would use the Pegasus chip; that it would have more than 5000 qubits and reduced noise; and that it would be available in mid-2020. A description of Pegasus and how it differs from the previous “Chimera” architecture has been available to the public.” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/D-Wave_Systems

Let us remember that quantum computers determine their performance on the basis on specific tests. So, they are not doing generic calculations, but are looking for an application where the QPU shows some advantage over the other QPUs or CPUs. More concretely: quantum computers are what Richard Feynman wrote in 1982: “Let the computer itself be built of quantum mechanical elements which obey quantum mechanical laws.” (Feynman, 1982). The quantum computer, when calculating, acts as a simulator of a quantum system (we talk about it in the Quantum Simulations section).

“What kind of computer are we going to use to simulate physics?” “Can physics be simulated by a universal computer?” These are two of the many questions posed by Feynman in 1982. He was talking about physics, and it is physics that quantum computers simulate, when quantum advantages occur.

Adiabatic Theorem

From https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adiabatic_theorem

“The adiabatic theorem is a concept in quantum mechanics. Its original form, due to Max Born and Vladimir Fock (1928), was stated as follows: *A physical system remains in its instantaneous eigenstate if a given perturbation is acting on it slowly enough and if there is a gap between the eigenvalue and the rest of the Hamiltonian's spectrum.* In simpler terms, a quantum mechanical system subjected to gradually changing external conditions adapts its functional form, but when subjected to rapidly varying conditions there is insufficient time for the functional form to adapt, so the spatial probability density remains unchanged.”

We have therefore to distinguish the use of the term “adiabatic” in quantum mechanics from that made in thermodynamics. “The quantum mechanical concept of adiabatic is related to adiabatic invariant, it is often used in the old quantum theory and has no direct relation with heat

exchange.” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adiabatic_invariant

Let us consider a system characterized by a discrete spectrum. To have adiabaticity, the presence of an energy gap between the energy levels is important; given a level, it must be separated, sufficiently separated, from the previous and the next levels. By changing slowly - and how slowly is indicated by the energy leap - the system always keeps itself on the same level.

In the “Introduction to quantum mechanics”, (1st ed.), D. J. Griffiths is proposing two examples of adiabatic processes, one is concerning the pendulum, the other molecules. “A more subtle example occurred in our discussion of the hydrogen molecule ... We began by assuming that the nuclei were at rest, a fixed distance R apart, and we solved for the motion of the electron. Once we had found the ground state energy of the system as a function of R, we located the equilibrium separation and from the curvature of the graph we obtained the frequency of vibration of the nuclei. In molecular physics this technique (beginning with nuclei at rest, calculating electronic wave functions, and using these to obtain information about positions and relatively sluggish – motion of the nuclei) is known as the Born-Oppenheimer approximation.”

“In quantum mechanics, the essential content of the adiabatic approximation can be cast in the form of a theorem. Suppose the Hamiltonian changes gradually from H(i) to H(f). The adiabatic theorem states that if the particle was initially in the n-th eigenstate of H(i), it will be carried (under the Schrödinger equation) into the n-th eigenstate of H(f). I assume that the spectrum is discrete and nondegenerate throughout the transition from H(i) to H(f), so there is no ambiguity about the ordering of the states; these conditions can be relaxed, given a suitable procedure for “tracking” the eigenvalues.”

Griffiths gives a demonstration of the theorem.

Calculation with adiabatic process

Let us go back to the text https://docs.dwavesys.com/docs/latest/c_gs_2.html (Archive), to better understand the calculation made with an adiabatic process. We start from the ground state of a Hamiltonian, to reach, by exploiting the adiabatic theorem, the ground state of another Hamiltonian, generally more complex.

The web page remembers that, “for a quantum system, a Hamiltonian is a function that maps certain states, called eigenstates, to energies. Only when the system is in an eigenstate of the Hamiltonian is its energy well defined and called the eigenenergy. When the system is in any other state, its energy is uncertain. The collection of eigenstates with defined eigenenergies make up the eigenspectrum. For the D-Wave quantum computer, the Hamiltonian may be represented as”:

$$\mathcal{H}_{ising} = \underbrace{-\frac{A(s)}{2} \left(\sum_i \hat{\sigma}_x^{(i)} \right)}_{\text{Initial Hamiltonian}} + \underbrace{\frac{B(s)}{2} \left(\sum_i h_i \hat{\sigma}_z^{(i)} + \sum_{i>j} J_{i,j} \hat{\sigma}_z^{(i)} \hat{\sigma}_z^{(j)} \right)}_{\text{Final Hamiltonian}}$$

We find the Pauli matrices, with coefficients $h_i, J_{i,j}$ having limits determined by the computer architecture. “The Hamiltonian is the sum of two terms, the initial Hamiltonian and the final Hamiltonian”. Changing A(s) and B(s), the Hamiltonian is tuned.

1) Initial Hamiltonian (first term)—“The lowest-energy state of the initial Hamiltonian is when all qubits are in a superposition state of 0 and 1. This term is also called the tunneling Hamiltonian”.

2) Final Hamiltonian (second term)—“The lowest-energy state of the final Hamiltonian **is the answer to the problem that you are trying to solve**. The final state is a classical state, and includes the qubit biases and the couplings between qubits. This term is also called the problem Hamiltonian”.

From https://docs.dwavesys.com/docs/latest/c_gs_2.html again.

“In quantum annealing, the system begins in the lowest-energy eigenstate of the initial Hamiltonian. As it anneals, it introduces the problem Hamiltonian, which contains the **biases and couplers**, and it reduces the influence of the initial Hamiltonian. At the end of the anneal, it is in an eigenstate of the problem Hamiltonian. ... As an anneal begins, the system starts in the lowest energy state, which is well separated from any other energy level. As the problem Hamiltonian is introduced, other energy levels may get closer to the ground state. The closer they get, the higher the probability that the system will jump from the lowest energy state into one of the excited states. There is a point during the anneal where the first excited state—that with the lowest energy apart from the ground state—approaches the ground state closely and then diverges away again. The minimum distance between the ground state and the first excited state throughout any point in the anneal is called the minimum gap. **Certain factors may cause the system to jump from the ground state into a higher energy state**. One is thermal fluctuations that exist in any physical system. **Another is running the annealing process too quickly**. An annealing process that experiences no interference from outside energy sources and evolves the Hamiltonian **slowly enough is called an adiabatic process**, and this is where the name **adiabatic quantum computing** comes from.”

AQC

Albash, T., & Lidar, D. A. (2018). *Adiabatic quantum computation*. Reviews of Modern Physics, 90(1), 015002. Abstract “Adiabatic quantum computing (AQC) started as an approach to solving optimization problems, and has evolved into an important universal alternative to the standard circuit model of quantum computing, with deep connections to both classical and quantum complexity theory and condensed matter physics”. The article is a review where it is given "an account of most of the major theoretical developments in the field, while focusing on the closed system setting. The review is organized around a series of topics that are essential to an understanding of the underlying principles of AQC, its algorithmic accomplishments and limitations, and its scope in the more general setting of computational complexity theory".

The authors give several variants of the adiabatic theorem, the cornerstone of AQC, and examples of explicit AQC algorithms, exhibiting a quantum speedup. The article contains also

an overview of several proofs of the universality of AQC and related Hamiltonian quantum complexity theory. We can find also the Stochastic AQC.

Adiabatic model

From “Equivalenza fra modello circuitale ed adiabatico di computazione quantistica”, Tesi di Laurea di Luca Mattiazzì, 2014, Università degli Studi di Padova, available at https://thesis.unipd.it/bitstream/20.500.12608/19820/1/Mattiazzi_Luca.pdf (Archive).

“Presenteremo ora un modello atto a risolvere problemi di *soddisfacibilità*, ovvero a verificare che una o un'insieme di condizioni siano verificate. Queste clausole possono essere vere o false a seconda dell'insieme di bits in esame. Più recente del circuitale, l'adiabatic quantum computation si basa sull'evoluzione adiabatica di autostati di una Hamiltoniana variabile nel tempo. Per svolgere un algoritmo, si prepara il sistema nello stato fondamentale della Hamiltoniana iniziale (di facile realizzazione, che chiameremo H_B). Questa viene fatta variare lentamente, affinché si rimanga nello stato ad energia minore durante tutta la trasformazione (fatto garantito dal Teorema Adiabatico), finché il sistema non è descritto da una Hamiltoniana finale (H_P) che decodificherà la soluzione al dato problema nel suo stato fondamentale, che andremo infine a misurare.”

We find the Hamiltonian: $H(s) = (1 - s)H_B + s H_P$ where $s \in [0, 1]$ is the time of evolution.

The thesis is discussing some examples, one of which is the Grover algorithm, that we will discuss in the next section. In summary, let us imagine a Hamiltonian of evolution $\tilde{H}(s)$. Let us consider eigenvalues as in the figure on the left.

Due to the adiabatic theorem, when varying s , the system remains in the ground state. However, we have an interval of parameter s , which is quite relevant, where the gap between E_0 and E_1 is minimum. This is reason why we have to move slowly.

Adiabatic Grover

Mattiazzì's thesis is mentioning the article by Roland, J., & Cerf, N. J. (2002). *Quantum search by local adiabatic evolution*. Physical Review A, 65(4), 042308.

“The adiabatic theorem has been recently used to design quantum algorithms of a new kind, where the quantum computer evolves slowly enough so that it remains near its instantaneous ground state which tends to the solution [Farhi, E., et al. (2000). Quantum computation by adiabatic evolution. arXiv preprint quant-ph/0001106]. We apply this time-dependent Hamiltonian approach to the Grover’s problem, i. e., searching a marked item in an unstructured database. We find that, by adjusting the evolution rate of the Hamiltonian so as to keep the evolution adiabatic on each infinitesimal time interval, the total running time is of order \sqrt{N} ”

, where N is the number of items in the database. We thus recover the advantage of Grover’s standard algorithm as compared to a classical search, scaling as N . This is in contrast with the constant-rate adiabatic approach developed in [Farhi et al.], where the requirement of adiabaticity is expressed only globally, resulting in a time of order N .” [Roland and Cerf]
 Before describing their local adiabatic search algorithm, authors describe Fahri et al. approach, “based on a global adiabatic evolution. Consider a set of N items among which one is marked, the goal being to find it in a minimum time. We use n qubits to label the items, so that the Hilbert space is of dimension $N=2^n$. In this space, the basis states are written $|i\rangle$, with $i=0, \dots, N-1$.” Let us consider $|m\rangle$ the state to find. This state is not a priori known, and therefore the initial state is assumed as:

$$|\psi_0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |i\rangle .$$

We need two Hamiltonians: $H_0 = I - |\psi_0\rangle\langle\psi_0|$, $H_m = I - |m\rangle\langle m|$ (both having eigenvalue 0). Let us write: $\hat{H}(s) = (1-s)H_0 + sH_m$.

The figure previously given shows the eigenvalues of this Hamiltonian. The largest eigenvalue is $E_2=1$ with $(N-2)$ degeneracy. E_0, E_1 : “The difference between these lowest two eigenvalues defines the gap g .”

The minimum gap $g_{min} = 1/\sqrt{N}$ is attained for $s = 1/2$. The adiabatic condition is satisfied in a computational time of N order, “and there is no advantage of this method compared to a classical search. ... Now, let us see how to improve on this adiabatic evolution method. One should note that by applying Eq. (6) [the adiabatic condition] globally, i. e. to the entire time interval T , we impose a limit on the evolution rate during the whole computation while this limit is only severe for the times around $s = 1/2$, where the gap g is minimum. Thus, by dividing T into infinitesimal time intervals dt and applying the adiabaticity condition locally to each of these intervals, we can vary the evolution rate continuously in time, thereby speeding up the computation. In other words, we do not use a linear evolution function $s(t)$ any more, but we adapt the evolution rate ds/dt to the local adiabaticity condition. ... As a consequence, we thus have a quadratic speed-up compared to a classical search, and this algorithm can be viewed as the adiabatic evolution version of Grover’s algorithm.” [Roland and Cerf]

Take advantage of topology

Positive temperatures

Today D-Wave system is the Pegasus Advantage. “Advantage is the most powerful and connected quantum computer in the world. It has 2.5x more connections and more than double

the number of qubits than the D-Wave 2000Q system, our previous generation quantum computer”. We can see the different topologies at the web page https://docs.dwavesys.com/docs/latest/c_gs_4.html, ([Archive](#)), and it is clear that the system is moving toward a macro scale QPU. “The D-Wave quantum processing unit (QPU) is a lattice of interconnected qubits. While some qubits connect to others via couplers, the D-Wave QPU is not fully connected. Instead, the qubits of D-Wave annealing quantum computers interconnect in one of the following topologies: Chimera for D-Wave 2000Q QPUs, Pegasus for Advantage QPUs, Zephyr for next-generation QPUs currently under development”.

For what concerns the temperature required by D-Wave systems, let us consider Boixo, S., et al. (2013), in *Quantum annealing with more than one hundred qubits*, arXiv preprint arXiv:1304.4595.

“Unlike adiabatic quantum computing, which has a similar schedule but assumes fully coherent adiabatic ground state evolution at zero temperature, quantum annealing is a positive temperature method involving an open quantum system coupled to a thermal bath. Nevertheless, one expects that similar to adiabatic quantum computing, small gaps to excited states may thwart finding the ground state. In hard optimisation problems, the smallest gaps of avoided level crossings have been found to close exponentially fast with increasing problem size, suggesting an exponential scaling of the required annealing time t_f with problem size N ”.

In the introduction of the article, authors say that the method of calculation with annealing takes its cue from the ancient technique of annealing the metals. “Mimicking this process in computer simulations is the idea behind simulated annealing as an optimisation method, which views the cost function of an optimisation problem as the energy of a physical system”.

“To perform quantum annealing, we map each of the Ising variables σ_i^z to the Pauli z-matrix (which defines the “computational basis”) and add a transverse magnetic field in the x-direction to induce quantum fluctuations, obtaining the time-dependent N-qubit Hamiltonian”:

$$H(t) = -A(t) \sum_i \sigma_i^x + B(t) H_{Ising} , \quad t \in [0, t_f]$$

The quantum annealing, at positive temperature, starts from the limit “of a strong transverse field and weak problem Hamiltonian, $A(0) \gg \max(k_B T, B(0))$, with the system state close to the ground state of the transverse field term. Monotonically decreasing $A(t)$ and increasing $B(t)$, the system evolves towards the ground state of the problem Hamiltonian, with $B(t_f) \gg A(t_f)$.”

In Boixo, S. et al. (2016), *Computational Role of Tunneling in a Programmable Quantum Annealer*, Nature Communications, at the following link <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20160001868/downloads/20160001868.pdf>, we can find the relevance of the quantum tunneling in the adiabatic calculation.

“Quantum tunneling, in particular for thin but high energy barriers, has been hypothesized as an advantageous mechanism for quantum optimization. In classical simulated annealing or cooling optimization algorithms, the corresponding temperature parameter must be raised to overcome

energy barriers. But if there are many potential local minima with smaller energy differences than the height of the barrier, the temperature must also be lowered to distinguish between them so the algorithm can converge to the global minimum.”

Quantum annealing

From https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_annealing

“Quantum annealing (QA) is an optimization process for finding the global minimum of a given objective function over a given set of candidate solutions (candidate states), by a process using quantum fluctuations. Quantum annealing is used mainly for problems where the search space is discrete (combinatorial optimization problems) with many local minima; such as finding the ground state of a spin glass or the traveling salesman problem. The term "quantum annealing" was first proposed in 1988 by B. Apolloni, N. Cesa Bianchi and D. De Falco as a quantum-inspired classical algorithm. It was formulated in its present form by T. Kadowaki and H. Nishimori in "Quantum annealing in the transverse Ising model ...”.

Boixo et al., in *Quantum annealing with more than one hundred qubits*, arXiv preprint arXiv:1304.4595, consider the Monte Carlo method and show the efficiency of quantum calculation. It was year 2013. In 2018, qubits were 1800.

In *Observation of topological phenomena in a programmable lattice of 1,800 qubits*, by Andrew D. King et al., Nature volume 560, pages 456–460 (2018), the authors describe and use a simple approach to statistical estimation with an annealing-based quantum processor that performs Monte Carlo sampling in a chain of reverse quantum annealing protocols. Observations are consistent with classical simulations across a range of Hamiltonian parameters.

Think modular

Modulare Rigetti

And here it is essential to note a new strategy.

Gold, A., Paquette, J. P., Stockklauser, A., Reagor, M. J., Alam, M. S., Bestwick, A., ... & **Rigetti, C.** *Entanglement across separate silicon dies in a modular superconducting qubit device*, Nature, 2021.

“Assembling future large-scale quantum computers out of smaller, specialized modules promises to simplify a number of formidable science and engineering challenges. One of the primary challenges in developing a modular architecture is in engineering high fidelity, low-latency quantum interconnects between modules”. In the article published in Nature, authors propose their solution for a “modular solid state architecture”.

“Having proven out the fundamental building blocks, this work provides the technological foundations for a **modular quantum processor technology** which will accelerate near-term experimental efforts and open up new paths to the fault-tolerant era for solid state qubit architectures”. The modular technology is useful to accelerate the next effort to the “fault-tolerant” era of quantum computing.

The authors show in their publication “a modular superconducting qubit device with direct coupling between physical modules. The device, which consists of four eight-qubit integrated

circuits (QuICs) fabricated on individual dies and flip-chip bonded to a larger carrier chip, achieves coupling rates and entanglement quality approaching the state-of-the-art in intra-chip coupling”.

“Rigetti Computing” is a California-based developer of quantum integrated circuits. The company has its cloud platform called Forest that enables programmers to write quantum algorithms, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rigetti_Computing .

“Rigetti Computing was founded in 2013 by **Chad Rigetti**, a physicist who previously worked on quantum computers at IBM, and studied under noted Yale quantum scientist Michel Devoret. ... By February 2016, the company had begun testing a three-qubit (quantum bit) chip made using aluminum circuits on a silicon wafer. ... By Spring of 2017, the company was testing eight-qubit computers, and in June, the company announced the public beta availability of a quantum cloud computing platform called Forest 1.0, which allows developers to write quantum algorithms. In October of 2021, it was announced that the company plans to go public via a SPAC merger, ... This process will allow the company to raise ... With this funding, Rigetti plans to scale its systems from 80 qubits to 1,000 qubits by 2024, and to 4,000 by 2026. The SPAC deal closed on 2 March, 2022, and the company began trading on the NASDAQ.”

“Rigetti Computing is a full-stack quantum computing company, a term that indicates that the company designs and fabricates quantum chips, integrates them with a controlling architecture, and develops software for programmers to use to build algorithms for the chips.”

“Diamonds Are a Girl's Best Friend”

[Marilyn Monroe]

Diamonds

In the article “Quest for qubits” by Gabriel Popkin we can find mentioned the “diamond vacancies”, where “A nitrogen atom and a vacancy add an electron to a diamond lattice. Its quantum spin state, along with those of nearby carbon nuclei, can be controlled by light.” (Company support: Quantum Diamond Technologies).

“The diamond quantum revolution”, by Matthew Markham and Daniel Twitchen, 23 April 2020, Physics World, link [Physicsworld](#) ([Archive](#)).

“Diamond is more than just a pretty gem – it has many attractive properties that stretch far beyond its aesthetic appeal. Matthew Markham and Daniel Twitchen explain how this special form of carbon now has many practical quantum applications too”.

“Now in the 21st century, scientists around the world are trying to develop the next wave of innovations. “Quantum 2.0” technology will rely on manipulating and reading out quantum states, and will typically exploit the quantum effects of superposition and entanglement.” [Markham and Twitchen]

In the article, new technologies for quantum devices are given: “trapped ions, superconductors, quantum dots, photons and defects in semiconductors. Each technical solution has different pros and cons. Trapped ions have exquisite quantum properties but are challenging to integrate, whereas circuits of superconductors can be fabricated but can only operate at cryogenic

temperatures. This is where materials like diamond come into play as they offer a compromise by being solid-state – making it easier to integrate into devices – and operational at room temperature”. [Markham and Twitchen]

Among lattice defects, we can find “the negatively charged nitrogen-vacancy (denoted as NV) defect. In 1997 Jörg Wrachtrup and colleagues at the University of Technology Chemnitz in Germany showed that a single NV defect could be manipulated and provide an optical output at room temperature (Science 276 2012). This discovery sparked the field of diamond quantum technology (see Nature 505 472 for a more detailed history). The process is called optically detected magnetic resonance (ODMR) and, with the NV defect, it is observed when measuring a change in fluorescence after shining green light on a single NV defect, or on an ensemble of them, while scanning an applied microwave field. ... by measuring the intensity of the fluorescence, you can read out the spin state of the defect. ... Over the next decade, a few academic groups around the world picked this work up, hoping to use diamond as a quantum bit, or “qubit”, in quantum information devices, such as quantum computers.” [Markham and Twitchen]

It was used a natural diamond, the “Magic Russian Diamond”. Meanwhile, many companies began to develop synthetic diamond production for “industrial applications using microwave-assisted chemical vapour deposition. In the early 2000s, a research staff of Element Six demonstrated the possibility to grow diamond with a few impurity atoms per billion carbon atoms. In this diamond, nitrogen is the predominant impurity. In 2006, a synthetic material comparable to the Magic Russian Diamond was found. This meant the mass production of such diamond. The article by Markham and Twitchen is mentioning the research of 2008 made by the team of Jörg Wrachtrup, University of Stuttgart, Germany, and by Mikhail Lukin and Ron Walsworth, Harvard University. These teams “proposed and showed that diamond could be used to make a magnetic sensor, in which the brightness of the NV defects’ optical output depends on the strength of the magnetic field. Since then, many new applications using the NV defect have been proposed.”

A reference to the physical reasons related to the importance of NV reticular defects is given in the article. Diamond is a wide band-gap material; this means that “it can host a range of defects with transition energies in the optical regime, enabling the defects to be manipulated with readily available lasers.” Carbon has low atomic mass and strong interatomic bonds in the diamond lattice (graphite has two-dimensional planes). Diamond has high Debye temperature, “which makes the interaction of the NV centre with the vibrational modes of the surrounding lattice unusually weak, even at room temperature. Diamond also has a naturally low concentration of nuclear spins ... This reduces the likelihood of the quantum states “decohering”, when the spin is no longer in the desired state. Quantum states can also decohere via spin-orbit coupling ... But because the NV defect has weak spin-orbit coupling, there is limited decoherence and the spin state lasts for longer.” [Markham and Twitchen] The result is that it is possible to manufacture a diamond with a spin decoherence time of the order of milliseconds at room temperature. “And as well as diamond being a good host for spin defects, the NV centre is also particularly special in that its electronic energy-level structure means that the electronic spin associated with it can be manipulated simply by shining green light on it.”

We are facing a very tempting scenario, but things are not simple, because of the phonons in the crystal lattice; the diamond has an excellent crystal lattice that makes it the material with the best heat conductivity (Sparavigna, 2002).

“Despite these desirable features, the NV defect in diamond is not perfect”. The photons useful for this application are emitted at different wavelengths due to the interaction with other phonons. Furthermore, diamond is not as easily processable as silicon.

“These limitations of diamond and the NV defect have led to scientists looking for alternative defects in diamond and in other wide band-gap materials such as silicon carbide (SiC) and zinc oxide (ZnO).” [Markham and Twitchen] Other defects useful for applications have been identified in diamond, but none are as performing as the NV centers.

A virtue of a diamond-based quantum device is its simplicity. “A basic device can be fabricated from a green light source, a diamond, a small microwave source and a photodetector. ... All of these components can be bought off the shelf for a few thousand pounds, and instructions to build such a room-temperature quantum device are readily available and suitable for a first-year physics degree demonstration (American Journal of Physics 86 225). However, while this set-up shows the principles of operation, it clearly does not show the enhancements in performance you would expect from a quantum device.” [Markham and Twitchen]

In the Physics World article a detailed discussion is given. Then, we find some devices.

“Despite these potential hurdles, several breakthrough results have been achieved with diamond, including the first successful “loophole-free Bell’s inequality test” in 2015 (Nature 526 682), and the longest spin lifetime without the use of any cryogenics”. Then a 10-qubit register able to store quantum information for up to 75 s has been demonstrated (see Phys Rev. X 9 031045). The **Ronald Hanson’s group** at the Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands used NV defects in diamond as a “quantum repeater node” to obtain a 100% secure quantum internet. Another application is the diamond-based maser. An article of 2018 (Nature 555 493) disclosed the world’s first continuous-wave (CW) room-temperature solid-state maser, based on NV defect in diamond. Then, Markham and Twitchen consider magnetic field and biomedical applications: “Using such a bulk magnetometer, a team at Lockheed Martin – the US-based aerospace company – has been developing a diamond magnetometer that can be used as an alternative GPS that does not rely on external signals. ... Diamond-based quantum technology also has applications in the medical industry. A few groups around the world, as well as the start-up NVision based in Germany, are using diamond to enhance magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) – turning it from an anatomical to a molecular imaging modality similar to positron emission tomography (PET). ...”

What are the companies involved in the diamond’s quantum future? More than 200 academic research teams, and a “growing number of companies developing diamond quantum technology, including large firms such as Lockheed Martin, Bosch and Thales, as well as many start-ups such as Quantum Diamond Technologies, NVision and Qnami”.

A quantum desktop

We can buy a quantum desktop from SpinQ: +86-755-23760210, mail contact@spinq.cn.
Indirizzo: 508-509, Tower A, Shenzhen Financial Science and Technology Innovation Center,

No.1 Shihua Road, Futian Free Trade Zone, Shenzhen.

“A Desktop Quantum Computer for Just \$5,000. A cheap, portable quantum computer, aimed at schools and colleges will be launched later this year.”. The Physics arXiv Blog, Jan 29, 2021 3:00 PM, link [discovermagazine](#) ([Archive](#)).

“A Chinese start-up has unveiled plans to sell a desktop quantum computer costing less than \$5,000. The new portable device is one of a range called SpinQ, aimed at schools and colleges. It is made by the Shenzhen SpinQ Technology, based in Shenzhen, China.” This is not the first quantum computer of this company. In 2020, the company was selling a desktop, about 50,000 dollars, weight 55kg. But the new machine is simpler, more portable and cheaper.

“The price of the machine is in stark contrast to commercial quantum computers, which can cost in the region of \$10 million and process more than 50 qubits. By contrast, the SpinQ machine is much less powerful, able to process just 2 qubits, and relies on an entirely different technology called **nuclear magnetic resonance**. This works by trapping specially selected molecules in a powerful magnetic field and then zapping them with radio frequency pulses to manipulate the spins of the atoms they contain. After each set of radio pulses, the atoms relax and emit their own radio frequency signals, which reveal their new state. In this way, it is possible to flip the spin of atoms—equivalent to changing a 0 into 1 – and make the spins of neighboring atoms interact, which can simulate mathematical operations, and finally to record the result”.

SpinQ uses dimethylphosphite. “To ensure that the radio signals from the hydrogen and phosphorus atoms are strong enough to pick up, a huge number of molecules must be used, about 10^{15} of them. That requires a few drops of liquid, which sit in a small vial in the middle of the powerful magnetic field. The technique is well understood and has long been used to make medical images of the body. Indeed, the first quantum computers built in the 1990s used exactly the same approach.”

“Although [its QPU] processes only 2 qubits, the SpinQ device is capable of a number of quintessential quantum calculations. For example, it can implement a version of Grover’s algorithm, which can search through a database more quickly than a classical algorithm.” The SpinQ devices “will never match the power of the quantum computers that Google, IBM, Microsoft and others are toying with. One of the drawbacks of quantum computation based on nuclear magnetic resonance is that the machines cannot handle more than a dozen or so qubits”. ArXiv blog discussed the desktop in January 2021. Today we can find that SpinQ (<https://www.spinquanta.com>, [Archive](#)) is proposing Triangulum with three qubits.

This machine is mentioned in the article “Pawsey is Empowering Students to Have a Quantum Mindset”, March 3, 2022

<https://www.hpcwire.com/off-the-wire/pawsey-is-empowering-students-to-have-a-quantum-mindset/>

It is told that the "Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre is supporting a pioneering quantum education and research program to enable students access to one of the first educational quantum computers in Australia. Based at the University of Western Australia (UWA), the new program will enable researchers and students to upskill in the emerging area of quantum computing and engage with Pawsey’s Quantum Supercomputing Innovation Hub. The education and research hub will be led by renowned quantum physicist Professor Jingbo Wang

and will offer two desktop quantum computers, the two-qubit SpinQ Gemini and the three-qubit SpinQ Triangulum system, operating at room temperature.”

Here a screenshot from <https://www.spinquanta.com/products-solutions/Triangulum>

“Real visible operation - Real quantum computer base on NMR system, uses the spin phenomenon of nuclei as the qubit carrier, to read and operate qubits states by RF pulse”.

1998, two qubit

Chuang, I. L., Gershenfeld, N., & Kubinec, M. (1998). *Experimental implementation of fast quantum searching*. Physical review letters, 80(15), 3408.

Using **nuclear magnetic resonance techniques with a solution of chloroform molecules** the authors implemented the Grover's search algorithm for a system with four states. "By performing a tomographic reconstruction of the density matrix during the computation good agreement is seen between theory and experiment. This provides the first complete experimental demonstration of loading an initial state into a quantum computer, performing a computation requiring fewer steps than on a classical computer, and then reading out the final state." <http://cba.mit.edu/docs/papers/98.03.grover.pdf>

Two or three qubits

Feng, G. R., Lu, Y., Hao, L., Zhang, F. H., & Long, G. L. (2013). *Experimental simulation of quantum tunneling in small systems*. Scientific Reports, 3(1), 1-7. The article is reporting "the first experimental simulation of quantum tunneling through potential barriers, a widespread phenomenon of a unique quantum nature, via NMR techniques". The experiment "is based on a digital particle simulation algorithm and requires very few spin-1/2 nuclei without the need of ancillary qubits. The occurrence of quantum tunneling through a barrier, together with the oscillation of the state in potential wells, are clearly observed through the experimental results. This experiment has clearly demonstrated the possibility to observe and study profound physical phenomena within even the reach of small quantum computers”.

Superconducting qubits and Josephson junctions

SpinQ uses an NMR system at room temperature.

Let us return to the computers based on superconducting qubits, which require very low

temperatures. D-Wave is a company that uses its *coupled rf-superconducting quantum interference device (rf-SQUID) flux qubits*, as mentioned above. Let us also remember that the Josephson junction is composed of two superconductors separated by an insulator. At the basis of the operation of a Josephson junction there is the tunnelling effect of Cooper pairs through the insulating layer. The Josephson effect was theorized and experimentally verified in the early 1960s.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brian_Josephson: Brian David Josephson is a theoretical physicist and professor emeritus of physics at the University of Cambridge. Best known for his pioneering work on superconductivity and quantum tunnelling, he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1973 for his prediction of the Josephson effect, made in 1962 when he was a 22-year-old PhD student at Cambridge University. He shared the prize with physicists Leo Esaki and Ivar Giaever, who jointly received half the award for their own work on quantum tunnelling.

Let us consider the “Controllo Ottimale Quantistico di Qubits Superconduttivi di Carica”, Tesi Specialistica di Angelo Di Marco, 2009/2010, Università degli studi di Pisa. [archive](#) .

After a detailed discussion of large and small Josephson junctions, and SQUID devices, the question arises of which devices are the best candidates for making qubits. “Questa scelta deve essere fatta tenendo conto di alcune caratteristiche basilari che un qubit deve possedere. Innanzitutto è importante che il sistema utilizzato come bit quantistico sia il più possibile a due stati. ... In particolare i livelli che rappresentano la base computazionale, $|0\rangle$ e $|1\rangle$, devono essere isolati dagli altri nel senso che la loro frequenza di transizione deve essere molto diversa da quella richiesta per passare da uno stato energetico all'altro, ... Un altro aspetto di cui tenere conto per la costruzione di un qubit è quello di rendere minima la dissipazione e così non avere perdite di energia quando si svolge qualsiasi operazione sul dispositivo. ... A questo bisogna aggiungere la possibilità di lavorare a basse temperature così si limita il rumore termico.” [Di Marco]

One device which satisfies these demands is the “small” Josephson junction for sure, as told by the thesis. The dimension is about a micron and therefore many junctions can be placed inside integrated circuits. Josephson “small” junctions can be exploited to create three types of superconducting qubits: flux, charge and phase qubits. Phase superconducting qubits are made through a Josephson junction driven by a bias current. RF-SQUID devices are used to have superconducting flux qubits, by exploiting the currents of Cooper pairs that circulate on their surface counterclockwise (flow upwards) or clockwise (flow downwards). These systems are driven by a bias magnetic field, generated by a radio-frequency current. Then there is the charge qubit called “Cooper-pair box”.

The thesis suggests “Superconducting Qubits: A Short Review”, 2004, di M. H. Devoret, A. Wallraff, J. M. Martinis, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.cond-mat/0411174> where we can find two fundamental assertions.

“For an integrated circuit to behave quantum mechanically, the first requirement is the absence of dissipation. More specifically, all metallic parts need to be made out of a material that has zero resistance at the qubit operating temperature and at the qubit transition frequency. ... Low temperature superconductors such as aluminium or niobium are ideal for this task. For this

reason, quantum integrated circuit implementations have been nicknamed “superconducting qubits”. And also: “the quantum integrated circuit must be cooled to temperatures where the typical energy kT of thermal fluctuations is much less than the energy quantum” linked to the transition between states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. The corresponding frequency for a superconducting qubit is in the range 5-20 GHz. Temperature is about 2 K (1 K corresponds to 20 GHz). “Perhaps more importantly though, the “electromagnetic temperature” of the wires of the control and readout ports connected to the chip must also be cooled to these low temperatures, which requires careful electromagnetic filtering.”

And also: <https://copilot.caltech.edu/documents/16821/leshouchesjunctionphysics.pdf>

Superconducting Qubits and the Physics of Josephson Junctions by John M. Martinis and Kevin Osborne, preprint arXiv, 2004, <https://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/0402415>

“Josephson junctions are good candidates for the construction of quantum bits (qubits) for a quantum computer. This system is attractive because the low dissipation inherent to superconductors makes possible, in principle, long coherence times. In addition, because complex superconducting circuits can be microfabricated using integrated-circuit processing techniques, scaling to a large number of qubits should be relatively straightforward. Given the initial success of several types of Josephson qubits, a question naturally arises: what are the essential components that must be tested, understood, and improved for eventual construction of a Josephson quantum computer?”

Let us consider an illustration from the article by Martinis and Osborne. This figure shows three manners of using a Josephson junction (X the figure) to create a qubit.

Below the circuit, it is given the Hamiltonian. The ground function is represented by the thin line.

Further references are Kockum, A. F., & Nori, F. (2019). *Quantum bits with Josephson junctions*. In *Fundamentals and Frontiers of the Josephson Effect* (pp. 703-741). Springer, Cham., <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.09558>, and Wendin, G., & Shumeiko, V. S. (2007). *Quantum bits with Josephson junctions*. *Low Temperature Physics*, 33(9), 724-744 (archiviato [Archive](#)).

Design and fabrication

“Superconducting Qubits: A Short Review”, 2004, by M. H. Devoret, A. Wallraff, J. M. Martinis, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.cond-mat/0411174>

“Superconducting junctions and wires are fabricated using techniques borrowed from conventional integrated circuits. Quantum circuits are typically made on silicon wafers using optical or electron-beam lithography and thin film deposition. They present themselves as a set of micron-size or sub-micron-size circuit elements (tunnel junctions, capacitors, and inductors)

connected by wires or transmission lines. The size of the chip and elements are such that, to a large extent, the electrodynamics of the circuit can be analyzed using simple transmission line equations or even a lumped element approximation. Contact to the chip is made by wires bonded to mm-size metallic pads. The circuit can be designed using conventional layout and classical simulation programs. Thus, many of the design concepts and tools of conventional semiconductor electronics can be directly applied to quantum circuits. Nevertheless, there are still important differences between conventional and quantum circuits at the conceptual level". From what has been said, the creation of QPU based on superconducting qubits takes advantage of the already existing microchip technology.

At the beginning of the analysis we reported from Il Sole 24 Ore that Simone Severini, director of Quantum computing at Amazon Web Services (AWS), when talking about classical computers mentioned them governed by Newtonian physics. Solid state physics is not Newtonian physics, but we can make semi-classical approximations and treat currents and voltages as classical objects. He also mentioned the different simulations that can be done with classical systems and quantum systems. Now let's add one more observation, again from <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.cond-mat/0411174> .

We can consider from this text that, "At the conceptual level, conventional and quantum circuits differ in that, in the former, the collective electronic degrees of freedom such as currents and voltages are classical variables, whereas in the latter, these degrees of freedom must be treated by quantum operators which do not necessarily commute. A more concrete way of presenting this rather abstract difference is to say that a typical electrical quantity, such as the charge on the plates of a capacitor, can be thought of as a simple number in conventional circuits, whereas in quantum circuits, the charge on the capacitor must be represented by a wave function giving the probability amplitude of all charge configurations. For example, the charge on the capacitor can be in a superposition of states where the charge is both positive and negative at the same time. Similarly the current in a loop might be flowing in two opposite directions at the same time. These situations have originally been nicknamed "macroscopic quantum coherence" effects by Tony Leggett to emphasize that quantum integrated circuits are displaying phenomena involving the collective behavior of many particles, which are in contrast to the usual quantum effects associated with microscopic particles such as electrons, nuclei or molecules".

Gooseberry and Sycamore

Azure Quantum

At the beginning, we have mentioned four methods for quantum computing (David Vitali, 2018): 1) quantum gate array, 2) one-way quantum computer, 3) adiabatic quantum computer or quantum annealing, 4) topological quantum computer, with braiding of anyons. For method n.4, we mentioned the Majorana particles. In the "Quest for qubits" by Gabriel Popkin we can

find, among five methods, also that based on topology, which is told as supported by Microsoft and Bell Labs. Then, let us see now the Majorana method for quantum computing.

<https://news.microsoft.com/innovation-stories/azure-quantum-majorana-topological-qubit/>

(opppure [Archive](#)). “In a historic milestone, Azure Quantum demonstrates formerly elusive physics needed to build scalable topological qubits”. Jennifer Langston, Mar 14, 2022 - “Microsoft’s Azure Quantum program has developed devices that can create quantum properties which scientists have imagined for nearly a century but have not been able to unambiguously produce in the real world — until now.”

“It’s a key scientific breakthrough that demonstrates the elusive building blocks for a topological quantum bit, or qubit, which Microsoft has long pursued as the most promising path to developing a scalable quantum computer that will launch a new generation of as-yet-unimagined computing capabilities for Azure customers.” [Microsoft]

“Building on two decades of scientific research and recent investments in simulation and fabrication, the Azure Quantum team has engineered devices that allow them to induce a topological phase of matter bookended by a pair of Majorana zero modes. These quantum excitations don’t normally exist in nature and must be coaxed into appearing under incredibly precise conditions. Scientists have sought to create and observe these excitations since they were first theorized about in 1937. More recently, they’ve realized that Majorana zero modes can play an important role in protecting quantum information and enabling reliable computation. The Azure Quantum team has also been able to produce what is known as a topological phase and to measure the topological gap, which quantifies the stability of the phase”. [Microsoft]

“The ability to create and sustain a quantum phase with Majorana zero modes and a measurable topological gap removes the biggest obstacle to producing a unique type of qubit, which Microsoft’s quantum machine will use to store and compute information, called a topological qubit. It’s the foundation for Microsoft’s approach to building a quantum computer that is expected to be more stable than machines built with other types of known qubits, and therefore scale like no other”. [Microsoft]

“... Azure Quantum has focused on developing topological qubits, which are expected to be faster, smaller and less prone to losing information than other types of qubits currently under development. Microsoft believes creating a more stable topological qubit is the clearest and fastest path to building an industrial-scale quantum machine. But, until now, the downside of pursuing a topological qubit was that no one was sure it was possible to harness the underlying quantum physics to produce them”. [Microsoft]

Majorana zero mode

Manna, S., Wei, P., Xie, Y., Law, K. T., Lee, P. A., & Moodera, J. S. (2020). *Signature of a pair of Majorana zero modes in superconducting gold surface states*. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 117(16), 8775-8782.

“In 1937 Ettore Majorana pointed out that unlike the standard solution of the Dirac equation which led to the electron and its antiparticle, the positron, it is possible to have a solution where the fermionic particle is its own antiparticle. While such a particle remains elusive in particle

physics, a pair of localized Majorana states has been predicted to reside at the ends of a specially designed superconducting wire. These Majorana zero modes can form building blocks of qubits for fault-tolerant quantum computers. Here we report signatures of Majorana zero modes in a platform consisting of EuS and gold films grown on vanadium. This platform is amenable to standard nanofabrication techniques and holds promise for scalable Majorana qubits.”

“Under certain conditions, a fermion in a superconductor can separate in space into two parts known as Majorana zero modes, which are immune to decoherence from local noise sources and are attractive building blocks for quantum computers. Promising experimental progress has been made to demonstrate Majorana zero modes in materials with strong spin–orbit coupling proximity coupled to superconductors. Here we report *signatures of Majorana zero modes* in a material platform utilizing the surface states of gold. Using scanning tunneling microscope to probe EuS islands grown on top of gold nanowires, we observe two well-separated zero-bias tunneling conductance peaks aligned along the direction of the applied magnetic field, as expected for a pair of Majorana zero modes. This platform has the advantage of having a robust energy scale and the possibility of realizing complex designs using lithographic methods.”

We have also the review article by Lutchyn, R. M., Bakkers, E. P., Kouwenhoven, L. P., Krogstrup, P., Marcus, C. M., & Oreg, Y. (2018). *Majorana zero modes in superconductor–semiconductor heterostructures*. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 3(5), 52-68.

“Realizing topological superconductivity and Majorana zero modes in the laboratory is one of the major goals in condensed matter physics. We review the current status of this rapidly-developing field, focusing on semiconductor-superconductor proposals for topological superconductivity. Material science progress and robust signatures of Majorana zero modes in recent experiments are discussed. After a brief introduction to the subject, we outline several next-generation experiments probing exotic properties of Majorana zero modes, including fusion rules and non-Abelian exchange statistics. Finally, we discuss prospects for implementing Majorana-based topological quantum computation in these systems.”

On Nature

In 2018, Nature published an article announcing the “Quantized Majorana conductance”, that is the observation of Majorana zero modes. The article reported about “electrical measurements and numerical simulations of hybrid superconducting–semiconducting nanowires in a magnetic field”. After publication, the article has been retracted, because of incongruences pointed out by Sergey Frolov and Vincent Mourik, as told in the “Retraction Note: Quantized Majorana conductance”, <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-021-03373-x> .

About the computer based on Majorana zero-modes, see please “Microsoft’s Majorana Announcement: A Restart for a Very Long Journey”, [quantumcomputingreport](#), March 2022, where it is pointed out that the Microsoft Company is not only engaged in the development of a computer based on the topological scheme; the company is also engaged in the development of new control electronics, suitable for quantum computers that require very low temperatures to operate.

“The other thing to mention is that Microsoft is working on two other important technologies

that will be also important for their topological based quantum computer. Besides the Majorana based qubits themselves, they are also working on the aforementioned Floquet based error correction code to eliminate any remaining errors that are not corrected by the hardware. Another important technology is cryoCMOS based control electronics. For these large systems, it is imperative to find a better solution to route the control signals to the qubit chip than the rat's nest of individual cables that are used today. By developing a low power cryoCMOS chip that can run at low temperatures the cabling can be made a lot simpler because the control chip is located very near or maybe even on the same die as the qubits. So overall, we recognize that the Microsoft team has put in a lot of effort and hard work to get to this stage, and we congratulate them on achieving this milestone. However, we also recognize that there still is a lot of additional hard work needed to create a working processor and there is still a lot of work left to be done”.

Let us briefly see Frolov's observations on Majorana fermions. The discussion is apparently specific to these particles, but it has a more general framework. We could apply it to the crisis of the race for quantum supremacy and to the reactions that are triggered by every announcement of exceptional performance from quantum computers.

Quantum computing's reproducibility crisis: Majorana fermions, by Sergey Frolov. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-00954-8>

“The controversy over Majorana particles is eroding confidence in the field. More accountability and openness are needed — from authors, reviewers and journal editors.”

“Experiments to find Majorana signals are performed by loading a nanowire into a dilution refrigerator capable of cooling it down to close to absolute zero.”

“As someone who works in this area, I've (Frolov) become concerned that, after a series of false starts, a significant fraction of the Majorana field is fooling itself. Several key experiments claiming to have detected Majorana particles, initially considered as breakthroughs, have not been confirmed”. A recent case ended with the withdrawal of an article published in Nature, link [Nature](#). At the beginning, there were the observations by Frolov and by Vincent Mourik, a physicist at the University of New South Wales in Sydney, Australia. Frolov and Mourik “raised concerns after obtaining additional data from the original experiments that were not included with the published paper”.

“Majorana particles are in theory their own antiparticles, and were predicted in 1937 by Italian physicist Ettore Majorana”. Microsoft hopes to use Majorana particles to have a computer. “Producing Majoranas in the laboratory is very hard. Experiments combine cutting-edge fields such as nanotechnology, superconductivity, device engineering and materials science. In the most developed approach, researchers must first grow a nanowire crystal — a feat in itself — to produce a column of atoms 100 nanometres ... across. Then they must connect the wire to a circuit sensitive enough to measure single electrons travelling through it. The whole experiment must be done at about one-hundredth of a degree above absolute zero, in a magnetic field 10,000 times that of Earth's. ... Under those extremes, when all the electrons in the wire are magnetized, Majorana particles should emerge from the two wire ends. In theory” [Frolov].

“More than 100 groups have tried this. Two dozen have reported Majorana manifestations. These usually appear in the form of a characteristic electronic signal: a narrow peak in current

as voltage is varied across the nanowire. I was a member of one of the first teams to observe this, in 2012 [Mourik, V. et al. *Science* 336, 1003–1007 (2012)]. More papers soon appeared. [one is that published on *Nature*, 2018, withdrawn] In 2020, these observations came under scrutiny after replication experiments were conducted. ... My group reproduced patterns from the 2018 *Nature* study, but demonstrated that they need not originate from Majorana. We did a cross-check on both ends of the same nanowire, but found a current peak on only one end. This violated the basic expectation from the theory that Majoranas always come in pairs. The rate of rebuttal is speeding up: ... The lesson: Majorana particles aren't necessary to produce the current peak signals. ... Yet, affirmative papers kept coming out without even mentioning alternative explanations, creating the impression that a debate is raging between Majorana optimists and pessimists" [Frolov].

The problem is that of the cherry-picking, and this is clearly told by Frolov. "But I think that researchers are *cherry-picking* — focusing on data that agree with the Majorana theory and sidelining those that don't. ... Sometimes there really is no need to present all of your data, if a single graph tells the whole story. But for Majorana particles, simply searching through the data to identify peaks of the right height is not enough to stake a detection claim, especially when alternative theories exist. It is all too easy for selection bias to take over in hypothesis-driven experimental research. The 'best' data are often considered to be those that fit the theory. So deviations are too readily dismissed as experimental or human error that can thus be discarded" [Frolov].

"Another problem is the breadth of peer review needed to check Majorana claims. Scrutiny is hard in any multidisciplinary field. Referees tend to be expert in one subject and struggle to judge others, and that leaves gaps. For example, a theoretical physicist might be comfortable assessing the calculations but not the experimental process, and a materials scientist, who understands how to grow nanowires, might skip the theory part. But a holistic view of the whole study is needed to properly assess it. It is an all too familiar story. In a *Nature* survey of the 'reproducibility crisis' across chemistry, biology, physics, engineering and medical sciences (see *Nature* 533, 452–454; 2016), selective reporting of results was a top culprit" [Frolov].

"What of Majorana research? It remains viable and important. But, in my view [Frolov], the key discoveries have yet to be made. A concentrated effort is now needed to improve our nanowire materials, experimental techniques and data analysis, as well as to tease out alternative explanations. Reliable proof is needed that the particles are indeed their own antiparticles — with our eyes on the full data" [Frolov].

Knots and Fermions

"Knot Logic and Topological Quantum Computing with Majorana Fermions", Louis H. Kauffman.

"This paper is an introduction to relationships between quantum topology and quantum computing. We take a foundational approach, showing how knots are related not just to braiding and quantum operators, but to quantum set theoretical foundations and algebras of fermions. We show how the operation of negation in logic, seen as both a value and an operator, can generate the fusion algebra for a Majorana fermion, a particle that is its own anti-particle and interacts

with itself either to annihilate itself or to produce itself. We call negation in this mode the mark, as it operates on itself to change from marked to unmarked states. The mark viewed recursively as a simplest discrete dynamical system naturally generates the fermion algebra, the quaternions and the braid group representations related to Majorana fermions. The paper begins with these fundamentals. They provide a conceptual key to many of the models that appear later in the paper. In particular, the Fibonacci model for topological quantum computing is seen to be based on the fusion rules for a Majorana fermion and these in turn are the interaction rules for the mark seen as a logical particle. It requires a shift in viewpoint to see that the operator of negation can also be seen as a logical value. The quaternions emerge naturally from the reentering mark. All these models have their roots in unitary representations of the Artin braid group to the quaternions.”. arXiv:1301.6214 at link <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1301.6214>

Gooseberry, the cryogenic control by Microsoft

In “A Restart for a Very Long Journey”, Microsoft tells that the company is engaged in another problem of quantum computing. “Another important technology is *cryoCMOS* based control electronics”. For larger computing systems, it is fundamental to find the best solution to the “*rat’s nest of individual cables that are used today*”. Microsoft mentions the article “Full stack ahead: Pioneering quantum hardware allows for controlling up to thousands of qubits at cryogenic temperatures”, Published January 27, 2021, di Chetan Nayak , link [Archive](#) .

On the left, a scheme arranged from an image of this article is given to illustrate the three levels of the Microsoft fundamental device. Many thanks to Microsoft Research Blog and Chetan Nayak for the very useful original image.

“Quantum computing offers the promise of solutions to previously unsolvable problems, but in order to deliver on this promise, it will be necessary to preserve and manipulate information that is contained in the most delicate of resources: highly entangled quantum states. One thing that makes this so challenging is that quantum devices must be ensconced in an extreme environment in order to preserve quantum information, but signals must be sent to each qubit in order to manipulate this information—requiring, in essence, an information superhighway into this extreme environment. Both of these problems must, moreover, be solved at a scale far beyond that of present-day quantum device technology.” [Chetan Nayak]

Quantum computing, however, has an Achilles heel.

“Despite the unmatched potential computing power of qubits, they have an Achilles’ heel: great instability. Since quantum states are easily disturbed by the environment, researchers must go to extraordinary lengths to protect them. This involves cooling them nearly down to absolute zero temperature and isolating them from outside disruptions, like electrical noise. Hence, it is necessary to develop a full system, made up of many components, that maintains a regulated,

stable environment. But all of this must be accomplished while enabling communication with the qubits. Until now, this has necessitated a bird's nest-like tangle of cables, which could work for limited numbers of qubits (and, perhaps, even at an "intermediate scale") but not for large-scale quantum computers." [Chetan Nayak]

Here the study on the control of many qubits: *A cryogenic CMOS chip for generating control signals for multiple qubits*, S. J. Pauka, K. Das, R. Kalra, A. Moini, Y. Yang, M. Trainer, A. Bousquet, C. Cantaloube, N. Dick, Geoff Gardner, M. J. Manfra, David Reilly, *Nature Electronics* | January 2021 , Vol 4: pp. 64-70.

"Scaled-up quantum computers will require control interfaces capable of the manipulation and readout of large numbers of qubits, which usually operate at millikelvin temperatures. Advanced complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) technology is an attractive platform for delivering such interfaces. ... Here we report a CMOS-based platform that can provide multiple electrical signals for the control of qubits at 100 mK." The researchers "demonstrate a chip that is configured by digital input signals at room temperature and uses on-chip circuit cells that are based on switched capacitors to generate static and dynamic voltages for the parallel control of qubits". The CMOS chip is used "to bias a quantum dot device and to switch the conductance of a quantum dot via voltage pulses generated on the chip. Based on measurements from six cells, we determine the average power dissipation for generating control pulses of 100 mV to be 18 nW per cell. We estimate that a scaled-up system containing a thousand cells could be cooled by a commercially available dilution refrigerator".

As told before, the cryo-CMOS chip has a name: Gooseberry.

<https://www.hpewire.com/2021/01/28/microsoft-develops-cryo-controller-chip-gooseberry-for-quantum-computing/>

Horse Ridge (Intel)

Besides Microsoft we have also the QuTech, Delft, and Intel Corporation that are working on the cryo-control. After Gooseberry, it was announced Horse Ridge.

"Intel vuole cambiare le regole del gioco dei computer quantistici", by Dario D'Elia, 11.06.2021, *Wired* <https://www.wired.it/attualita/tech/2021/06/11/computer-quantistici-intel-horse-ridge/> ([Archive](#)). With Horse Ridge and the cryogenic control, the company wants to overcome the obstacles to the scalability of quantum computers.

Details have been published by *Nature* (Xue et al., 2021, CMOS-based cryogenic control of silicon quantum circuits. *Nature*, 593(7858), 205-210.). The article tells that "silicon spin qubits can be operated and measured above 1 K" and "they are well positioned for overcoming the wiring bottleneck by on-die or on-package co-integration with classical electronics at a temperature of 1–3 K, where the cooling power is orders of magnitude higher than at millikelvin temperatures."

From the abstract: "In current solid-state qubit implementations, an important interconnect bottleneck appears between the quantum chip in a dilution refrigerator and the room-temperature electronics. Advanced lithography supports the fabrication of both control electronics and qubits in silicon using technology compatible with complementary metal oxide semiconductors (CMOS). When the electronics are designed to operate at cryogenic

temperatures, they can ultimately be integrated with the qubits on the same die or package, overcoming the ‘wiring bottleneck’. Here we report a cryogenic CMOS control chip operating at 3 kelvin, which outputs tailored microwave bursts to drive silicon quantum bits cooled to 20 millikelvin. We first benchmark the control chip and find an electrical performance consistent with qubit operations of 99.99 per cent fidelity, assuming ideal qubits. Next, we use it to coherently control actual qubits encoded in the spin of single electrons confined in silicon quantum dots and find that the cryogenic control chip achieves the same fidelity as commercial instruments at room temperature. Furthermore, we demonstrate the capabilities of the control chip by programming a number of benchmarking protocols, as well as the Deutsch–Josza algorithm, on a two-qubit quantum processor. These results open up the way towards a fully integrated, scalable silicon-based quantum computer”.

Intel and QuTech

<https://qutech.nl/2022/03/29/intel-qutech-first-industrially-manufactured-qubit/>

29 March 2022. Intel and QuTech announced to offer the first industrially produced qubit. And here some information.

As we have already seen from the discussion about Horse Ridge chip, Intel and QuTech are interested in the development of qubits based on the spin of single electrons captured in a silicon nanoscale device. One of the main advantages of this device is its similarity to conventional transistors. But this is not enough. Currently, semiconductor qubit chips are manufactured in clean rooms using tools, which have been optimized for this purpose. Industrial semiconductor manufacturing, on the other hand, is extremely reliable but is bound by strict design rules. The problem was therefore to understand if a qubit project can be feasible within the framework of industrial rules, which require conditions which are different from those that we have to product quantum dots in laboratoris. The Intel and QuTech collaboration showed that silicon spin qubits are compatible with CMOS semiconductor manufacturing. Lieven Vandersypen, who directs the research for QuTech, says that the device yield achieved by the Intel team was 98 percent, compared to 50 percent of that achieved in the lab.

“The type of quantum information that makes this qubit is the electron spin. The electron is trapped inside a “box”, given by a potential well in an energy landscape, called a quantum dot. The energy landscape is produced by a combination of material properties (similar layouts to a conventional transistor: silicon–silicon oxide interface) and electric fields. In this way it is possible to isolate and address a single electron in the quantum dot and have full control over its spin.”

About qubit manufacturing, see also “Qubits made by advanced semiconductor manufacturing”, di Zwerver, et al. (2022), Nature Electronics, link <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41928-022-00727-9>

"Full-scale quantum computers require the integration of millions of qubits, and the potential of using industrial semiconductor manufacturing to meet this need has driven the development of quantum computing in silicon quantum dots. However, fabrication has so far relied on electron-beam lithography and, with a few exceptions, conventional lift-off processes that suffer from low yield and poor uniformity. Here we report quantum dots that are hosted at a $^{28}\text{Si}/^{28}\text{SiO}_2$

interface and fabricated in a 300 mm semiconductor manufacturing facility using all-optical lithography and fully industrial processing. With this approach, we achieve nanoscale gate patterns with excellent yield. In the multi-electron regime, the quantum dots allow good tunnel barrier control—a crucial feature for fault-tolerant two-qubit gates. Single-spin qubit operation using magnetic resonance in the few-electron regime reveals relaxation times of over 1 s at 1 T and coherence times of over 3 ms".

Quantum circuits and atom-based quantum dots

Let us add news June 22, 2022: “A Huge Step Forward in Quantum Computing Was Just Announced: The First-Ever Quantum Circuit”, di Felicity Nelson.

<https://www.sciencealert.com/a-huge-step-forward-in-quantum-computing-was-just-announced-the-first-ever-quantum-circuit> (archiviato [Archive](#)).

“Australian scientists have created the world's first-ever quantum computer circuit – one that contains all the essential components found on a classical computer chip but at the quantum scale. The landmark discovery, published in Nature today, was nine years in the making.” One author of this article is “Michelle Simmons, founder of Silicon Quantum Computing and director of the Center of Excellence for Quantum Computation and Communication Technology”. “Simmons says the achievement of moving from quantum transistor [2012] to circuit in just nine years is mimicking the roadmap set by the inventors of classical computers”.

The article published on June 22, 2022, in Nature is “Engineering topological states in atom-based semiconductor quantum dots”, M. Kiczynski, S. K. Gorman, H. Geng, M. B. Donnelly, Y. Chung, Y. He, J. G. Keizer & M. Y. Simmons. Nature volume 606, pages 694–699 (2022).

Abstract: “The realization of controllable fermionic quantum systems via quantum simulation is instrumental for exploring many of the most intriguing effects in condensed-matter physics. Semiconductor quantum dots are particularly promising for quantum simulation as they can be engineered to achieve strong quantum correlations. However, although simulation of the Fermi–Hubbard model and Nagaoka ferromagnetism have been reported before, the simplest one-dimensional model of strongly correlated topological matter, the many-body Su–Schrieffer–Heeger (SSH) model, has so far remained elusive—mostly owing to the challenge of precisely engineering long-range interactions between electrons to reproduce the chosen Hamiltonian. Here we show that for precision-placed atoms in silicon with strong Coulomb confinement, we can engineer a minimum of six all-epitaxial in-plane gates to tune the energy levels across a linear array of ten quantum dots to realize both the trivial and the topological phases of the many-body SSH model. The strong on-site energies (about 25 millielectronvolts) and the ability to engineer gates with subnanometre precision in a unique staggered design allow us to tune the ratio between intercell and intracell electron transport to observe clear signatures of a topological phase with two conductance peaks at quarter-filling, compared with the ten conductance peaks of the trivial phase. The demonstration of the SSH model in a fermionic system isomorphic to qubits showcases our highly controllable quantum system and its usefulness for future simulations of strongly interacting electrons”.

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-022-04706-0>

Simulating polyacetylene chain

The article published in Nature considers “the full Hamiltonian of the extended (spinless) Hubbard model for a linear array of N quantum dots, given by”

$$H_U = \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i n_i + \sum_i U_i n_i (n_i - 1) + \sum_i^{N-1} t_{i,i+1} (c_i^\dagger c_{i+1} + h.c.) + \sum_{i,j} V_{i,j} n_i n_j$$

where ε_i is the energy-level of the i-dot of the array, n_i is the dot occupation operator, $t_{i,i+1}$ is the tunnel coupling between nearest-neighbour dots, U_i is a Coulomb term, $V_{i,j}$ is intersite Coulomb interaction, c_i^\dagger, c_i are creation and annihilation operators. The given Hamiltonian is used for the quantum simulation.

From “Scientists engineer quantum processor to emulate a small organic molecule”, by Lachlan Gilbert, <https://phys.org/news/2022-06-scientists-quantum-processor-emulate-small.html> .
Archive 23 June 2022

“A team of quantum computer physicists at UNSW Sydney has engineered a quantum processor at the atomic scale to simulate the behavior of a small organic molecule, solving a challenge set some 60 years ago by theoretical physicist Richard Feynman.”

The quantum circuit is used for the simulation of polyacetylene, that is a repeating chain of carbon and hydrogen atoms, which is characterized by alternating single and double bonds of carbon. The chain is simulated by 10 quantum dots, corresponding to “the precise location of atoms in the polyacetylene chain”.

“The research relied on measuring the electric current through a deliberately engineered 10-quantum dot replica of the polyacetylene molecule as each new electron passed from the source outlet of the device to the drain—the other end of the circuit. ... Not only did the measurements match the theoretical predictions, they matched perfectly.”

Let us now turn to why a chain of 10 atoms was chosen. The reason is that it is “within the size limit of what a classical computer is able to compute. ... Increasing it to a 20-dot chain would see the number of possible interactions rise exponentially, making it difficult for a classical computer to solve.” We are therefore at the limit of the classical simulation possibilities.

Spin qubit in quantum dots

“The idea of using quantum dots for quantum computation was first described in [D. Loss and D. P. DiVincenzo, 1998] and [B. E. Kane, 1998]. In the years since, a variety of qubits in quantum dots have been studied, each with their own strengths and weaknesses. Several of the most common ones will be discussed in the following sections, which will explain how they are defined and controlled, their experimental results, and major challenges they face, in an attempt to give some coherence to a broad field of study.” Suggested readings “Quantum Dots / Spin Qubits”, by Shannon Harvey.

The abstract of this article tells that “Spin qubits in semiconductor quantum dots represent a prominent family of solid state qubits in the effort to build a quantum computer. They are formed when electrons or holes are confined in a static potential well in a semiconductor, giving

them a quantized energy spectrum. The simplest spin qubit is a single electron spin located in a quantum dot, but many additional varieties have been developed, some containing multiple spins in multiple quantum dots, each of which has different benefits and drawbacks. While these spins act as simple quantum systems in many ways, they also experience complex effects due to their semiconductor environment. They can be controlled by both magnetic and electric fields depending on their configuration and are therefore dephased by magnetic and electric field noise, with different types of spin qubits having different control mechanisms and noise susceptibilities”. In the article, we can find the increasing variety of semiconductor devices. The article is available in arXiv <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2204.04261> and it is a review written for the Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Physics, March 2022).

<https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190871994.013.83>

Learning Coulomb Diamonds

Krause, O. et al. (2022). “Learning Coulomb Diamonds in Large Quantum Dot Arrays.” arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.01443.

“Semiconductor qubits controlled by gate electrodes provide a promising route to large scale quantum computation. In these types of systems, individual electrons are confined in quantum dots (QDs) and qubits are formed, for example, by the spin or charge degrees of freedom of the electrons. Controlling and manipulating the quantum state of the qubits is then achieved by applying external voltages via gate electrodes (gate voltages)”. Tuning the “gate voltages, transitions between different states can be realized”. In this manner, we can obtain the quantum computation. To produce large arrays “creates a new challenge, as the simultaneous manual tuning of many gate voltages quickly becomes infeasible for such large arrays.”

“Changing the gate voltages and measuring the quantum dot occupations in the systems ground state leads to a so-called charge-stability diagram (CSD), mapping the high-dimensional voltage space to that of the number of electrons on each dot. Constructing a CSD is typically done by performing many two-dimensional raster scans of pairs of gate voltages. ... While this approach is feasible for small arrays of quantum dots, mapping out the CSD for large arrays quickly becomes a very tedious task. To date, hand-tuned loading and shuttling of electrons in QD arrays has been achieved with as large as 8 or 9 quantum dots [see please the references in arXiv]. Automating this process instead is highly desirable, freeing up valuable time towards more impactful experiments”. In their article, the authors introduced an algorithm for the automated exploration of large quantum dot arrays.

What are the arrays considered by the researchers? “We consider devices of N quantum dots with significant charging energies ($E_c \gg k_B T$) that are weakly-tunnel coupled to each other and to G external gate electrodes, such as the one schematically shown in Fig. 1 (see the figure in arXiv). The gate voltages define a high-dimensional space that can be divided into regions where the device assumes a certain ground state of QD occupations. *These extended regions are referred to as Coulomb diamonds*, because it is the *Coulomb blockade effect* that prevents additional electrons from tunneling onto a quantum dot unless the potential is large enough”.

To understand the Coulomb Diamonds, a suggested reading is “Single Charge Transport and Charge Sensing in Quantum Dots”, Tesi di Fotios Avgidis, Universiteit Twente (UT), Enschede,

2016, http://essay.utwente.nl/69376/1/Avgidis_BA_EEMCS.pdf (Archive).

“By measuring the current through the dot while sweeping the bias voltage for different values of the gate voltage, a source-drain bias voltage versus gate voltage plot can be made (figure 2.9 [in the thesis]). The plot can also contain information about the differential conductance (the derivative of the current with respect to the source-drain bias), which is usually represented by a color gradient. This plot is often called a level spectroscopy diagram or a stability diagram and *always exhibits a characteristic rhombic structure*. Inside the diamond-shaped regions, the number of electrons on the dot is fixed due to the Coulomb blockade effect and no current can flow through them. *These regions are often called Coulomb diamonds*. Each diamond corresponds to a fixed number of N electrons inside the dot. The points at the end of each diamond where the upper right and lower right edge of the diamond join along the gate voltage axis are called degeneracy points”.

Sycamore (Google's Artificial Intelligence division)

Let's now turn to Google and its Sycamore computer, another computer that, like Borealis, has received widespread interest from the press. Sycamore qubits are based on transmons. Sycamore works through quantum gates.

“Quantum supremacy using a programmable superconducting processor”, Frank Arute et al., Ottobre 2019. Nature volume 574, pages 505–510 (2019), <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-019-1666-5>

“The promise of quantum computers is that certain computational tasks might be executed exponentially faster on a quantum processor than on a classical processor. A fundamental challenge is to build a high-fidelity processor capable of running quantum algorithms in an exponentially large computational space. Here we report the use of a processor with programmable superconducting qubits to create quantum states on 53 qubits, corresponding to a computational state-space of dimension 2^{53} (about 10^{16}). Measurements from repeated experiments sample the resulting probability distribution, which we verify using classical simulations. Our Sycamore processor takes about 200 seconds to sample one instance of a quantum circuit a million times—our benchmarks currently indicate that the equivalent task for a state-of-the-art classical supercomputer would take approximately 10,000 years. This dramatic increase in speed compared to all known classical algorithms is an experimental realization of quantum supremacy for this specific computational task, heralding a much-anticipated computing paradigm.”

“We designed a quantum processor named ‘Sycamore’ which consists of a two-dimensional array of 54 (actually 53, one is defective) transmon qubits, where each qubit is tunably coupled to four nearest neighbours, in a rectangular lattice. ... A key systems engineering advance of this device is achieving high-fidelity single- and two-qubit operations, not just in isolation but also while performing a realistic computation with simultaneous gate operations on many qubits. ... In a superconducting circuit, conduction electrons condense into a macroscopic quantum state, such that currents and voltages behave quantum mechanically. Our processor uses transmon qubits, which can be thought of as nonlinear superconducting resonators at 5–7 GHz. The qubit is encoded as the two lowest quantum eigenstates of the resonant circuit. Each transmon has two

controls: a microwave drive to excite the qubit, and a magnetic flux control to tune the frequency. Each qubit is connected to a linear resonator used to read out the qubit state.”

Sycamore and the time-crystals

News December 2021: “Cosa sono i cristalli temporali, appena ottenuti con il computer quantistico di Google”. “Sono particolari strutture che si ripetono e sono regolari nel tempo invece che nello spazio, come avviene per i cristalli tradizionali. Un gruppo di Stanford li ha ottenuti grazie al processore quantistico Sycamore”. Viola Rita, 14 Dicembre 2021, Wired Italia, <https://www.wired.it/article/cristalli-temporali-computer-quantistico-google-fisica/> ([Archive](#)).

The experiment is described in Nature, “Time-crystalline eigenstate order on a quantum processor”, di Xiao Mi et al., volume 601, pages 531–536 (2022).

“Quantum many-body systems display rich phase structure in their low-temperature equilibrium states. However, much of nature is not in thermal equilibrium. Remarkably, it was recently predicted that out-of-equilibrium systems can exhibit novel dynamical phases that may otherwise be forbidden by equilibrium thermodynamics, a paradigmatic example being the discrete time crystal (DTC). Concretely, dynamical phases can be defined in periodically driven many-body-localized (MBL) systems via the concept of eigenstate order. In eigenstate-ordered MBL phases, the entire many-body spectrum exhibits quantum correlations and long-range order, with characteristic signatures in late-time dynamics from all initial states.” In the experiment, the researchers implemented uncontrolled-phase (CPHASE) gates, nested on an array of superconducting qubits. The experiment consisted in the observation of “an MBL-DTC and demonstrate its characteristic spatiotemporal response for generic initial states”.

For the experiment, the researchers used an open-ended chain of “20 superconducting transmon qubits (Q_1 to Q_{20}) that are isolated from a two-dimensional grid. We drive the qubits via a time-periodic (Floquet) circuit”:

$$\hat{U}_F = e^{-\frac{i}{2} \sum_i h_i \hat{Z}_i} e^{-\frac{i}{4} \sum_i h_i \hat{Z}_i \hat{Z}_{i+1}} e^{-\frac{i}{2} \pi g \sum_i h_i \hat{X}_i}$$

In the propagator, the first term contains longitudinal fields, the second is the Ising interaction, and the third the “x rotation by πg ”. In the propagator we can find the Pauli operators.

Sycamore and the chemistry

From Wired Italia: “La prima simulazione di una reazione chimica con un computer quantistico”. “Con Sycamore, il super computer quantistico di Google, gli scienziati sono riusciti a simulare per la prima volta una reazione chimica di una molecola composta da 4 atomi. Tanto che in futuro i computer quantistici potrebbero aiutare a studiare e simulare nuove sostanze chimiche”, by Viola Rita , 31.08.2020,

<https://www.wired.it/scienza/lab/2020/08/31/prima-simulazione-reazione-chimica-computer-quantistico/> ([Archive](#)).

“Per la simulazione della diazina i ricercatori hanno utilizzato 12 dei 54 qubit – i bit quantistici,

le unità dell'informazione quantistica – una prova molto più ampia e strutturata di tutte le precedenti”.

The research has been published in Science, “Hartree-Fock on a superconducting qubit quantum computer”. At the page <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abb9811> we can find a “twelve-qubit quantum computing for chemistry”. “Accurate electronic structure calculations are considered one of the most anticipated applications of quantum computing that will revolutionize theoretical chemistry and other related fields. Using the Google Sycamore quantum processor, Google AI Quantum and collaborators performed a variational quantum eigensolver (VQE) simulation of two intermediate-scale chemistry problems: the binding energy of hydrogen chains (as large as H_{12}) and the isomerization mechanism of diazene (see the Perspective by Yuan). The simulations were performed on up to 12 qubits, involving up to 72 two-qubit gates, and show that it is possible to achieve chemical accuracy when VQE is combined with error mitigation strategies. The key building blocks of the proposed VQE algorithm are potentially scalable to larger systems that cannot be simulated classically.”

The Sycamore QPU

Sycamore architecture

Arute, F., Arya, K., Babbush, R., Bacon, D., Bardin, J. C., Barends, R., ... & Martinis, J. M. (2019). *Quantum supremacy using a programmable superconducting processor*. Nature, 574(7779), 505-510.

“In a superconducting circuit, conduction electrons condense into a macroscopic quantum state, such that currents and voltages behave quantum mechanically. Our processor uses transmon qubits, which can be thought of as nonlinear superconducting resonators at 5–7 GHz. The qubit is encoded as the two lowest quantum eigenstates of the resonant circuit. Each transmon has two controls: a **microwave drive to excite the qubit**, and a **magnetic flux control to tune the frequency**. Each qubit is connected to a linear resonator used to read out the qubit state. As shown in (the image given above), **each qubit is also connected to its neighbouring qubits** using a new adjustable **coupler**. Our coupler design allows us to quickly tune the qubit–qubit coupling ... One qubit did not function properly, so the device uses 53 qubits and 86 couplers.”

“The processor is fabricated using aluminium for metallization and Josephson junctions, and

indium for bump-bonds between two silicon wafers. The chip is wire-bonded to a superconducting circuit board and cooled to below 20 mK in a dilution refrigerator to reduce ambient thermal energy to well below the qubit energy. The processor is connected through filters and attenuators to room-temperature electronics, which synthesize the control signals. The state of all qubits can be read simultaneously by using a frequency-multiplexing technique.”

“We execute single-qubit gates by driving **25-ns microwave pulses resonant** with the qubit frequency **while** the qubit–qubit coupling is turned off. The pulses are shaped to minimize transitions to higher transmon states. ... We therefore optimize the single-qubit operation frequencies to mitigate these error mechanisms.”

Transmon

Sycamore uses transmon qubits like IBM. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transmon> For superconducting quantum computing, a transmon is a superconducting charge qubit, created to reduce the charge noise. It has been developed by Robert J. Schoelkopf, Michel Devoret, Steven M. Girvin, Isaiah T. Chiraira, and colleagues from Yale University in 2007. The name means “transmission line shunted plasma oscillation” qubit. It is a Cooper-pair box "where the two superconductors are also capacitatively shunted in order to decrease the sensitivity to charge noise, while maintaining a sufficient anharmonicity for selective qubit control".

“The transmon achieves its reduced sensitivity to charge noise by significantly increasing the ratio of the Josephson energy to the charging energy. This is accomplished through the use of a large shunting capacitor. The result is energy level spacings that are approximately independent of offset charge.”

A transmon is similar to the “charge qubit”, known as "Cooper-pair box".

Both devices are described by the same Hamiltonian, with different E_J/E_C due to the Josephson junction with an added capacity. E_J is the energy of the Josephson junction, and E_C is the capacitor energy. “Measurement, control and coupling of the transmons is performed by means of microwave resonators with techniques of circuit quantum electrodynamics, also applicable to other superconducting qubits. The coupling to the resonators is done by putting a capacitor between the qubit and the resonator, at a point where the resonator electromagnetic field is biggest”.

Charge qubits

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Charge_qubit

A charge qubit is also known as Cooper-pair box. It is a qubit whose basis states are charge states (i.e. states which represent the presence or absence of excess Cooper pairs in the island). In superconducting quantum computing, a charge qubit is formed by a tiny superconducting island coupled by a Josephson junction (or practically, superconducting tunnel junction) to a superconducting reservoir. The state of the qubit is determined by the number of Cooper pairs which have tunneled across the junction. The charge states of an "island" involve a macroscopic number of conduction electrons of the island. The quantum superposition of charge states can be

achieved by tuning the gate voltage U that controls the chemical potential of the island. The charge qubit is typically read-out by electrostatically coupling the island to an extremely sensitive electrometer such as the radio-frequency single-electron transistor.

And here we can find another detail that brings us to the logistics of quantum computing, and it concerns manufacturing. It occurs with the technology of microelectronics and superconductivity. “Charge qubits are fabricated using techniques similar to those used for microelectronics. The devices are usually made on silicon or sapphire wafers using electron beam lithography (different from phase qubit, which uses photolithography) and metallic thin film evaporation processes. To create Josephson junctions, a technique known as shadow evaporation is normally used; this involves evaporating the source metal alternately at two angles through the lithography defined mask in the electron beam resist. This results in two overlapping layers of the superconducting metal, in between which a thin layer of insulator (normally aluminum oxide) is deposited.”

“To-date, the realizations of qubits that have had the most success are ion traps and NMR, with Shor's algorithm even being implemented using NMR. However, it is hard to see these two methods being scaled to the hundreds, thousands, or millions of qubits necessary to create a quantum computer. Solid-state representations of qubits are much more easily scalable, but they themselves have their own problem: decoherence. Superconductors, however, have the advantage of being more easily scaled, and they are more coherent than normal solid-state systems.”

Google, IBM and the quantum supremacy

From [Sole24Ore](#) , 24 October 2019, [Archive](#) . “Il computer quantistico è realtà. Supremazia di Google ma Ibm non ci sta”, by Luca Tremolada. “Risolto in 200 secondi un calcolo che un supercomputer tradizionale risolverebbe in 10.000 anni. Google conquista la supremazia nel quantum computing ma Ibm non ci sta e non ci crede”. The news concerns Sycamore. But Sycamore is an experiment on a quantum calculation.

There is no computer that has been programmed and solved in a time interval of 200 seconds a problem (any problem) that a classical supercomputer would solve in 10,000 years. And in fact the article emphasizes: “Quello pubblicato ieri [24 Ottobre 2019] è un esperimento di informatica teorica. Gli scienziati di Google avrebbero dimostrato la capacità di un processore quantistico di risolvere un calcolo che un computer tradizionale compierebbe in anni e anni.” [Sole24Ore]. “Fino a oggi, spiegano gli esperti di intelligenza artificiale, nessuno era riuscito a mantenere una coerenza quantistica così a lungo. E nessuno sa come ci siano riusciti. Entusiasta Sundar Pichai, il Ceo di Google, in un post sul blog ufficiale ha celebrato la supremazia della sua azienda. Meno felice è Ibm che sta lavorando per commercializzare il proprio computer quantistico e che sul Wsj ha dichiarato di non credere ai risultati raggiunti, affermando che il problema che è stato affidato alla macchina di Big G potrebbe essere gestito da un computer tradizionale in 2 giorni e mezzo e non in diecimila anni” [Sole24Ore]

And now, let's see an article that mentions quantum supremacy and Sycamore computer, as well as IBM. But we don't find only the computers of Google and IBM; we also find the quantum computer Jiuzhang.

“Cos'è la supremazia quantistica e perché è importante”. [no author and date] www.fastweb.it/fastweb-plus/digital-magazine/cos-e-la-supremazia-quantistica/ (Archive)

“La corsa alla supremazia quantistica non si ferma. I ricercatori creano computer quantistici sempre più potenti e veloci in grado di eseguire calcoli fino ad oggi ritenuti impossibili coi computer tradizionali. Queste macchine basate sul calcolo quantistico possono così eseguire in appena pochi minuti le elaborazioni che a un normale computer richiederebbero miliardi di anni. Il nuovo record è stato raggiunto dai ricercatori in Cina, i quali, con il supercomputer Jiuzhang, hanno completato in appena 200 secondi un calcolo che avrebbe richiesto ai migliori computer non-quantistici attualmente disponibili circa 2.5 miliardi di anni. La Cina si aggiudica così la supremazia quantistica nel 2020, battendo il precedente record registrato da Google nel 2019, il cui supercomputer Sycamore a 53 qubit ha svolto un calcolo che avrebbe richiesto 10mila anni di computazione "ordinaria" in appena 3 minuti e 20 secondi. Google riuscì così a conquistare la supremazia quantistica, battendo a sua volta il precedente risultato raggiunto dal supercomputer di IBM, che non lasciò volentieri ai ricercatori di Mountain View il primato.” [Fastweb]

“ ... Il primato raggiunto da Google fu contestato da IBM, che rispose duramente all'annuncio della supremazia quantistica accusando Google di aver sbagliato i conteggi e che il supercomputer Summit avrebbe eseguito il calcolo in 2 giorni e mezzo, non 10.000 anni. L'errore, secondo IBM, era nel non considerare che il supercomputer tradizionale avrebbe potuto eseguire i calcoli non solo con una enorme quantità di RAM, ma sfruttando anche lo storage su disco, ottenendo un risultato anche più accurato oltre che più veloce.” [Fastweb]

“Nel 2020 però arrivano nuovi pretendenti per la supremazia quantistica: ricercatori cinesi appartenenti a diverse università e istituzioni che hanno unito le forze per realizzare il computer quantistico Jiuzhang. Al contrario del progetto Sycamore di Google, dove il processore è basato su qubit realizzati con materiali superconduttori, il computer quantistico *Jiuzhang* è *basato su fotoni* in grado di eseguire un unico tipo di operazione molto specifica: il campionamento del bosone gaussiano. Il risultato ottenuto dai ricercatori cinesi è stato pubblicato sulla rivista scientifica *Science* e rappresenta un passo avanti nel calcolo quantistico.” [Fastweb]

Dopo varie altre informazioni si legge: “Il vero problema della valutazione della velocità di un computer quantistico, e quindi della stessa supremazia quantistica, è che questo tipo di elaborazioni viene realizzato per eseguire uno specifico "set" di calcoli. Questi calcoli vengono portati a termine con una velocità incredibile, ma non è affatto detto che si possano ottenere le stesse prestazioni, con lo stesso computer quantistico, su un diverso "set" di istruzioni, come invece avviene per i computer tradizionali, in grado di elaborare una grande gamma di istruzioni di diversa origine e tipologia. Siamo ancora lontani, quindi, dal quantum computing universale”. [Fastweb]

“What is the quantum supremacy and why does it matter”. The race for quantum supremacy does not stop. Researchers are creating ever more powerful and faster quantum computers capable of performing calculations, which had been previously considered as impossible for traditional computers. These machines based on quantum computing can thus perform in just a few minutes a processing that a normal computer performed in billions of years. The new record was achieved by researchers in China that, with the Jiuzhang supercomputer, completed a

calculation in just 200 seconds, a calculation that would have required about 2.5 billion years using the best non-quantum computer currently available. China thus wins quantum supremacy in 2020, beating the previous record by Google in 2019, whose 53 qubit Sycamore supercomputer performed a calculation that would have required 10,000 years of "ordinary" computing in just 3 minutes and 20 seconds. Google was thus able to conquer quantum supremacy, in turn beating the previous result achieved by the IBM supercomputer.

The record achieved by Google was contested by IBM, which responded to the announcement of quantum supremacy, by pointing out that Google miscalculated the time and that the Summit supercomputer would perform the calculation in 2 and a half days, not 10,000 years. According to IBM, the mistake is in the fact that it has not been considered that the traditional supercomputer could have performed the calculations not only with a huge amount of RAM, but also exploiting disk storage, obtaining an even more accurate result as well as faster.

In 2020, however, new pretenders for quantum supremacy arrived: Chinese researchers belonging to different universities and institutions have joined their efforts to create the Jiuzhang quantum computer. Unlike Google's Sycamore project, where the processor is based on superconducting qubits, the Jiuzhang quantum computer is based on photons, able of performing a single type of very specific operation, that is the sampling of Gaussian boson. The result obtained by the Chinese researchers was published in the scientific journal *Science* and represents a step forward in quantum computing.

We can also read in the Fastweb article that the real problem of the evaluation of the speed of a quantum computer, and therefore of the quantum supremacy itself, is that this type of computer is made to perform a specific set of calculations. These calculations are carried out with incredible speed, but it is by no means certain that the same performance can be obtained, with the same quantum computer, on a different set of instructions, as is the case for traditional computers, capable of elaborate a wide range of instructions of different origin and typology. We are therefore still a long way from universal quantum computing.

How do optical quantum computers work?

The boreal light

Advantage using photons (Jiuzhang)

The advantage of Jiuzhang is described by Zhong, H. S. et al. (2020). Quantum computational advantage using photons. *Science*, 370(6523), 1460-1463. Preprint available in <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/2012/2012.01625.pdf>

“Inspired by the original proposal of Aaronson and Arkhipov, numerous experiments have demonstrated boson sampling with continuously increasing complexity. However, scaling up boson sampling to a computationally interesting regime remained an outstanding experimental challenge. The early proof-of-principle demonstrations of boson sampling used probabilistic, post-selected pseudo-single photons from parametric down-conversion (PDC). ... Recently,

Gaussian Boson Sampling (GBS) has emerged as a new paradigm that can not only provide a highly efficient approach to large-scale implementations but also offer potential applications in graph-based problems, point processes, and quantum chemistry”. Instead of using “single photons, GBS makes full use of the Gaussian nature of the PDC sources and utilizes single-mode squeezed states (SMSS) as input non-classical light sources which can be deterministically prepared. ... Computing the Torontonian, which is an infinite sum of Hafnians, is a computationally hard problem in the complexity class $\#P$. Many efforts have been devoted to benchmarking the classical computational capacity of calculating the Hafnians and Torontonians on supercomputers using continuously optimized algorithms. The most efficient method so far reported that it takes about two days to evaluate a Torontonian function for a 50-photon click pattern”.

On Torontonian, see please Quesada, N., Arrazola, J. M., & Killoran, N. (2018). “Gaussian boson sampling using threshold detectors”, Physical Review A and other references given in Science's article.

The article by Zhong, H. S. et al. (2020) describes the quantum computer. Very shortly: it starts from the quantum light source arrays. Laser is Mira 900, 1.4 W pulsed 250 kHz, central wavelength 776 nm, pulse width 200 fs. The researchers used a repeater at ~ 80 MHz. They used a “deformable mirror to cancel unwanted chirp and dispersion of the laser pulse, reshaping it to reach Fourier transform limit”. In this manner, photons useful for simulation are produced. “The laser is split into 13 paths with equal intensity, and focused on 25 individual PPKTP crystals”. They resulted “25 two-mode squeezed states (TMSSs) as input, which, due to our hybrid-encoding (which will be discussed later) unitary transformation, is equivalent to 50 SMSSs [single-mode squeezed states]. The relative phase and squeezing parameter for each pair are” given in the article. “The whole optical setup - from the 25 PPKTPs to the 100-mode interferometer - must be locked to a fixed phase in the presence of various environmental perturbations. ... After propagating through a ~ 2 -m free space and 20-m optical fiber, a ~ 10 μ W laser pulse is separated by a dichromatic mirror, which is then combined on a beam splitter with the reference laser pulse. ... After the dichromatic mirror ... the squeezed states are then sent into the multi-mode interferometer, ... In the output of this interferometer, half- and quarter-wave plates set at random angles are used to apply random transformations between the two orthogonal polarizations, which are then split into two spatial modes using 50 polarizing beam splitters. ... Finally, the 100 output modes are detected by 100 superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors with an average efficiency of 81% (see SOM)”.

The last page in <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/2012/2012.01625.pdf> shows the computer. Spectacular!

Zuchongzhi 2.1

Chinese research is not only limited to qumode computer.

english.cas.cn/newsroom/cas_media/202110/t20211028_289325.shtml October 2021. “China Achieves Quantum Computational Advantage in Two Mainstream Technical Routes”, Editor: LIU Jia | Oct 28, 2021. ([Archive](#))

“A Chinese research team has successfully designed a 66-qubit programmable superconducting quantum computing system named "Zuchongzhi 2.1," significantly enhancing the quantum computational advantage.” China is the “first country to achieve a quantum computational advantage in two mainstream technical routes -- one via photonics quantum computing technology and the other via superconducting quantum computing technology”. [Liu]

In December 2020, the researchers built the quantum computer prototype, Jiuzhang, "through which up to 76 photons were detected, achieving quantum computational advantage.” [Liu]

“Gaussian boson sampling (GBS) based on photons and random quantum circuits sampling based on superconducting qubits are two major technical schemes to demonstrate a quantum computational advantage in experiments. In May this year, the researchers designed a 62-qubit programmable superconducting quantum processor named Zuchongzhi, achieving *two-dimensional programmable quantum walks* on the system”. [Liu]

In October 2021, the advantage was Chinese both for qubit and qumode computers. Today, qumode advantage is passed to Borealis.

Borealis abacus with qumodes

We talked a lot about qubits and their implementation in superconducting and other devices. We also talked about computers with optical QPUs. Are the two systems, which produce for example an IBM QPU and a Xanadu QPU, comparable? Difficult to answer.

“Processori quantici fotonici, la nuova frontiera della capacità di calcolo”, <https://www.fastweb.it/fastweb-plus/digital-magazine/processori-quantici-fotonici-la-nuova-frontiera-della-capacita-di-calcolo/> (archiviato [Archive](#)). “Sfruttare le proprietà della luce infrarossa per costruire un nuovo tipo di processore quantico fotonico: la sfida dei computer quantistici passa dai qumode”.

“La costruzione di un computer quantistico parte prima di tutto dalla ricerca del materiale più adatto per le sue componenti hardware.” Uno nuovo è la luce infrarossa. Stiamo parlando di Xanadu, che ha “realizzato due computer quantici fotonici sfruttando proprio le proprietà dei raggi laser infrarossi. Utilizzare raggi laser piuttosto che materiali superconduttori apre a un nuovo modo di pensare il computer quantistico, che è molto diverso da quello a cui ci stiamo abituando in questi anni. Niente qubit per l'architettura del chip della startup canadese, ma fasci di luce laser infrarossa che trasportano le informazioni "rimbalzando" su un chip al silicio. Come un "abaco" quantistico, il computer elabora complessi algoritmi contando il numero di fotoni nei raggi laser riflessi piuttosto che le perline di legno, rivelandosi così più veloce nel calcolo rispetto a un convenzionale PC”.

“Se quindi nell'abaco le perline di legno vengono mosse seguendo una serie di regole e il risultato finale sarà dato dal numero di perline su ognuna delle righe, nel processore quantico fotonico un set di 8 o 12 fasci laser infrarossi vengono riflessi, combinati e fatti interagire in modo controllato seguendo le regole della meccanica quantistica. Il risultato finale sarà il conteggio del numero di fotoni in ogni fascio dopo aver svolto complessi calcoli.”

Invece del qubit si usa il qumode. “Utilizzando i fotoni come unità fondamentale per trasportare le informazioni, quello che si ottiene è un'architettura del processore quantico fotonico basata

sul "quantum mode" (chiamato anche "qumode") che è caratterizzata da un sistema a variabile continua." Dopo aver ricordato il principio di indeterminazione di Heisenberg, si dice che Xanadu usa lo "squeezing" della luce.

The title of the article is "Photonic quantum processors, the new frontier of computing capacity", that is "Exploiting the properties of infrared light to build a new type of photonic quantum processor: the challenge of quantum computers passes through qumodes".

The creation of a quantum computer starts from the search for the most suitable material for its hardware components. A new one is the infrared light. We are talking of Xanadu, that has created two photonic quantum computers by exploiting the properties of infrared laser rays. Using laser beams rather than superconducting materials opens up a new way of thinking about quantum computing, which is very different from what we are getting used to in recent years. No qubits for the Canadian startup's chip architecture, but beams of infrared laser light that carry information "bouncing" off a silicon chip. Like a quantum "abacus", the computer elaborates complex algorithms by counting the number of photons in the reflected laser rays, rather than the wooden beads, thus revealing itself in the calculus faster than a classical computer.

Therefore, like in the abacus the wooden beads are moved following a series of rules and the final result will be given by the number of beads on each of the lines, in the photonic quantum processor a set of 8 or 12 infrared laser beams are reflected, combined and let them interact in a controlled way following the rules of quantum mechanics. The final result will be the count of the number of photons in each beam, after they have carried out complex calculations.

Instead of the qubit, the qumode is used. Using photons as the fundamental unit to transport information, what we get is a quantum mode photonic processor architecture (also called "qumode") which is characterized by a continuous variable system. After recalling the Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, it is said that Xanadu uses the "squeezing" of light.

Let us also mention "Explore quantum computational advantage with Xanadu's Borealis device on Amazon Braket", by Cedric Lin, Eric Kessler, Jordan Sullivan, and Stefan Natu | on 02 JUN 2022, in Amazon Braket, Announcements, Quantum Technologies.

<https://aws.amazon.com/it/blogs/quantum-computing/explore-quantum-computational-advantage-with-xanadus-borealis-device-on-amazon-braket/> and in particular, let us see what was told about the cloud: "Customers can access Borealis on Braket by using Strawberry Fields, Xanadu's open source library for photonic quantum computing. Like in the experiment above, you can specify different operations to be applied to each qumode with some restrictions arising from the physical architecture of the device. You can define the initial squeezing parameter of each qumode by applications of Sgates [squeezing gates] on each qumode at the beginning of the program. Then, for each of the three loop interferometers and for each qumode, you can specify a single qumode rotation angle via Rgates [rotation], as well as the transmittivity of Bsgates [boson sampling] between the qumode and the time-delayed qumode given by the delay of the respective interferometer."

A new abacus to study indeed.

Borealis is a Lichtperlenspiel.

Qumodes in quantum photonics

We have to learn a new language to program Borealis.

<https://strawberryfields.ai/photronics/concepts/photronics.html>

“Many physical systems are intrinsically continuous, with light being the prototypical example. Such systems reside in an infinite-dimensional Hilbert space, offering a paradigm for quantum computation which is distinct from the qubit model. This continuous-variable model takes its name from the fact that the quantum operators underlying the model have continuous spectra. The CV model is a natural fit for simulating bosonic systems (electromagnetic fields, harmonic oscillators, phonons, Bose-Einstein condensates, or optomechanical resonators) and for settings where continuous quantum operators – such as position & momentum – are present. Even in classical computing, recent advances from deep learning have demonstrated the power and flexibility of a continuous picture of computation”.

We pass from qubit to qumode.

Basic element	Qumodes	Qubits
Relevant operators	Quadrature operators \hat{x}, \hat{p} Mode operators \hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger	Pauli operators $\hat{\sigma}_x, \hat{\sigma}_y, \hat{\sigma}_z$
Common states	Coherent states $ \alpha\rangle$ Squeezed states $ z\rangle$ Number states $ n\rangle$	Pauli eigenstates $ 0/1\rangle, \pm\rangle, \pm i\rangle$
Common gates	Rotation, Displacement, Squeezing, Beamsplitter, Cubic Phase	Phase Shift, Hadamard, CNOT, T Gate

“The dichotomy between qubit and CV systems is perhaps most evident in the basis expansions of quantum states:”

$$\text{Qubit: } |\phi\rangle = \phi_0|0\rangle + \phi_1|1\rangle$$

$$\text{Qumode: } |\psi\rangle = \int dx \psi(x)|x\rangle$$

... nothing to get hung about, Strawberry fields forever

Encoding a qubit in an oscillator

Strawberry Fields tells: “**Qubit-based computations can be embedded into the CV picture**, e.g., by using the **Gottesman-Knill-Preskill (GKP) embedding**, so the CV model is as computationally powerful as its qubit counterparts”.

“Quantum error-correcting codes are constructed that embed a finite-dimensional code space in

the infinite-dimensional Hilbert space of a system described by continuous quantum variables. These codes exploit the noncommutative geometry of phase space to protect against errors that shift the values of the canonical variables q and p . In the setting of quantum optics, fault-tolerant universal quantum computation can be executed on the protected code subspace using linear optical operations, squeezing, homodyne detection, and photon counting; however, nonlinear mode coupling is required for the preparation of the encoded states. Finite-dimensional versions of these codes can be constructed that protect encoded quantum information against shifts in the amplitude or phase of a d -state system. Continuous-variable codes can be invoked to establish lower bounds on the quantum capacity of Gaussian quantum channels.” Gottesman, D., Kitaev, A., & Preskill, J. (2001). “Encoding a qubit in an oscillator”. *Physical Review A*, 64(1), 012310.

Gottesman-Knill-Prekill (GKP) embedding

The web site <https://www.xanadu.ai/photonics> tells that “Xanadu’s architecture is modular and capable of scaling to one million qubits through optical networking. To get there, we are developing a manufacturable, fault-tolerant module consisting of four components that work together to generate, entangle, and process thousands of qubits.”

Qubits? Let us read the Blueprint Paper by Xanadu. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.02905>

“Photonics is currently the only platform that enables building room-temperature, modular, and easily-networked quantum computers. The advantages of photonics are augmented by using qubits that are encoded into the state of light using a method proposed by Gottesman, Kitaev and Preskill (GKP). These **so-called GKP qubits** are a leading candidate for optical quantum computation because: (i) an important class of gates, operations, and measurements on these states can be performed with Gaussian resources, which are natively available and easy to implement on integrated photonic devices, and (ii) they are inherently robust to noise and optical losses. Moreover, computation with GKP qubits can be performed at room-temperature, which makes them especially attractive for the scalable fabrication and operation of quantum computers.”

“Specifically, GKP qubits can be produced by **Gaussian boson sampling (GBS) devices**. These devices displace, squeeze, and interfere light – all Gaussian operations – and then guide it toward photon-counting detectors.”

The Borealis chip is proposed in the following manner: “Photonic quantum computation using hybrid resource states. A planar chip (top) generates a resource state for fault tolerant quantum computation. The optical modes comprising the lattice are either GKP states of light (red dots) or squeezed light (blue dots); whenever the former is unavailable – its generation is probabilistic – the latter is guaranteed to be there. The light is measured at homodyne detectors (bottom), whose output is carefully decoded. Measurement settings are changed accordingly to perform measurement-based quantum computation”.

The light is squeezed “if its electric field strength \mathcal{E} for some phases θ has a quantum uncertainty smaller than that of a coherent state. The term squeezing thus refers to a reduced quantum uncertainty. To obey Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation, a squeezed state must also have phases at which the electric field uncertainty is anti-squeezed, i.e. larger than that of a coherent

state”.

By means of squeezed light we can have qubits through the GBS, Gaussian Boson Sampling. “GBS state preparation consists of sending N displaced squeezed vacuum states into a general interferometer on N modes, followed by PNR (photon-number-resolver) detectors on $N - 1$ of the modes, as depicted in Fig. 1.” (see please the Blueprint)

In the abstract it is stressed that “Central to our (Xanadu) architecture is the generation and manipulation of three-dimensional resource states comprising both bosonic qubits and squeezed vacuum states. The proposal exploits state-of-the-art procedures for the non-deterministic generation of bosonic qubits combined with the strengths of continuous-variable quantum computation, namely the implementation of Clifford gates using easy-to-generate squeezed states”.

Optical hybrid approaches to quantum information

Suggested reading - Van Loock, P. (2011). Optical hybrid approaches to quantum information. *Laser & Photonics Reviews*, 5(2), 167-200.

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1002.4788.pdf>

“This article reviews recent hybrid approaches to optical quantum information processing, in which both discrete and continuous degrees of freedom are exploited. There are well-known limitations to optical single-photon-based qubit and multi-photon-based qumode implementations of quantum communication and quantum computation, when the toolbox is restricted to the most practical set of linear operations and resources such as linear optics and Gaussian operations and states. The recent hybrid approaches aim at pushing the feasibility, the efficiencies, and the fidelities of the linear schemes to the limits, potentially adding weak or measurement-induced nonlinearities to the toolbox.”

Hi, friends

<https://discuss.pennylane.ai/t/borealis-is-qubit-based/1956>

The screenshot shows a forum post by user 'Kuma-quant2' dated JUN 5. The post content is: 'Hi, friends. I try to study GBS using Borealis. About the machine, "Borealis boasts over 216 squeezed-state qubits" can be seen in news release. I'm cofusing. What "qubits" mean in this context? What is the difference from "qumodes"?'. Below the post, there are icons for heart, share, and a dropdown arrow. At the bottom, a statistics bar shows: created (K Jun 5), last reply (K Jun 7), replies (2), views (190), users (2), like (1), link (1). There are also icons for a user and a GitHub logo.

created	last reply	replies	views	users	like	link
Jun 5	Jun 7	2	190	2	1	1

And here, the suggested link: https://pennylane.ai/qml/demos/tutorial_photonics.html (Archive) - Photonic quantum computers. Author: Alvaro Ballon. Posted: 31 May 2022. Last updated: 16 June 2022.

There are different manners of using photons for calculus. “We will focus on *linear optical quantum computing*, an approach that has already achieved quantum advantage. It is being developed further by Xanadu, PsiQuantum, and other institutions around the globe. Unlike other physical systems, photonics allows us access to an infinite number of states. How can we leverage these extra states to make quantum computers?” Reading the document, “You will learn how to prepare, measure, and manipulate the quantum states of light, and how we can encode qubits in photons. Moreover, you will identify the strengths and weaknesses of photonic devices in terms of Di Vincenzo’s criteria, introduced in the blue box below.”

We have already seen the **DiVincenzo's criteria**. Let us see how Pennylane gives them.

1. Well-characterized and scalable qubits. We must be able to define the qubit in a physically characterizable way. Defined in this manner, the qubit is useful if the set of such objects is scalable.
2. Qubit initialization. We must be able to prepare an initial state and be able to repeat the preparation of that state, in a reasonable way concerning errors.
3. Long coherence times. Qubits must maintain their state, at least until operations are performed on them.
4. Universal set of gates. To act on qubits we must have unitary, single-qubit or two-qubit operators.
5. Measurement of individual qubits. "To read the result of a quantum algorithm, we must accurately measure the final state of a pre-chosen set of qubits."

To be a quantum computer, photons must be manipulated to meet DiVincenzo's criteria. Let us then follow Alvaro Ballon's text, starting with the Gaussian states of light.

Why are the quantum states of light so durable? Photons rarely interact with each other, and this means that it is easy to avoid unwanted interactions. But to have a quantum computer, we need

"multi-qubit gates, which means that photons must be made to communicate with each other somehow!". We can make photons interact using a material.

Let's start with a linear material. "With linear materials, we can produce a subset of the so-called Gaussian states. They can be fabricated with a 100% success rate using common optical devices, so they are our safest tool in photonics." By definition: "A photonic system is said to be in a Gaussian state if its Wigner function is a two-dimensional Gaussian function". An example: the states produced by lasers are called coherent states, and are also Gaussian. Coherent states, in general, can have non-zero expectation values for the quadratures (i.e., they are not centered around the origin).

The coherent states are produced by the laser, "but how can we obtain any Gaussian state of our liking? This is achieved through Gaussian operations, which transform a Gaussian state to another Gaussian state. These operations are relatively easy to implement in a lab using some of the optical elements ". Waveguides, phase-shifters and beamsplitters are used. And here, please remember that the Borealis machine uses squeezed light. The text does not explain, but says that the technology is mature for squeezing light.

After a detailed discussion of on gaussian states, the entanglement is discussed, to create non-gaussian states. "Entanglement is not a problem, since combinations of Gaussian operations involving squeezers and beamsplitters can easily create entangled states! Let us set on the more challenging mission to find a way to prepare non-Gaussian states. All of the operations that we have learned so far—displacements, rotations, squeezing—are Gaussian. Do we need some kind of strange material that will implement a non-Gaussian operation? That's certainly a possibility, and there are materials which can provide non-Gaussian interactions—like the **Kerr effect**. But relying on these non-linear materials is far from optimal, since the Kerr effect is weak and we don't have much freedom to manipulate the setup into getting an arbitrary non-Gaussian state."

No Kerr effect then, "But there's one non-Gaussian operation that's been right in front of our eyes all this time. The **measurement of the number of photons** takes a Gaussian state and collapses it into a Fock state (although this destroys the photons); therefore, photon-number detection is not a Gaussian operation. Measuring the exact number of photons is not that easy. We need fancy devices known a photon-number resolving detectors (commonly abbreviated as PNRs), which are superconductor-based, so they work only at low temperatures. Combined with squeezed states and beamsplitters, we have all the ingredients to produce non-Gaussian states. Let's explore how this works. The main idea is to tweak a particular photonic circuit known as a **Gaussian Boson Sampler**, which is shown below."

The diagram above shows three registers with three squeezers, which mix the lines in three beamsplitters, from which three registers emerge that lead to three counters. By removing a counter, the lower register is shown to produce a non-Gaussian state, in a probabilistic way.

“Circuits like the above can, after photon detection of the other qumodes, produce non-Gaussian states. The reason is that the final state of the circuit is entangled, and we apply a non-Gaussian operation to some of the qumodes. This measurement affects the remaining qumode, whose state becomes non-Gaussian in general. This is the magic of quantum mechanics: due to entanglement, a measurement on a physical system can affect the state of another! Moreover, one can show that generalizations of the GBS circuit above can be built to produce any non-Gaussian state that we want”.

Why are we interested in non-Gaussian states? We are interested in them because we need them to emulate qubits with qumodes. “A way that has proven to be quite robust to errors is to encode qubits in states of light, using a special type of non-Gaussian states called GKP states”. These states are produced by the GBS circuit.

In pennylane.ai/qml/demos/tutorial_photonics.html we can find how to implement X, H and CNOT by means of optical devices.

But now, let us return to DiVincenzo's criteria.

“The second criterion, the ability to prepare a qubit, is clearly a challenge. We need GKP states, but these cannot be prepared deterministically; we need to get a bit lucky. We can bypass this by multiplexing, that is, using many Gaussian Boson Sampling circuits in parallel. Moreover, higher-quality GKP states need larger circuits, which in turn can decrease the probability of qubit production. How can we try to solve this? Xanadu is currently following a hybrid approach. When we fail to produce a GKP state, Xanadu’s architecture produces squeezed states using a separate squeezer. Strongly-entangled squeezed states are a precious resource, since other encodings beyond GKP allow us to use these states as a resource for (non-universal) quantum computing”.

Quadrature

<https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/193061/quadrature-in-quantum-optics>

([Archive](#)) . An user asks: “I am reading a chapter about Squeezed state, and came across this word, quadrature, which I have never seen before in the book. Here is the quote from that chapter.” And here the text: “A general class of minimum-uncertainty states are known as squeezed states. In general, a squeezed state may have less noise in one quadrature than a coherent state. [...]” “I have looked up on the internet and found explanations to be very confusing. Could you help explain to me the meaning of quadrature?”

The answer is to read Wikipedia. “I have. However, after reading all of these and other more, I cannot make out the physical meaning of Quadrature. That baffle me.” Reply: “I feel your pain. “Quadrature” is used all over the place in several subfields of physics and engineering and it's vaguely defined at best. In this case we can definitely be more specific. Are you familiar with the operators $X=a+a^\dagger$ and $Y=a-a^\dagger$?”

Of course, the user knows the operators, since he is struggling with squeezed states. After some case studies, who answers says: “As you've seen, the word quadrature is overladen with many,

none-too-precise meanings. Here the "quadratures" loosely refer to the position and momentum observables:

$$\hat{x} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(a + a^\dagger) \quad , \quad \hat{p} = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}(a - a^\dagger)$$

where a, a^\dagger (lowering/raising operators), and I've normalized the two observables so that $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}] = i/2$. These two (or measurements coming from these observables) are loosely called "quadratures" because, for a coherent / squeezed state ψ the mean measurements $\langle \psi | \hat{x} | \psi \rangle$ and $\langle \psi | \hat{p} | \psi \rangle$ are sinusoidally-with-time varying quantities which are in phase quadrature, i.e. a quarter cycle out of phase" (see also [Wikipedia](#)).

"The squeezed states are the most general states that saturate (i.e. actually achieve equality in) the Heisenberg product. A coherent state is a special case for which the normalized momentum and position uncertainties are equal, and their product is the uncertainty bound $\hbar/2$. A squeezed state has the same uncertainty product, but the uncertainty on one of position or momentum measurements is smaller than the uncertainty on the other, so one achieves smaller uncertainty than for the corresponding coherent state at the expense of the other. One can generalize the above comments for any "generalized" position and momentum, defined, for any $\phi \in \mathbb{R}$, by:

$$\hat{x} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(e^{i\phi} a + e^{-i\phi} a^\dagger) \quad , \quad \hat{p} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(e^{i\phi} a - e^{-i\phi} a^\dagger)$$

which are conjugate in the QM sense of fulfilling the CCR and the means of whose measurements vary sinusoidally with time, again, in phase quadrature."

<https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/193061/quadrature-in-quantum-optics>

Quantum Machine Learning (Pennylane)

<https://pennylane.ai/qml/whatisqml.html> (<https://archive.ph/yJYQ4>)

"Quantum machine learning is a research area that explores the interplay of ideas from quantum computing and machine learning. For example, we might want to find out whether quantum computers can speed up the time it takes to train or evaluate a machine learning model. On the other hand, we can leverage techniques from machine learning to help us uncover quantum error-correcting codes, estimate the properties of quantum systems, or develop new quantum algorithms."

Pennylane is a "cross-platform Python library for differentiable programming of quantum computers. Train a quantum computer the same way as a neural network." <https://pennylane.ai>

An application "Modelling chemical reactions on a quantum computer"

https://pennylane.ai/qml/demos/tutorial_chemical_reactions.html

Borealis (Wired)

Wired is mentioned Borealis too.

<https://www.wired.it/article/computer-quantistico-processore-fotonico-superveloce/> (Archive).

“Un processore fotonico superveloce per il computer quantistico del futuro”, di Sandro Iannaccone, 6 Giugno 2022. “Una equipe di scienziati è riuscita a “programmare” particelle di luce ottenendo uno strumento incredibilmente potente”. Si noti che “programmare” è un virgolettato.

“Da 9mila anni a 36 microsecondi. A tanto ammonta l’incredibile balzo in avanti per il computer quantistico permesso da un nuovo processore fotonico messo a punto dagli scienziati di Xanadu Quantum Technology e dei National Institutes of Standard and Technology. Stando a quanto raccontano sulla rivista Nature, infatti, il loro dispositivo, Borealis, sarebbe stato in grado di risolvere un problema computazionale (la cosiddetta boson sampling challenge) in un tempo di gran lunga inferiore a quello necessario ai più potenti supercomputer “tradizionali”. L’impresa è stata salutata come un grande avanzamento nel campo dei computer quantistici e come il raggiungimento del cosiddetto vantaggio quantistico”.

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-022-04725-x>

“ ... i processori quantistici usano i qubit, particelle subatomiche come fotoni o elettroni [più avanti vediamo che il fotone è detto “flying qubit”], che invece possono immagazzinare molte più informazioni: nei processori tradizionali infatti i due stati possibili (zero e uno) sono legati al flusso degli elettroni (cioè al passaggio di corrente), mentre in quelli quantistici ogni singolo elettrone trasporta un’informazione, il che amplifica enormemente la potenza di calcolo. Le leggi della meccanica quantistica, infatti, postulano (tra le altre cose) che ogni particella sia soggetta al cosiddetto principio di sovrapposizione, una legge secondo la quale la particella si può trovare contemporaneamente, e con probabilità diverse, in più stati differenti: in virtù di questo principio si può “superare” il dualismo acceso/spento e veicolare molta più informazione, parallelizzando i calcoli e svolgendo così molte più operazioni contemporaneamente”.

Iannaccone parla solo di qubit, e quindi ricordiamo che abbiamo processori che usano i qubit e processori che usano i qumode. Con Borealis, si producono i GKP qubit. Nella quantum communication, il fotone è visto come un “flying qubit”, nel senso che il fotone viene a emulare il qubit.

Con Borealis, “gli scienziati si sono serviti di una macchina fotonica che usa le particelle di luce (i fotoni, per l’appunto) per **rappresentare** i qubit, [giustamente si dice “rappresentare”] per risolvere la cosiddetta boson sampling challenge, ossia un problema fisico/computazionale in cui si “preparano” dei fasci di luce, li si indirizzano verso una rete di specchi e separatori di fasci e poi si conta quanti fotoni arrivano al rivelatore posto alla fine del “percorso”. Un problema la cui risoluzione non ha alcuna implicazione pratica particolarmente importante, ma che costituisce un ottimo “banco di prova” per testare le prestazioni di un computer. Fino a questo momento, si era tentato di risolvere il problema con un numero di fotoni compreso tra 76 e 113; Borealis è riuscito ad arrivare a “contare” ben 219 fotoni, con una media (rispetto a tutte le simulazioni) di 125, in un tempo di 36 microsecondi. Un’impresa che, stando sempre ai calcoli dei ricercatori, un computer tradizionale avrebbe impiegato circa 9mila anni per portare a termine.”

Wired li chiama qubit, ma sono delle rappresentazioni, ottenute con embedding e qumode.

L'articolo sottolinea una cosa importante, ed è che il computer Borealis si cimenta sul Boson Sample Challenge, che è un programma di simulazione per un sistema di fotoni. Borealis è il sistema quantistico adatto a simulare un sistema quantistico bosonico, come detto da Feynman nel 1982.

"A superfast photonic processor for the quantum computer of the future", by Sandro Iannaccone, June 6, 2022. "A team of scientists has managed to "program" particles of light obtaining an incredibly powerful tool". From 9 thousand years to 36 microseconds. An incredible leap forward for the quantum computing, made possible by a new photonic processor developed by scientists at Xanadu Quantum Technology and the National Institutes of Standard and Technology. According to what they tell in the journal Nature, in fact, their device Borealis would have been able to solve a computational problem (the so-called boson sampling challenge) in a time far shorter than that necessary for the most powerful "traditional" supercomputer. This feature was hailed as a great advance in the field of quantum computers and marked with the achievement of the so-called quantum advantage.

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-022-04725-x>

Sandro Iannaccone tells that the quantum processors use qubits, subatomic particles such as photons or electrons [later on we will see that the photon is called "flying qubit"], which can store much more information: in traditional processors the two possible states (zero and one) are linked to the flow of electrons (i.e. to the passage of current), while in quantum ones every single electron carries information, and this fact greatly amplifies the computing power. The laws of quantum mechanics postulate (among other things) that every particle is subjected to the so-called superposition principle, a law according to which the particle can be found simultaneously, and with different probabilities, in several different states. By virtue of this principle, it is possible to "overcome" the dualism on / off and convey much more information, parallelizing the calculations and thus carrying out many more operations at the same time.

Iannaccone is mentioning only the "qubits", and therefore it is better to remember that we have processors that use qubits and processors that use qumodes. With Borealis, GKP qubits are produced. In quantum communication, the photon is seen as a "flying qubit", in the sense that the photon comes to emulate the qubit.

With Borealis, - Iannaccone tells - scientists have used a photonic machine that uses particles of light (photons, in fact) to represent qubits, [let us stress that they say "represent"] to solve the so-called boson sampling challenge, that is a physical / computational problem in which beams of light are "prepared", directed towards a network of mirrors and beam separators and then it is counted how many photons arrive at the detector placed at the end of the "path". A problem whose resolution has no particularly important practical implication, but which constitutes an excellent manner for testing the performance of a computer. Up to now, attempts have been made to solve the problem with a number of photons between 76 and 113; Borealis managed to "count" 219 photons, with an average (compared to all simulations) of 125, in a time of 36 microseconds. According to the researchers' evaluation, a traditional computer would have taken about 9 thousand years to complete the calculation.

Wired calls them qubits, but they are representations, obtained with embedding and qumodes. The article underlines one important thing, that is, Borealis computer rests on the Boson Sample

Challenge, which is a simulation program for a photon system. And Borealis is the quantum system suitable for simulating a bosonic quantum system, as told by Feynman in 1982.

Programmable Photonic Processor

“Quantum computational advantage with a programmable photonic processor”, di Lars S. Madsen et al. Nature volume 606, pages75–81 (2022).

“A quantum computer attains computational advantage when outperforming the best classical computers running the best-known algorithms on well-defined tasks. No photonic machine offering programmability over all its quantum gates has demonstrated quantum computational advantage: previous machines were largely restricted to static gate sequences. Earlier photonic demonstrations were also vulnerable to spoofing, in which classical heuristics produce samples, without direct simulation, lying closer to the ideal distribution than do samples from the quantum hardware. Here we report quantum computational advantage using **Borealis**, a photonic processor offering dynamic programmability on all gates implemented. *We carry out Gaussian boson sampling (GBS) on 216 squeezed modes entangled with three-dimensional connectivity*, using a time-multiplexed and photon-number-resolving architecture. On average, it would take more than 9,000 years for the best available algorithms and supercomputers to produce, using exact methods, a single sample from the programmed distribution, whereas Borealis requires only 36 μ s. This runtime advantage is over 50 million times as extreme as that reported from earlier photonic machines. Ours constitutes a very large GBS experiment, registering events with up to 219 photons and a mean photon number of 125. This work is a critical milestone on the path to a practical quantum computer, validating key technological features of photonics as a platform for this goal.”

An here what we can find in the text. “Only a handful of experiments have used quantum devices to carry out computational tasks that are outside the reach of present-day classical computers. In all of these, the computational task involved sampling from probability distributions that are widely believed to be exponentially hard to simulate using classical computation. One such demonstration relied on a 53-qubit programmable superconducting processor, whereas another used a non-programmable photonic platform implementing Gaussian boson sampling (GBS) with 50 squeezed states fed into a static random 100-mode interferometer. Both were shortly followed by larger versions, respectively enjoying more qubits and increased control over brightness and a limited set of circuit parameters. In these examples, comparison of the duration of the quantum sampling experiment to the estimated runtime and scaling of the best-known classical algorithms placed their respective platforms within the regime of quantum computational advantage.”

“The superconducting quantum supremacy demonstrations serve as crucial milestones on the path to full-scale quantum computation. On the other hand, the choice of technologies used in the photonic machines, and their consequential lack of programmability and scalability, places them outside any current proposed roadmap for fault-tolerant photonic quantum computing or any GBS application. A demonstration of photonic quantum computational advantage incorporating hardware capabilities required for the platform to progress along the road to fault-tolerance is still lacking”.

Hence we have the study on the programmable photonic processor. Where is it programmable? The answer is "Quantum computational advantage with a programmable photonic processor", by Lars S. Madsen et al. (2022).

“Using time-domain multiplexing, large one- and two-dimensional cluster states have been deterministically generated with programmable linear operations implemented by projective measurements, whereas similar operations have been implemented using a single loop with reconfigurable phase. These demonstrations leverage low-loss optical fibre for delay lines, which allows photonic quantum information to be effectively buffered. Although groundbreaking, these demonstrations have remained well outside the domain of quantum computational advantage, as they lacked non-Gaussian elements and were unable to synthesize states of sufficient complexity to evade efficient classical simulation. The demonstration of a set of hardware capabilities needed for universal fault-tolerant quantum computing, in the demanding context of quantum computational advantage, would serve as a validating signal that the corresponding technologies are advancing as needed. ... [The researchers] solve technological hurdles associated with time-domain multiplexing, fast electro-optical switching, high-speed photon-number-resolving detection technology and non-classical light generation, to build a scalable and programmable Gaussian boson sampler, which we name Borealis. These features allow us to synthesize a 216-mode state with a three-dimensional entanglement topology.”

Here the Borealis QPU. “A periodic pulse train of single-mode squeezed states from a pulsed OPO [optical parametric oscillator] enters a sequence of three dynamically programmable loop-based interferometers. Each loop contains a VBS [variable beamsplitters], including a programmable phase shifter, and an optical fibre delay line. At the output of the interferometer, the Gaussian state is sent to a 1-to-16 binary switch tree (demux), which partially demultiplexes the output before readout by PNRs [photon-number resolving]. The resulting detected sequence of 216 photon numbers, in approximately 36 μ s, comprises one sample. The fibre delays and accompanying beamsplitters and phase shifters implement gates between both temporally adjacent and distant modes, enabling high-dimensional connectivity in the quantum circuit. ... Each run of the device involves the specification of 1,296 real parameters, corresponding to the sequence of settings for all VBS units”.

More on Borealis

It is necessary to continue with Borealis, because it is about it, that we have the most sensational and most recent news. <https://tech.everyeye.it/notizie/computer-quantistico-risolto-36-microsecondi-problema-9mila-anni-590612.html> an article by Alessio Marino, June 2, 2022.

A success, as we can read in the study published in the prestigious journal Nature, was achieved thanks to the Borealis programmable processor created by the Canadian-based startup Xanadu, which made use of some innovative techniques. The link to Nature leads to <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-022-01402-x>, “Loops simplify a set-up to boost quantum computational advantage”, by Daniel Jost Brod.

The approach used by Xanadu is diametrically different from the machines launched a few years ago by Google. In September 2019 Google announced that it had achieved quantum

supremacy, among Intel's general doubts. And now, Xanadu is able to perform a calculation in 36 microseconds, calculation that otherwise would require at least 9 thousand years,. Xanadu is working at room temperature (and therefore without the need of a QPU being cooled) and with a programmable photonic processor. The problem solved is known as Gaussian Boson sampling.

Is it possible to compare a qubit processor with a qumode one? They are two different systems, simulating different physical systems.

The Nature article by Daniel Jost Brod (June 1, 2022) says:

“Fully fledged quantum computers are still a distant prospect, but Madsen et al. have taken us a step closer to making such devices a reality. In a paper in Nature, they report the construction of Borealis, a quantum device that takes just 36 microseconds to perform a task that would take a classical supercomputer several thousand years to complete, even with state-of-the-art algorithms. The speed-up was made possible by the clever use of optical fibre loops to simplify previous record-holding quantum experiments. Many applications have already been proposed for when large-scale quantum computers do become a reality. They could be used to factor large numbers, compromise certain cryptographic schemes, or simulate systems of interest in quantum chemistry, biology and possibly pharmaceutical research. **Unfortunately, a quantum computer capable of such tasks would require millions of controllable, robust quantum bits (qubits), whereas current quantum processors have fewer than 100 qubits.** And because classical computers have a head start of at least half a century, both in algorithm design and device miniaturization, one might worry that quantum computers are still decades away from catching up with their classical counterparts.”

And here, we can find a fundamental observation, and a slightly different definition of quantum advantage.

“Quantum-computing researchers have a **medium-term goal, known as quantum advantage**, which shifts the focus from clear-cut practical applications to the more modest objective of finding a task — **any task** — that quantum devices can perform faster than can classical supercomputers. The goal is to showcase the raw computational power afforded by quantum mechanics, with, it is to be hoped, considerably fewer resources than are needed for factoring or quantum simulation. One proposal for showing quantum advantage is **Gaussian boson sampling**, which involves preparing special states of light (known as squeezed states), directing them through a network of beam splitters (semi-reflective mirrors) and counting how many photons arrive at each detector. The optical techniques needed for this experiment are well established, as is the theory that can be used to calculate how difficult the task would be for classical computers to perform. Such estimates suggest that an experiment performed with a few hundred photons would already pose a substantial challenge to the simulation capabilities of current supercomputers”. [Daniel Jost Brod]

On Gaussian Boson Sampling, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boson_sampling

Boson sampling

Therefore, the boson sampling is used for qumode computers.

In https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boson_sampling#Gaussian_boson_sampling we can find

remarked that “Boson sampling is a restricted model of **non-universal** quantum computation”. The model has been proposed “by Scott Aaronson and Alex Arkhipov after the original work of L. Troyansky and Naftali Tishby, that explored possible usage of boson scattering to evaluate expectation values of permanents of matrices. The model consists of sampling from the probability distribution of identical bosons scattered by a linear interferometer. Although the problem is well defined for any bosonic particles, its photonic version is currently considered as the most promising platform for a scalable implementation of a boson sampling device, which makes it a **non-universal approach** to linear optical quantum computing. Moreover, while not universal, the boson sampling scheme is strongly believed to implement computing tasks which are hard to implement with classical computers by using far fewer physical resources than a full linear-optical quantum computing setup. This makes it an ideal candidate for demonstrating the power of quantum computation in the near term.”

Borealis was able to solve a non-universal quantum computation problem.

We are currently working on non-universal computers, and there is still a long way to have the universal computer.

Quantum random walk

“Cammino casuale, meglio del calcolatore classico”, 18 febbraio 2013. Le Scienze, https://www.lescienze.it/news/2013/02/18/news/campionamento_bosonico_calcolo_quantistico-1513565/ ([Archive](#)).

And here what the article (in Italian) is telling.

The latest significant advance, in chronological order, is the one described in the pages of the journal Science by Justine B. Spring of the Department of Physics of the University of Oxford, in the United Kingdom, and colleagues. The result is using the physical concept of random walk. In its classical version it concerns, for instance, a particle that must go from a point A to a point B having the possibility to move in several parallel channels, or paths. At any instant, the particle can jump to the path to its right with probability $P(D)$ and to the path to its left with probability $P(S)$. If particles that do not interact are moving in the channels, the probability that any particle can exit from the B end of a channel is given by the sum of the probabilities concerning individual particles. In the quantum case, the matter becomes complicated: the behavior of the particles is described by a wave function f , and the probability of finding a particle in a certain position x is given by the square of $f(x)$. If the channels are crossed by identical particles (indistinguishable), the probabilistic calculations must take this fact into account. In particular, the probability of finding the particle p_1 at the point x_1 and the particle p_2 at the point x_2 must be equal to the probability of finding p_1 at the point x_2 and p_2 at the point x_1 . This means that the two particles are indistinguishable.

This indistinguishability poses some restrictions on the wave functions, which result in the existence of bosons, characterized by having an integer spin, and of fermions, which have half-odd integer spin. Whether or not obeying the Pauli exclusion principle, it forces bosons to follow the Bose-Einstein statistics while the fermions follow the Fermi-Dirac statistics. The symmetry properties for the exchange of two particles shown by bosons and fermions are different: a system composed of identical bosonic particles is always in a completely

symmetrical global state under the exchange of two particles. If the system is composed of identical fermions it is always in an anti-symmetrical state due to the exchange of two fermions. Let us now take a boson system suitable for boson sampling.

A system of this kind can be made of a series of parallel waveguides placed on the surface of a chip, so close that the photons that pass through them and also from one guide to another. A single photon detector is placed at the end of each channel. By varying the characteristics of the channels and continuing the measurements for a sufficiently long time, it was possible to measure the distribution of probability of the output from the different channels, about the transmission of a certain number of photons. The link with quantum computing is due to the fact that with N channels, the probability distribution is proportional to a certain function, known as "permanent", of a NxN matrix linked to the characteristics of the channels themselves, which can be controlled experimentally. With a classical computer, the calculation of the permanent becomes exponentially more complex as N increases. Spring and colleagues showed that boson sampling surpasses classical computation, because it is not using logic gates, since in classical hardware "quantum" building blocks "are not available or are not easily controllable". After all, as Feynman said, it is better to have a quantum system simulated by a quantum system.

The article by Spring et al. (2013) is "Boson sampling on a photonic chip". Science, or arXiv, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1212.2622.pdf> There we can find the conditional probability between exit and enter states. Let be $|T\rangle = |T_1 \dots T_M\rangle$ the input state and $|S\rangle = |S_1 \dots S_M\rangle$ a given exit state. The probability is:

$$P(\mathbf{S}|\mathbf{T}) = |\langle \mathbf{S} | \Psi_{out} \rangle|^2 = \frac{|\text{Per}(\Lambda^{\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{T}})|^2}{\prod_{j=1}^M S_j! \prod_{i=1}^M T_i!}$$

(see please definitions in the Spring et al. article, and suplementar material).

"Per" means permanent of the NxN matrix.

We can also see [https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Permanente_\(matematica\)](https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Permanente_(matematica)) or https://strawberryfields.ai/photonics/demos/run_boson_sampling.html (Archive).

The article in "Le Scienze" adds that in a theoretical work, Andrew M. Childs, University of Waterloo, Ontario, and colleagues consider the random path constituted by a graph at the vertices of which there are bosons, according to the scheme known as the Bose-Hubbard model. Bosons represent bits of quantum information and constitute the elements on which the architecture of quantum computers should be based. In this case, scientists have shown that, by implementing logical operations in random paths, it is possible to arrive at universal quantum computing. The article is by Childs, A. M., Gosset, D., & Webb, Z. (2013). with title "Universal computation by multiparticle quantum walk". Science, available on arXiv, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1205.3782.pdf> .

See also https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_walk

"Quantum walks are quantum analogues of classical random walks. In contrast to the classical random walk, where the walker occupies definite states and the randomness arises due to

stochastic transitions between states, in quantum walks randomness arises through: (1) quantum superposition of states, (2) non-random, reversible unitary evolution and (3) collapse of the wave function due to state measurements.”

And so we are in a new quantum way of thinking.

“Quantum walks are motivated by the widespread use of classical random walks in the design of randomized algorithms, and are part of several quantum algorithms. For some oracular problems, quantum walks provide an exponential speedup over any classical algorithm. ... The well-known Grover search algorithm can also be viewed as a quantum walk algorithm”.

Supremacy test

Let us add some information on supremacy tests for superconducting qubits. From the article entitled “A blueprint for demonstrating quantum supremacy with superconducting qubits”, by Neill, C. et al. Science 360, 195–199 (2018), DOI <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao4309> or <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1709.06678>

“Using 9 superconducting qubits, we demonstrate an immediate path towards quantum supremacy. By individually tuning the qubit parameters, we are able to generate thousands of unique Hamiltonian evolutions and probe the output probabilities. The measured probabilities obey a universal distribution, consistent with uniformly sampling the full Hilbert-space. As the number of qubits in the algorithm is varied, the system continues to explore the exponentially growing number of states. Combining these large datasets with techniques from machine learning allows us to construct a model which accurately predicts the measured probabilities. We demonstrate an application of these algorithms by systematically increasing the disorder and observing a transition from delocalized states to localized states. By extending these results to a system of 50 qubits, we hope to address scientific questions that are beyond the capabilities of any classical computer”.

“A programmable quantum system consisting of merely 50 to 100 qubits could revolutionize scientific research. While such a platform is naturally suited to address problems in quantum chemistry and materials science, applications range to fields as far as classical dynamics and computer science. A key milestone on the path towards realizing these applications will be the demonstration of an algorithm which exceeds the capabilities of any classical computer - achieving quantum supremacy. Sampling problems are an iconic example of algorithms designed specifically for this purpose. A successful demonstration of quantum supremacy would prove that engineered quantum systems, while still in their infancy”.

With Sycamore, the researchers (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-019-1666-5>) compared the “quantum processor against state-of-the-art classical computers in the task of sampling the output of a pseudo-random quantum circuit. Random circuits are a suitable choice for benchmarking because they do not possess structure and therefore allow for limited guarantees of computational hardness. We design the circuits to entangle a set of quantum bits (qubits) by repeated application of single-qubit and two-qubit logical operations. Sampling the quantum circuit’s output produces a set of bitstrings, for example {0000101, 1011100, ...}. Owing to quantum interference, the probability distribution of the bitstrings resembles a speckled intensity pattern produced by light interference in laser scatter, such that some

bitstrings are much more likely to occur than others. Classically computing this probability distribution becomes exponentially more difficult as the number of qubits (width) and number of gate cycles (depth) grow.” The researchers uses the cross-entropy benchmarking, “which compares how often each bitstring is observed experimentally with its corresponding ideal probability computed via simulation on a classical computer”.

Let us see also Bouland, et al. (2019). “On the complexity and verification of quantum random circuit sampling.” Nature Physics. In the abstract, the authors remind us that quantum supremacy is the demonstration that the quantum system is capable of solving a quantum computation that is prohibitive for classical computers. “A leading near-term candidate is sampling from the probability distributions of randomly chosen quantum circuits, which we call random circuit sampling (RCS). ...”

Photonic companies

“6 Companies Working With Photonic Quantum Computing Technology in 2022”, by James Dargan, March 24, 2022, al link <https://thequantuminsider.com/2022/03/24/6-quantum-computing-companies-working-with-photonic-technology/> ([Archive](#)).

“Like many classifications, the term photonic quantum computing can be misleading – Xanadu’s approach to building quantum computers is very different to PsiQuantum for example. Nonetheless, we hope this gives a high level overview of the ecosystem.”

Here the fundamental question. What is the Photonic Quantum Computing?

“Photonic quantum computing is a type of quantum computing that uses photons as a **representation of qubits**. It consists of the ring that is used as a photons storage, along with the scattering unit. Determining whether the information they are carrying is 1 or a 0, is left to the direction of the photon travel, but it can also be both 1 and 0 as a product of the quirks of quantum superposition. The scattering unit is used as an encoder, directing the photons onto it as they will enter a cavity containing just a single atom. Interaction between the photon and atom will create a quantum state, such that any changes will affect both of them, without the restrain of the separation distance.”

The main advantage is that the computer works at room temperature.

Companies are:

1. Xanadu Quantum Technologies (Photonics Quantum Computing), Canada.
2. ORCA Computing, London-based.
3. PsiQuantum. Silicon Valley.
4. TundraSystems Global (Photonics Computing). Cardiff.
5. Quandela. Parigi.
6. QuiX Quantum. Enschede, the Netherlands.

Meanwhile

And IBM?

“IBM accelera sul calcolo quantistico: ecco la nuova Quantum Roadmap”. 14 May 2022, by Nicodemo Angi, [innovationpost](#) (archiviato [Archive](#)).

“Il processore IBM Condor, in arrivo l’anno prossimo, crea molte aspettative dato che le specifiche parlano di 1121 qubit (una quantità dichiarata essere la più alta al mondo), un valore che fa tesoro dell’esperienza dei suoi predecessori Eagle, con 127 qubit, e Osprey, che verrà presentato quest’anno, con 433 qubit.” Più dettagli in “IBM’s roadmap for scaling quantum technology”, <https://research.ibm.com/blog/ibm-quantum-roadmap> . L’IBM usa l’approccio del Superconducting quantum computing. Più dettagli su tale approccio in generale, si veda: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Superconducting_quantum_computing

Roadmap

The IBM roadmap (10 May 2022) is available at <https://research.ibm.com/blog/ibm-quantum-roadmap-2025> “Our goal is to build *quantum-centric supercomputers*. The quantum-centric supercomputer will incorporate quantum processors, classical processors, quantum communication networks, and classical networks, all working together to completely transform how we compute. In order to do so, we need to solve the challenge of scaling quantum processors, develop a runtime environment for providing quantum calculations with increased speed and quality, and introduce a serverless programming model to allow quantum and classical processors to work together frictionlessly.” ([Archive](#)).

Meanwhile, partners are sought to identify where the advantage is relevant. For example <https://www.ibm.com/case-studies/exxonmobil/> “As IBM’s quantum hardware scales rapidly – from small prototype systems to more promising larger devices – researchers are excited about the possibility to one day handle previously insoluble routing problems”. Stimulating the researchers in pursuing new tasks for quantum computing leads in turn to stimulating the development of new, more performing QPUs.

IBM Open Plan

<https://www.ibm.com/quantum> “Run your first quantum circuits for free on simulators and real quantum systems. Take advantage of the same feature-rich tools included in our Premium Plan. Use free cloud simulators (Statevector, MPS, Stabilizer). Access real 7-qubit and 5-qubit QPUs. Build circuits in IBM Quantum Composer, IBM Quantum Lab, and Qiskit. Execute workloads more efficiently in Qiskit Runtime”

<https://developer.ibm.com/series/programming-on-quantum-computers/>

<https://qiskit.org>

You need Python.

```
import qiskit
# Qiskit quantum circuits libraries
quantum_circuit = qiskit.circuit.library.QuantumVolume(5)
```

```
quantum_circuit.measure_all()
quantum_circuit.draw()
# prepare your circuit to run
from qiskit import IBMQ
# Get the API token in
# https://quantum-computing.ibm.com/
IBMQ.save_account("YOUR TOKEN")
provider = IBMQ.load_account()
backend = provider.get_backend('ibmq_quito')
optimized_circuit = qiskit.transpile(quantum_circuit, backend)
optimized_circuit.draw()
# run in real hardware
job = backend.run(optimized_circuit)
retrieved_job = backend.retrieve_job(job.job_id())
result = retrieved_job.result()
print(result.get_counts())
```

Circuit Library: Qiskit includes a comprehensive set of quantum gates and a variety of pre-built circuits so users at all levels can use Qiskit for research and application development. https://qiskit.org/documentation/apidoc/circuit_library.html

Transpiler: The transpiler translates Qiskit code into an optimized circuit using a backend's native gate set, allowing users to program for any quantum processor or processor architecture with minimal inputs.

From <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qiskit>

“Qiskit is an open-source software development kit (SDK) for working with quantum computers at the level of circuits, pulses, and algorithms. It provides tools for creating and manipulating quantum programs and running them on prototype quantum devices on IBM Quantum Experience or on simulators on a local computer. It follows the circuit model for universal quantum computation, and can be used for any quantum hardware (currently supports superconducting qubits and trapped ions) that follows this model.”

“Qiskit was founded by IBM Research to allow software development for their cloud quantum computing service, IBM Quantum Experience”. “A range of Jupyter notebooks are provided with examples of quantum computing being used.”

Let us see also “Quantum Algorithm Implementations for Beginners”, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03719.pdf>

Different languages and Q#

From <https://www.analyticsinsight.net/top-quantum-programming-languages-to-learn-in-2022-to-know/> “... quantum computers are capable of accelerating *machine learning processes*,

reducing thousands of years of learning to mere seconds. Quantum computers are based on quantum bits which have two possible values either a 0 or 1. And so quantum computers are used by the big tech companies such as IBM and Google. Quantum programming languages are the foundations to interpret ideas into instructions to be carried out by quantum computers. Here are the top quantum programming languages to know for 2022”.

Moreover, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_programming

And also, <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/quantum/overview-what-is-qsharp-and-qdk>

“What are the Q# programming language and the Quantum Development Kit?”

“Q# is Microsoft’s open-source programming language for developing and running quantum algorithms. It’s part of the Quantum Development Kit (QDK), an SDK which offers a set of tools that will assist you in the quantum software development process. The Quantum Development Kit provides Python packages to submit Qiskit and Cirq applications to the Azure Quantum service, the Q# programming language and libraries, the IQ# kernel for running Q# on Jupyter Notebook ... With the Quantum Development Kit, you can build programs that run on quantum hardware or formulate problems that run on quantum-inspired solvers in Azure Quantum, an open cloud ecosystem with a diverse set of quantum solutions and technologies”.

A Qiskit code of a Bell state

“Quantum Algorithm Implementations for Beginners”, 2022,

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1804.03719>

"Qiskit can be viewed as a Python library for quantum circuit execution. A basic Qiskit code has two parts, designing the circuit and running it. In the circuit design phase, we create an instance of QuantumCircuit with the required number of qubits and classical bits. Then gates and measurements are added to this blank circuit. Gates and measurements are implemented in Qiskit as methods of the QuantumCircuit class. After the circuit has been designed we need to choose a backend to run the circuit. This can be either be a simulator called the qasm_simulator or it can be one of IBM’s quantum processors. To use a quantum processor, you will need to load your IBM Q account information into Qiskit. Given in Fig. 5 is a simple code to construct the Bell state. This is the Qiskit version of the circuit in Fig. 1 with measurement added at the end to verify our results”.

Fig. 1. Quantum circuit for preparing a Bell state

```
#### Quantum circuit for preparing the Bell state #####
import numpy as np
from qiskit import QuantumCircuit, execute, Aer
# Create a Quantum Circuit with two qubits and 2 classical bits
```

```

circuit = QuantumCircuit(2,2)
# Add a H gate on qubit 0
circuit.h(0)
# Add a CX (CNOT) gate on control qubit 0 and target qubit 1
circuit.cx(0,1)
# Map the quantum measurement to the classical bits
circuit.measure([0,1],[0,1])
# Use Aer's qasm_simulator
simulator = Aer.get_backend('qasm_simulator')
# Execute the circuit on the qasm simulator
job = execute(circuit, simulator, shots=1000)
# Grab results from the job
result = job.result()
# Returns counts
counts = result.get_counts(circuit)
print("\nTotal count for 00 and 11 are:",counts)

```

Autors tell “we are running the circuit on the simulator for 1000 independent runs. The final output was {'11': 493, '00': 507}.”

Shor algorithm

“Quantum Algorithm Implementations for Beginners”, 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1804.03719>

“The integer factorization problem asks, given an integer N as an input, to find integers $1 < N_1, N_2 < N$ such that $N = N_1N_2$. This problem is hardest when N_1 and N_2 are primes with roughly the same number of bits. ... In practice, integers with 1000 or more bits are impossible to factor using known algorithms and classical hardware. The difficulty of factoring big numbers is the basis for the security of the RSA cryptosystem, one of the most widely used public-key cryptosystems. One of the most celebrated results in quantum computing is the development of a quantum algorithm for factorization that works in time polynomial in n . This algorithm, due to Peter Shor and known as Shor’s algorithm ... The first experimental implementation of this algorithm on a quantum computer was reported in 2001, when the number 15 was factored. The largest integer factored by Shor’s algorithm so far is 21” .

The article explains the algorithm and discusses a case. “We implemented the algorithm on `ibmqx4`, a 5-qubit quantum processor from the IBM Quantum Experience, in order to factor number 15 with $x = 11$. The circuit ... requires 12 qubits and 196 gates, too large to be implemented on `ibmqx4`. Hence, we used an optimized/compiled version from that uses 5 qubit and 11 gates.”

And further details in “Crittografia quantistica e algoritmo di Shor”, Tesi di Laurea in Crittografia di Michele Bandini, Università di Bologna. [Lauree-Unibo](#) (oppure [Archive](#)).

Countermeasures

At the beginning, we mentioned the end of NISQ era, when quantum computers will break the RSA encryption. And while the research moves towards the universal computer (quantum, of course), countermeasures are already being considered.

Nature, 8 July 2022. “These ‘quantum-proof’ algorithms could safeguard against future cyberattacks”. “US government agency endorses tools to keep the Internet safe from quantum computers capable of cracking conventional encryption keys.”, by Davide Castelvecchi. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-01879-6>

“Long before the age of quantum computing has even begun, the Internet is entering its post-quantum era. Many people are concerned about future quantum computers’ ability to break the cryptographic keys that modern life depends on ... Now the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has officially endorsed cryptographic technologies that are thought to be resistant to attack from quantum computers. These include an encryption algorithm ... called CRYSTALS-Kyber, along with three algorithms for use in digital signatures, which provide identity authentication. All of them rely on tried-and-tested mathematical techniques, including one called structured lattices.” Maybe, we are not so long before the age.

Honeywell and ions

Another player is Honeywell.

“Una nuova “vecchia” tecnologia nella corsa al computer quantistico”, di Elizabeth Gibney per Nature. Le Scienze, 30 novembre 2020, link [lescienze](#) .

“La multinazionale Honeywell ha annunciato di aver costruito il computer quantistico più potente al mondo ricorrendo alla “vecchia” tecnologia delle trappole ioniche, apparentemente superata da quella a superconduttori a cui si sono affidati Google e IBM. In realtà entrambi gli approcci hanno dei pro e dei contro e la sfida appare quanto mai aperta” [Gibney]

“Mentre nell’ultimo decennio il calcolo quantistico si è trasformato da esercizio accademico a grande business, i riflettori sono stati per lo più puntati su una tecnica: i piccoli anelli di materiale superconduttore adottati da giganti della tecnologia come IBM e Intel. L’anno scorso, i superconduttori hanno permesso ai ricercatori di Google di affermare di aver raggiunto la supremazia quantistica quando una loro macchina ha eseguito per la prima volta un calcolo al di là delle capacità pratiche dei migliori computer classici. Tuttavia un approccio diverso, basato su ioni intrappolati all’interno di campi elettrici, sta guadagnando terreno nella corsa a costruire un computer quantistico su scala commerciale. All’inizio di quest’anno [2020], la multinazionale statunitense Honeywell ha lanciato il suo primo computer quantistico che usa ioni intrappolati come base dei suoi quantum bit, o qubit, un progetto su cui lavorava in silenzio da oltre un decennio. Honeywell, la cui sede principale si trova a Charlotte, nella Carolina del Nord, è stata la prima grande azienda a intraprendere questa strada. A ottobre, sette mesi dopo il lancio, la compagnia ha presentato una versione migliorata della sua macchina, che ha in

programma di ampliare ulteriormente.” [Gibney]

"A new/old technology in the quantum computer race", by Elizabeth Gibney for Nature.

Honeywell has announced that it has built the most powerful quantum computer in the world using the “old” technology of the ion traps, apparently superseded by the superconducting technology of Google and IBM. In reality, both approaches have pros and cons and the challenge is open. While quantum computing has evolved from an academic exercise to business over the past decade, the spotlight has mostly been on one technique: the tiny rings of superconducting material adopted by tech giants like IBM and Intel. Last year, superconductors allowed Google researchers to claim they achieved quantum supremacy when one of their machines first performed a computation beyond the practical capabilities of the best classical computers. However, a different approach, based on ions trapped inside electric fields, is gaining ground in the race to build a quantum computer on a commercial scale. Earlier this year [2020], US Honeywell launched its first quantum computer that uses trapped ions as the basis of its qubits, a project Honeywell has been working on silently for over a decade. Honeywell, headquartered in Charlotte, North Carolina, was the first major company to take this route. In October, seven months after the launch, the company unveiled an improved version of its machine, which Honeywell plans to expand further.

This is what Gibney told.

From <https://www.honeywell.com/us/en/company/quantum/quantum-computer>

“The Honeywell System Model H1 is now available commercially. With high-fidelity, fully connected qubits and features like mid-circuit measurement and qubit reuse, our system enables quantum developers to design deeper, more meaningful circuits. This will accelerate organizations along the path to value. The System Model H1 is fully accessible over the cloud and compatible with a variety of software frameworks.”

From “Honeywell’s Ion Trap Quantum Computer Makes Big Leap”, by Samuel K. Moore, 3 MAR 2020, IEEE Spectrum, al link <https://spectrum.ieee.org/honeywells-ion-trap-quantum-computer-makes-big-leap>

"Honeywell’s computer uses ytterbium ions trapped in an electromagnetic field in a narrow groove built in a chip. The qubit relies on the spin state of the ion’s outermost electron and that of its nucleus. This can be manipulated by lasers and can hold its state—remain coherent—for a fairly long time compared to other types of qubits. Importantly, the qubits can be moved around on the trap chip, allowing them to interact in ways that produce quantum algorithms".

In IEEE Spectrum we can find that “Ion-trap quantum systems were first developed at the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology in the 1990s. In 2015, a veteran of that group Chris Monroe cofounded the ion-trap quantum computer company IonQ. IonQ has already fit 160 ytterbium-based qubits in its system and performed operations on 79 of them. The startup has published several tests of its system, but not a quantum volume measure.” (the article in IEEE Spectrum is of 2020. It is mentioning Wright, K., Beck, K.M., Debnath, S. et al. Benchmarking an 11-qubit quantum computer. Nat Commun 10, 5464 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13534-2>, about IonQ).

IonQ has its cloud too <https://ionq.com>

On trapped ions: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trapped_ion_quantum_computer

Engineering challenges

“Comment: Quantum computers are now just a set of engineering problems”, 06 Jul 2022. “Zak Romaszko, quantum chip lead at Universal Quantum, reveals the four fundamental engineering challenges to build a ‘useful’ quantum computer”

<https://www.theengineer.co.uk/content/opinion/comment-quantum-computers-are-now-just-a-set-of-engineering-problems/> ([Archive](#)).

In the quantum computing we have passed from “if” these machines will do something useful for society to “when”. However, to see the true potentialities of quantum computers, they have to be large. “To start to do anything useful with quantum computers, we need to reach the million-qubit scale.”

Qubit are incredibly fragile. “Even the slightest amount of noise can cause the underlying quantum information to break down, rendering the quantum computer useless. Controlling these qubits is the crux of the scalability issue and quantum computing hardware companies are faced with four key challenges to address”. [Zak Romaszko]

I) The first challenge for engineering is choosing the qubit. There are many types of qubits with pros and cons. Superconducting and trapped-ion systems are two of the main contenders. Superconducting qubits have the advantage of possessing basic components compatible with chip technology. “But as we scale further, trapped ion systems are starting to break through thanks to their less stringent refrigeration requirements, improved connectivity and long coherence times.” Qubits are single ions. “These trapped ions are naturally identical, well isolated from the environment and easily controllable”. With a specific architecture it is possible to move qubits to ‘talk’ to one another. [Zak Romaszko]

II) The second challenge is the temperature. To keep qubits stable, it takes a low temperature. For ions, cooling to 70 K (liquid nitrogen) is sufficient. [Zak Romaszko]

III) Then we have Engineering Challenge #3: Lose the lasers.

“To complete a quantum calculation, you need to run a quantum circuit. To achieve this, quantum gates manipulate qubits in the quantum computer. Again, there are many ways to achieve this. Trapped ion quantum computers generally use pairs of laser beams that must be aligned to the position of individual ions to execute quantum gates. This requires alignment accuracy to a fraction of the width of a human hair”. If we imagine we are at the scale of a million of qubits, it takes very little to make the computer stop. We need something simpler: “our quantum gates use global microwaves, effectively creating radio stations. Want to do a single qubit gate? Apply voltages to tune into that channel. Want to do a two-qubit gate? Apply a different set of voltages to tune into that channel. The best part of this gate scheme is that it doesn’t matter if we have 10 or 10 million qubits, the number of microwave sources is fixed allowing for dramatically simplified scaling.” [Zak Romaszko]

IV) Engineering Challenge #4: Fully integrated modules. “With a single wafer holding just a

few thousand qubits at most,” one has to consider the modularity problem to scale to one million of qubits. A proposal is to use photonic interconnections. Instead, Universal Quantum thinks of electric field links between adjacent quantum computing modules, where the experience of conventional chips could be capitalized. “In truth, the hard (and exciting) work in quantum computing is just beginning. As these machines start to scale and move out of the world’s laboratories, these engineering problems need to be resolved. While it’s a mammoth task, it’s not an impossible one – with a practical engineering approach”. [Zak Romaszko]

What are the problems a quantum computer can solve?

Hard work but exciting, according to Zak Romaszko, on machine and software. If successful, what are the problems a quantum computer can solve?

This is the question that “Computer quantistico: quali problemi può risolvere”, by Michele Nasi, is answering, https://www.ilsoftware.it/articoli.asp?tag=Computer-quantistico-quali-problemi-puo-risolvere_23117 , June 2021.

Quantum computers will not replace traditional computers: they are only intended to solve problems other than those that can be solved with classical computers. That is, any problem which is impossible to solve with classical computers will be impossible to solve even with quantum computers (that is, the so-called "undecidable problems").

To date, quantum computers represent an epochal revolution in computing. Thanks to the use of the principle of superimposition and entanglement, a quantum computer can be extremely more powerful than any system created up to now, managing to process parallelly many more calculations. As previously told, they can perform very specific tasks, but, by the very nature of the qubit, they are more prone to errors. Qubits are unstable so quantum computers must be carefully isolated from heat, vibrations and wandering atoms [Nasi]. You are probably thinking that if quantum computers solve just problems that can also be faced with traditional computers, and they are complicated to build, install, manage, and cost a lot, then why all this hype? Quantum computers have the potential to solve some problems better, faster and more efficiently than traditional computers. Orders of magnitude faster and more efficiently [Nasi].

In computer science, problems are classified according to how many computational steps it would take to solve them using the best known algorithms. This translates into an estimate of the time it will take a computer to solve each problem (computational complexity theory). The categories of problems are vast and often overlap but the three most used categories are P, NP, NP-complete. P problems are those that classical computers can solve efficiently in polynomial time. For NP problems the solutions are easy to verify but difficult to implement efficiently from an IT point of view. Every problem P is also an NP problem, so P is a subset of NP. NP-complete are the most difficult problems to solve [Nasi]. An example of these problems is the following: given a map and having three colors available, the problem is to color countries so that neighboring countries have different colors. On this problem see Steinberg, 1993, “The state of the three color problem”.

If we could design an efficient solution for an NP-complete problem then we could arrive at an efficient solution for all NP problems. To date, however, no known algorithm can solve an NP-complete problem efficiently. Quantum computers can solve NP-complete problems efficiently

since they offer the possibility of exponentially accelerating computation with respect to the classical approach [Nasi]. The article by Nasi continues with a discussion of cryptography and other issues.

Cosmic rays

Michele Nasi tells that “I qubit sono instabili quindi i computer quantistici devono essere accuratamente isolati dal calore, dalle vibrazioni e dagli atomi vaganti”. Atomi vaganti?

“Cosmic-ray threat to quantum computing greater than previously thought”, 28 Jul 2021, di Margaret Harris.

“Quantum computers may need a redesign to protect them from background radiation, say physicists. After earlier experiments showed that cosmic rays can severely disrupt the operation of superconducting quantum bits (qubits), an international team led by Robert McDermott of the University of Wisconsin-Madison, US, has now concluded that a leading error-correction method is unlikely to fix the problem on its own. Instead, McDermott and colleagues suggest that a combination of shielding and changes in qubit chip design may be required to keep errors at a manageable level.”

Here the experiment. “ McDermott and colleagues constructed a chip containing two pairs of qubits ... While performing quantum operations on this four-qubit system, the physicists observed numerous simultaneous jumps in the charge induced on the paired qubits. When they modelled these bursts of charge using a standard particle-physics toolkit, they determined that the correlated jumps stem from collisions between the chip and a mixture of gamma rays and cosmic rays.”

For error correction, nearest neighbour qubits are used.

“I computer quantistici hanno un nemico imbattibile (per ora): i raggi cosmici”, di Riccardo Lichene, https://www.corriere.it/tecnologia/21_dicembre_18/i-computer-quantistici-hanno-nemico-imbattibile-per-ora-raggi-cosmici-fd07b6e6-5e5c-11ec-bd4c-ff71c0b97a67.shtml

“La correzione degli errori si basa sulla configurazione di gruppi vicini di qubit in modo che agiscano come un'unica unità logica, proteggendo le informazioni quantistiche da eventuali errori che influiscono sui singoli qubit. Ma nel caso dei raggi cosmici, è probabile che tutti i qubit vicini subiscano errori contemporaneamente. Non esiste un modo realistico per mantenere la correzione degli errori funzionante in tali circostanze.”

“Let the computer itself be built of quantum mechanical elements which obey quantum mechanical laws.” (Feynman, 1982).

Hamiltonians

Quantum simulations (DQS)

Where is pursued the quantum advantage today? It is pursued by considering quantum problems and, as said by Feynman, having them run with quantum systems. And then we have Borealis that, in the Gaussian Boson Sampling, is winning the race. Borealis is made of photons, it is a lichtperlenspiel, and therefore wins when it comes to simulate a photonic problem. The same is true in the case of qubit computers, which simulate specific problems related to the "pseudo-random quantum circuit".

Now, let us see one aspect of the quantum gates acting on qubits, that we have not yet fully investigated, and it is the link to Hamiltonians.

From Georgescu, I. M., Ashhab, S., & Nori, F. (2014). Quantum simulation. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 86(1), 153. This is a fundamental article.

Since the 1980s it has been clear that simulating quantum mechanics is a major challenge. It takes a fast computer with large memory, because the physical system is described by parameters whose number grows exponentially as the system grows. The exponential explosion is inevitable, even if there are approximate methods for simulation, such as the Monte Carlo methods. "Therefore, the simulation of quantum systems in general remains a hard task even for today's supercomputers. A proposed solution to this problem came in the new type of computer envisaged by Richard Feynman (Feynman, 1982) — the quantum computer . . . Feynman realized at the time that a quantum machine would itself experience an exponential explosion, but with good consequences. The machine would have the capacity to contain an exponentially large amount of information without using an exponentially large amount of physical resources, thus making it a natural tool to perform quantum simulation." [Georgescu et al.] Feynman was not lavish with details. He just showed the way, with the sentence given above (1982).

"More than a decade later, it was shown (Lloyd, 1996) that a quantum computer – an array of quantum gates - can indeed act as a universal quantum simulator". The adjective "universal" is understood in the sense that the computer - the same computer - must be capable of facing many different problems. "Simpler quantum devices that mimic the evolution of other quantum systems in an analog manner could be used for this task (note that these are not universal simulators, but rather problem-specific machines). It is therefore expected that practical quantum simulation will become a reality well before full-fledged quantum computers." [Georgescu et al.] [And this explains why we have the race for quantum advantage, made with specific problems designed for a specific quantum machine].

In recent years, interest in quantum simulation has grown, and also the number of possible simulations in physics, chemistry and biology. In the condensed matter physics, we can simulate many difficult problems such as "quantum phase transitions, quantum magnetism or high-Tc superconductivity. Other potential application areas include high-energy physics, quantum chemistry, cosmology and nuclear physics".

The article by Georgescu et al., 2014, is also mentioning the "coherent manipulation of quantum systems", made by "atoms in optical lattices, trapped ions, nuclear spins, superconducting

circuits, or spins in semiconductors, practical applications of quantum simulation can be expected in the coming years.”

With the term “quantum simulator”, we mean a controllable quantum system used to simulate / emulate another quantum system. And the basic idea is in the following diagram.

Let the state of the system be $|\phi\rangle$, represented in the computational basis. For instance, let us simulate a particle with spin-1/2. The spin-up $|\uparrow\rangle$ state is represented by qubit $|1\rangle$, and spin-down $|\downarrow\rangle$ state as $|0\rangle$. Three spin $|\phi\rangle = |\uparrow\uparrow\downarrow\rangle$ state is represented as $|\psi\rangle = |110\rangle$.

To have $|\psi(t)\rangle = \exp\{-i\hbar Ht\} |\psi(0)\rangle$, we have to apply operation $U = \exp\{-i\hbar Ht\}$ to the initial state. U , the propagator we have seen at the beginning of our discussion in the Benioff's work, becomes a sequence of gates operating on one and two-qubits. “Such a circuit-based quantum simulation recreating the evolution $|\psi(0)\rangle \rightarrow |\psi(t)\rangle$ is usually referred to as digital quantum simulation (DQS)”.

“Since any unitary operation can be written in terms of universal quantum gates, it follows that in principle “anything” can be simulated, i.e. DQS is universal (Lloyd, 1996)”. However, it should be noted that not all the unitary operators can be simulated efficiently. But a local and finite Hamiltonian can be simulated. This is important, since one can map spin systems in such a local Hamiltonian.

The first step is to prepare the initial state. Figure 2 of the article by Georgescu et al. shows an example of quantum algorithm to prepare “a pure state of a molecular system with a given number m of electrons occupying a given number n of spin orbitals that exhibits polynomial scaling in m (regardless of n)” (see also Wang et al., 2009).

Let us consider operation U . We assume that the Hamiltonian can be written as the finite sum of terms coming from local interactions, as in Hubbard and Ising Hamiltonians.

$$H = \sum_{l=1}^M H_l, \text{ then we have: } U = \prod_l \exp(-i\hbar H_l t) \quad (\text{Trotter formula}).$$

The decomposition of U is a sequence of quantum gates. It is detailed in the Georgescu et al. article. The Trotter formula is originated from the Lie product (Sophus Lie, 1875), but it is known as the Trotter product (Hale Trotter), telling that, with $m \times m$ matrices A and B :

$$e^{A+B} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (e^{A/n} e^{B/n})^n$$

where e^A is the matrix exponential of A. The same for B. This formula is the analogue of the well-known formula:

$$e^{x+y} = e^x e^y$$

This formula also holds for commuting matrices. The Lie product also holds for non-commuting matrices. Lie's formula is related to the Baker – Campbell – Hausdorff formula. Lie's formula allows to separate kinetic and potential energy operators in the propagator, that is the Schrödinger evolution operator. In this case it is called Suzuki – Trotter decomposition (from Trotter and Masuo Suzuki).

Let's see what Georgescu et al. (2014) say about superconducting qubits.

In superconducting circuits, quantum information can be encoded with superconductivity in the direction of the loop current, for instance. “The circuit can be manipulated by applied voltages and currents (including both dc and microwave-frequency ac signals) and measured with high accuracy using integrated on-chip instruments. Although macroscopic in size, these circuits can display quantum behavior and they can be seen as “artificial atoms”. The advantage over real atoms is that superconducting circuits can be designed and constructed to tailor their characteristic frequencies, interaction strengths and so on. ... The fact that superconducting circuits can be produced in large numbers and “wired” together on a chip offers a rather straightforward way of realizing various lattice geometries”.

Spin qubit quantum computer (Loss–DiVincenzo quantum computer)

Let us talk about the Loss-DiVincenzo computer model. It is the simplest model where we find a Hamiltonian and the propagator U. It is a spin qubit quantum computer, based on controlling the spin of charge carriers (electrons and electron holes) in semiconductor devices. The model was proposed by Daniel Loss and David P. DiVincenzo in 1997. The proposal was to use the intrinsic spin-1/2 degree of freedom of individual electrons confined in quantum dots as qubits. https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Loss-DiVincenzo_quantum_computer

And here the Loss–DiVincenzo proposal.

On the right: “A double quantum dot. Each electron spin S_L or S_R define one quantum two-level system, or a spin qubit in the Loss-DiVincenzo proposal. A narrow gate between the two dots can modulate the coupling, allowing swap operations”.

Implementation of the two-qubit gate: The Loss–DiVincenzo quantum computer operates, basically, using inter-dot gate voltage for implementing swap operations and local magnetic fields (or any other local spin manipulation) for implementing the controlled NOT gate (CNOT gate).

The swap operation is achieved by applying a pulsed inter-dot gate voltage, so the exchange constant in the Heisenberg Hamiltonian becomes time-dependent:

$$H_s(t) = J(t) \mathbf{S}_L \cdot \mathbf{S}_R$$

And we have conditions concerning energy, impulse time and decoherence. From the pulsed Hamiltonian follows the time evolution operator:

$$U_s(t) = T \exp \left\{ -i \int_0^t dt' H_s(t') \right\} ,$$

where we find the time-ordering symbol. We can choose the length of the pulse so that U_s becomes the swap operator U_{sw} .

A Hamiltonian

Quantum Hamiltonian H is an operator. In the time-independent Schrödinger equation, it is associated to a set of eigenstates:

$$H|j\rangle = \hbar \omega_j |j\rangle$$

which are forming an orthogonal basis. ω_j are eigenvalues of the Hamiltonian. The dimension of these eigenvalues is energy, therefore they are real and operator H is hermitian. Any state of the system is given by the linear combination:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_j \alpha_j |j\rangle$$

The evolution is given by the Schrödinger equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} |\psi\rangle = -\frac{i}{\hbar} H |\psi\rangle$$

$$|\psi\rangle = U(t) |\psi(0)\rangle , \text{ where } U(t) = \exp(-iHt/\hbar) .$$

U is the propagator. If the Hamiltonian is time-dependent, we can think of it as constant in time intervals, and then it corresponds to a series of Hamiltonian pieces which are applied in a time sequence, U_1 , U_2 and so on. Therefore: $|\psi\rangle \rightarrow U_3 U_2 U_1 |\psi\rangle$, with three propagators, for instance. Each propagator has a specific Hamiltonian.

The Pauli matrices, that we have seen at the beginning, are Hermitian. They are the natural basis on which to build the density matrices. In this way, it is possible to transform the Hamiltonian into a weighted sum of Pauli matrices. The Pauli matrices are therefore perfect for describing

the single qubit interaction. And consequently, the logic gates become operators with a corresponding Hamiltonian.

Let's see a simple case, from “Physics of Quantum Computation”, di Javier Cerrillo, Sommersemester 2016, Technische Universität Berlin. [Tu-berlin-de](#) . The problem is to find state $|x\rangle$. Let us postulate a system that is able to implement the Hamiltonian:

$$H = |x\rangle\langle x| + |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$$

where $|\psi\rangle$ is a starting state and $|x\rangle$ is a solution of the search.

A decomposition $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|x\rangle + \beta|y\rangle$, where $\langle x|y\rangle = 0$, is possible so that the Hamiltonian in the basis $\{|x\rangle, |y\rangle\}$ takes now the form

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \alpha^2 & \alpha\beta \\ \alpha\beta & \beta^2 \end{pmatrix} = I + \alpha(\beta X + \alpha Z) ,$$

since $\alpha^2 + \beta^2 = 1$. X, Y, Z are the Pauli matrices, and I the identity. Thus, evolution of the initial state under this Hamiltonian takes the form

$$\exp(-iHt)|\psi\rangle = e^{-it} [\cos(\alpha t)|\psi\rangle - i\sin(\alpha t)(\beta X + \alpha Z)|\psi\rangle]$$

where time is dimensionless, or the energy scale of the Hamiltonian is assumed 1. One can show that:

$$(\beta X + \alpha Z)|\psi\rangle = |x\rangle$$

and therefore the state evolves following $|x(t)\rangle = \cos(\alpha t)|x(t)\rangle - i\sin(\alpha t)|x(t)\rangle$, by choosing the uniform superposition state as the initial state.

Molecular and Material Science

A part of the article by Bauer, B., Bravyi, S., Motta, M., & Chan, G. K. L. (2020). “Quantum algorithms for quantum chemistry and quantum materials science”. *Chemical Reviews*, 120(22), 12685-12717, is devoted to the applications of quantum calculus.

“We now turn to survey a representative, but certainly nonexhaustive, set of scientific problems that could be interesting for quantum simulation. We group these roughly into a few areas: quantum chemistry, the problem of determining the low-lying states of electrons in molecules; quantum molecular spectroscopy, concerned with stationary states of the nuclei vibrating and rotating in molecules; chemical quantum dynamics, that studies the nonequilibrium electronic and nuclear motion of molecules associated with reactions and external fields; correlated electronic structure in materials, a close cousin of quantum chemistry in the materials domain, but with several important differences in practice and in emphasis; and dynamical quantum effects in materials, concerned with driven and out-of equilibrium material systems.”

Variational Quantum Eigensolver

From the article that we have previously mentioned, we understand that a series of quantum simulations is devoted to chemistry, and this is also told by recent news.

APS News, July/August 2022 (Volume 31, number 7), “Searching for New Molecules with Quantum Computers. Could the budding technology see a breakthrough application in chemistry?” di Sophia Chen, [APSNews](#)

“At this year’s APS March Meeting in Chicago, researchers from both academia and industry—including Google, IBM, and smaller startups—dove into quantum computing’s applications in chemistry.” Researchers are very interested in quantum simulations for applications in chemistry, because any simulation with binary machines, which contains more than 20 electrons, becomes impossible.

“Quantum computing could change this. Molecules obey quantum mechanical equations, like qubits do (a qubit is the quantum counterpart to a 1-or-0 “bit” in normal computing). For example, in some algorithms, a qubit corresponds to a single electron orbital. As a result, researchers think it will be easier to simulate complex molecules on quantum computers, as they should be less bogged down with each added electron compared to classical computers. For instance, if researchers can simulate how electrons move around a molecule, they’ll gain insight into its properties, like its electrical conductivity or its likelihood of bonding with another molecule.” This is answering Richard Feynman's suggestion. But we have NISQ machines, and “researchers can test their molecular simulations only on the imperfect quantum computers we have today”.

“Challenges with NISQ computers abound. Their qubits hold on to information for limited time, which constrains the number of computations they can do in a row. It’s also difficult to make qubits interact precisely, so researchers try to avoid operations involving qubits that are far apart, says Robert Parrish of the quantum computing startup QC Ware. These challenges mean that a central part of developing algorithms is tailoring them to NISQ-era hardware, with all its limits—and researchers have gotten creative. Many use an algorithm developed in 2013 called the **Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE)** as a framework to build their own algorithms. In VQE, a quantum computer and a classical computer work together to calculate the ground state energy of a molecule.” VQE is used both in quantum and classical computers.

In arXiv we can find “VQE Method: A Short Survey and Recent Developments”, di Dmitry A. Fedorov, Bo Peng, Niranjana Govind, Yuri Alexeev.

The method VQE uses a hybrid approach to find eigenvalues and eigenvectors of Hamiltonians. “VQE has been proposed as an alternative to fully quantum algorithms such as quantum phase estimation because fully quantum algorithms require quantum hardware that will not be accessible in the near future. VQE has been successfully applied to solve the electronic Schrödinger equation for a variety of small molecules. However, the scalability of this method is limited by two factors: the complexity of the quantum circuits and the complexity of the classical optimization problem. Both of these factors are affected by choice of the variational ansatz used to represent the trial wave function”.

The research on this issue is very active (<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2103.08505>).

The variational calculus starts from an ansatz. “A trial wave function or ansatz is constructed with adjustable parameters, followed by the design of a quantum circuit capable of realizing this ansatz. The ansatz parameters are then variationally adjusted until the expectation value of the electronic Hamiltonian” (arXiv).

Let us consider the expression:

$$E \leq \frac{\langle \psi(\vec{\theta}) | \hat{H}_{el} | \psi(\vec{\theta}) \rangle}{\langle \psi(\vec{\theta}) | \psi(\vec{\theta}) \rangle}$$

Here we find the trial wave function, depending on a vector containing the variational parameters. E is the energy of the ground state of the electronic Hamiltonian (the lowest value is the lowest eigenvalue of the Hamiltonian). In the second quantization, the Hamiltonian is written as:

$$H_{el} = \sum_{p,q} h_{pq} a_p^\dagger a_q + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{pqrs} h_{pqrs} a_p^\dagger a_q^\dagger a_r a_s$$

where we can find annihilation and creation operators among orbitals. The first term describes the single electron, the second regards two electrons. Coefficients h_{pq}, h_{pqrs} are evaluated by means of a classical computer.

To use a quantum computer, one must pass from the Hamiltonian with indistinguishable fermions to a Hamiltonian with (distinguishable) qubits.

The qubit Hamiltonian becomes:

$$H = \sum_j \alpha_j P_j = \sum_j \alpha_j \prod_i \sigma_i^j$$

where α_j are real scalar coefficients depending on h_{pq}, h_{pqrs} . P_j are strings of Pauli matrices created by products of matrices σ_i^j , where i denotes the qubit on which the Pauli operator is acting on and j is the term in the Hamiltonian.

After having chosen the wave function, the quantum computer is ready to calculate the energy:

$$E(\vec{\theta}) = \sum_j^N \alpha_j \langle \psi(\vec{\theta}) | \prod_i \sigma_i^j | \psi(\vec{\theta}) \rangle$$

N is the number of terms in the Hamiltonian. According to the used basis, we can have M^4 terms, if M is the number of the basis functions.

The trial wave function must then be prepared, starting from a given state. ArXiv illustrates the method in the case of an exponential operator, and the article continues with details of further ansatzs.

Let us consider a specific example to show the method.

The example is from Joshua J. Goings <https://joshuagoings.com/2020/08/20/VQE/> , many thanks a lot. <https://web.archive.org/web/20220817102545/https://joshuagoings.com/2020/08/20/VQE/> . The code is also given.

“The problem we want to tackle is to implement the VQE to compute the energy of molecular hydrogen in a minimal basis. We will base this implementation off the really neat paper O’Malley, Peter JJ, et al. “Scalable quantum simulation of molecular energies.” Physical Review X 6.3 (2016): 031007. O’Malley and coworkers have runned a VQE approach on a real quantum computer. And here the steps of the method as given by Joshua Goings:

- 1) Put the Hamiltonian in the computational (qubit) basis.
- 2) Obtain a variational ansatz to parameterize the wave function.
- 3) Represent this ansatz as a quantum circuit.
- 4) Given this circuit, measure the expectation value of Hamiltonian (energy).
- 5) Vary the circuit parameters until the energy is minimized.

The first step is to represent the Hamiltonian of fermions by means of qubits.

In the article by O’Malley et al. it is used “the BK[Bravyi-Kitaev]-transformed Hamiltonian and exploiting some of the symmetry in the H₂ molecule, the Hamiltonian can be represented by only two qubits. (Nice) - The Hamiltonian has five components". With the Pauli basis σ_i^j , named X,Y,Z , where the index is specifying the qubit:

$$\hat{H}_{BK} = g_0 \mathbf{I} + g_1 Z_0 + g_2 Z_1 + g_3 Z_0 Z_1 + g_4 Y_0 Y_1 + g_5 X_0 X_1$$

Coefficients are coming from classical calculations and are given by O’Malley et al.

From O’Malley et al. “The central problem of quantum chemistry is to compute the lowest energy eigenvalue of the molecular electronic structure Hamiltonian. The eigenstates of this Hamiltonian determine almost all of the properties of interest in a molecule or material, and as the gap between the ground and first electronically excited state is often much larger than the thermal energy at room temperature, the ground state is of particular interest.” [O’Malley et al.]. We have nuclear charges Z_i and electrons:

$$H = -\sum_i \frac{\nabla_{R_i}^2}{2M_i} - \sum_i \frac{\nabla_{r_i}^2}{2} - \sum_{i,j} \frac{Z_i}{|R_i - r_j|} + \sum_{i,j>i} \frac{Z_i Z_j}{|R_i - R_j|} + \sum_{i,j>i} \frac{1}{|r_i - r_j|}$$

Positions, masses and charges of nuclei are R_i, M_i, Z_i and positions of electrons is r_i .

The Hamiltonian is given in hartree energy unit. And therefore we do not find in the Hamiltonian the mass and charge of electron. https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Energia_di_Hartree O’Malley et al. tell that “this form of the Hamiltonian and its real-space discretization are often referred to as the first quantized formulation of quantum chemistry. Several approaches have

been developed for treating this form of the problem on a quantum computer; however, the focus of this [O'Malley] work is the second quantized formulation. To reach the second quantized formulation, one typically first approximates the nuclei as fixed classical point charges under the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, chooses a basis ϕ_i in which to represent the wave function, and enforces antisymmetry with the fermion creation and annihilation operators a_i^+, a_j to give:

$$H_{el} = \sum_{p,q} h_{pq} a_p^+ a_q + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{pqrs} h_{pqrs} a_p^+ a_q^+ a_r a_s$$

where:

$$h_{pq} = \int dx \phi_p^*(x) \left(\frac{\nabla_r^2}{2} - \sum_i \frac{Z_i}{|R_i - r|} \right) \phi_q(x)$$

$$h_{pqrs} = \int dx_1 dx_2 \frac{\phi_p^*(x_1) \phi_q^*(x_2) \phi_s(x_1) \phi_r(x_2)}{|r_1 - r_2|}$$

Coordinates x, x_1, x_2 represent the spatial and spin coordinates: $x_i = (r_i, s_i)$.

Then we have to pass from creation and annihilation operators to Pauli matrices. Details are given in Seeley, J. T., Richard, M. J., & Love, P. J. (2012). The Bravyi-Kitaev transformation for quantum computation of electronic structure. *The Journal of chemical physics*, 137(22), 224109. In the Bravyi-Kitaev form, “the spin Hamiltonian for molecular hydrogen in the minimal (STO-6G) basis,” [O'Malley et al], it is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} H = & f_0 \mathbb{1} + f_1 Z_0 + f_2 Z_1 + f_3 Z_2 + f_1 Z_0 Z_1 \\ & + f_4 Z_0 Z_2 + f_5 Z_1 Z_3 + f_6 \mathbf{X}_0 Z_1 \mathbf{X}_2 + f_6 \mathbf{Y}_0 Z_1 \mathbf{Y}_2 \\ & + f_7 Z_0 Z_1 Z_2 + f_4 Z_0 Z_2 Z_3 + f_3 Z_1 Z_2 Z_3 \\ & + f_6 \mathbf{X}_0 Z_1 \mathbf{X}_2 Z_3 + f_6 \mathbf{Y}_0 Z_1 \mathbf{Y}_2 Z_3 + f_7 Z_0 Z_1 Z_2 Z_3, \end{aligned}$$

Coefficients are depending on the “fixed bond length of the molecule. We notice that this Hamiltonian acts off diagonally on only two qubits (the ones having tensor factors of 0 and 2), those set in bold in Equation. Because we start our simulations in the Hartree-Fock state, a classical basis state, we see that the Hamiltonian stabilizes qubits 1 and 3 so that they are never flipped throughout the simulation. We can use this symmetry to scalably reduce the Hamiltonian of interest to the following effective Hamiltonian which acts only on two qubits:” [O'Malley et al.]

$$\hat{H}_{BK} = g_0 \mathbf{I} + g_1 Z_0 + g_2 Z_1 + g_3 Z_0 Z_1 + g_4 Y_0 Y_1 + g_5 X_0 X_1 \quad (*)$$

The Hamiltonian acts only on two qubits. Let us start from $|01\rangle$ state. “To obtain this from $|00\rangle$, we just need to act on the zeroth qubit with the Pauli X operator. This is the first step in the quantum circuit ... from the O’Malley paper.” [Joshua J. Goings] “In the O’Malley paper, they utilize the Unitary Coupled Cluster (UCC) ansatz, which in this case depends only on a single parameter θ .” [Joshua J. Goings]

$$U(\theta) = \exp(-i\theta X_0 Y_1)$$

Then: $|\psi(\theta)\rangle = \exp(-i\theta X_0 Y_1)|01\rangle$. We find the product of Pauli-X acting on qubit 0 and Pauli-Y on qubit 1. It is also necessary to represent $U(\theta)$ as a series of quantum gates. Let us remember:

$$\langle \psi | U^\dagger(\theta) \hat{H}_{mol} U(\theta) | \psi \rangle = \langle \psi' | \hat{H}_{mol} | \psi' \rangle$$

with normalized wave functions and U unitary operators. We can calculate energy:

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \langle \psi' | g_0 \mathbf{I} + g_1 Z_0 + g_2 Z_1 + g_3 Z_0 Z_1 + g_4 Y_0 Y_1 + g_5 X_0 X_1 | \psi' \rangle \\ &= g_0 \langle \mathbf{I} \rangle + g_1 \langle Z_0 \rangle + g_2 \langle Z_1 \rangle + g_3 \langle Z_0 Z_1 \rangle + g_4 \langle Y_0 Y_1 \rangle + g_5 \langle X_0 X_1 \rangle \\ &= \sum_i g_i \langle \hat{O}_i \rangle \end{aligned}$$

By varying parameter θ , it is possible to find the ground energy.

“VQE solves for the parameter vector θ with a classical optimization routine. One first prepares an initial ansatz and then estimates the ansatz energy by measuring the expectation values of each term in Eq.(*) and summing these values together”. [O’Malley et al.]

Remarkable, in the article by O’Malley et al., are the two figures that schematically represent, in a very clear manner, the calculation made by hardware and software. Figure 1 concerns the implementation of the VQE scheme on the quantum computer. And here what the caption says: “Hardware and software schematic of the variational quantum eigensolver. (Hardware) micrograph shows two Xmon transmon qubits and **microwave pulse sequences** to perform single-qubit rotations (thick lines), **dc pulses** for two-qubit entangling gates (dashed lines), and microwave spectroscopy tones for qubit measurements (thin lines). (Software) quantum circuit diagram shows preparation of the Hartree-Fock state, followed by application of the unitary coupled cluster ansatz in Eq. (3) and efficient partial tomography (R_t) to measure the expectation values in Eq. (1). Finally, the total energy is computed according to Eq. (4) and provided to a classical optimizer which suggests new parameters”.

Equation (1) is the (*) given above. Eq. (3) is ansatz $|\psi(\theta)\rangle = \exp(-i\theta X_0 Y_1)|01\rangle$. Eq. (4) is the calculus of energy. In the caption we find the “partial tomography”, and in the article it is told that “The expectation values we use to calculate the energy of the prepared state are measured with partial tomography; for example, $X_1 X_0$ is measured by applying $Y_{\pi/2}$ gates to each qubit prior to measurement”.

From Hamiltonian (physical system) to Hamiltonian (qubit system)

A many-body system with fermions is used to describe the electronic properties of molecules and materials. The Hamiltonian is:

$$H = -\sum_i \frac{\nabla_{R_i}^2}{2M_i} - \sum_i \frac{\nabla_{r_i}^2}{2} - \sum_{i,j} \frac{Z_i}{|R_i - r_j|} + \sum_{i,j>i} \frac{Z_i Z_j}{|R_i - R_j|} + \sum_{i,j>i} \frac{1}{|r_i - r_j|}$$

In the second quantization:

$$H_{el} = \sum_{p,q} h_{pq} a_p^\dagger a_q + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{pqrs} h_{pqrs} a_p^\dagger a_q^\dagger a_r a_s$$

as we have previously seen. Using the Jordan–Wigner transformation or that by Bravyi–Kitaev, the electronic Hamiltonian is converted iso-spectrally to a qubit form [Ryabinkin et al., 2018].

This Hamiltonian is:

$$\hat{H} = \sum_l C_l \hat{P}_l$$

where \hat{P}_l “are Pauli “words”, products of Pauli operators of different qubits” [Ryabinkin et al., 2018].

Pauli strings

The “words” are also known as Pauli strings.

See <https://mitiq.readthedocs.io/en/stable/guide/observables.html> or the “Variational Algorithms”, by Xavier Bonet-Monroig, Casper Gyurik and Thomas O’Brien, February 26, 2020

<https://liacs.leidenuniv.nl/~dunjkov/aQa/aQa-Lecture-3-vqe1.pdf> (Archive)

“An incredibly useful set of operators in quantum computing are the Pauli matrices $P = \{I, X, Y, Z\}$, or more generally the Pauli basis, $P = \{I, X, Y, Z\}^{\otimes N}$. The Pauli basis contains all possible tensor products of the Pauli matrices acting on N-qubits, for a total of 4^N elements. Elements of the Pauli basis are typically written without explicit tensor products - e.g. $ZZ \equiv Z \otimes Z$. Moreover, instead of writing a lot of I’s, we often drop them, and instead index operators with which qubits they act on - e.g.

$$Z_1 X_3 \equiv ZIX \equiv Z \otimes I \otimes X.$$

The Pauli matrices are both unitary and hermitian. Given a Pauli operator \hat{P} , we have:”

$$\hat{P}^+ \hat{P} = I, \quad \hat{P} = \hat{P}^+, \quad \hat{P}^2 = I$$

Eigenvalues are $s \pm 1$. Moreover, $Tr[\hat{P}_i \hat{P}_j] = 2^N \delta_{ij}$. Being hermitian, we can write the exponential:

$$U(\hat{P}) = e^{-i\theta \hat{P}}$$

Then:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{\hat{P}}(\theta) &= e^{-i\theta \hat{P}} = \sum_k \frac{(-i\theta \hat{P})^k}{k!} = \sum_k \frac{(-i\theta \hat{P})^{2k}}{(2k)!} + \sum_k \frac{(-i\theta \hat{P})^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!} \\ &= \sum_k \frac{(-i)^{2k} \theta^{2k} \hat{P}^{2k}}{(2k)!} + \sum_k \frac{(-i)^{2k+1} \theta^{2k+1} \hat{P}^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!} \\ &= \sum_k \frac{(-1)^k \theta^{2k}}{(2k)!} I + (-i) \sum_k \frac{\theta^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!} \hat{P} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore:

$$U_{\hat{P}}(\theta) = \cos(\theta) I - i \sin(\theta) \hat{P}.$$

“Note here that critically, although \hat{P} when acting as a unitary operator by itself does not generate any entanglement between qubits, $U_{\hat{P}}(\theta)$ is an entangling gate! Indeed, as we will cover in the next lecture, every possible operation on a quantum computer may be approximated by a series of $U_{\hat{P}_i}(\theta)$ for different operators \hat{P}_i . Physically, the expectation value of a Pauli operator acting on a single qubit can be thought of as the splitting of the two eigenstates of that qubit for a period of time, and typically on NISQ devices some gate similar to $e^{i\theta Z_i}$ may be achieved.”

In Qiskit see also: https://qiskit.org/documentation/stubs/qiskit.quantum_info.Pauli.html

Phase Estimation Algorithm (Trotterization)

In their article, O’Malley et al. give also an “experimental demonstration of the original quantum algorithm for chemistry, [the Phase Estimation] Similar to VQE, the first step of this algorithm is to prepare the system register in a state having good overlap with the ground state

of the Hamiltonian H ." This approach is known as "Phase Estimation Algorithm". [see also Aspuru-Guzik, A., Dutoi, A. D., Love, P. J., & Head-Gordon, M. (2005). Simulated quantum computation of molecular energies. *Science*, 309(5741), 1704-1707. <https://arxiv.org/ftp/quant-ph/papers/0604/0604193.pdf>].

In the article published in the *Physical Review X*, O'Malley et al. "begin with the Hartree-Fock state $|\phi\rangle$. We then evolve this state under H using a Trotterized approximation to the time-evolution operator." The execution of this unitary operation is controlled by an ancilla initialized in the superposition state $(|0\rangle+|1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$. The time-evolution operator is approximated by Trotterization as:

$$e^{-iHt} = e^{-it \sum_y g_y H_y} \approx U_{Trot}(t) \equiv \left(\prod_y e^{-ig_y H_y t/\rho} \right)^\rho$$

with local Hamiltonians:

$$\hat{H}_{BK} = g_0 \mathbf{I} + g_1 Z_0 + g_2 Z_1 + g_3 Z_0 Z_1 + g_4 Y_0 Y_1 + g_5 X_0 X_1$$

The application of the propagator is inducing a phase on the system register, and then:

$$e^{-iHt}|\phi\rangle = \left(\sum_n e^{-iE_n t} |n\rangle \langle n| \right) |\phi\rangle = \sum_n a_n e^{-iE_n t} |n\rangle,$$

where we find eigenstates $|n\rangle$, eigenvalues E_n and product $a_n = \langle n|\phi\rangle$.

"By controlling this evolution on the ancilla superposition state, one entangles the system register with the ancilla. Accordingly, by measuring the phase between the $|0\rangle$ state and $|1\rangle$ state of the ancilla, one measures the phase $E_n t$ and collapses the system register to the state $|n\rangle$ with probability a_n^2 ". [O'Malley et al.]

The Figure 4 of O'Malley et al. article shows hardware and software also for the PEA-Trotter approach. Now, we have three qubits (two plus the ancilla). The captions tells: "Hardware and software schematic of the Trotterized phase estimation algorithm. (Hardware) micrograph shows three Xmon transmon qubits and microwave pulse sequences, including (i) the variable amplitude CZ_ϕ ... and (ii) dynamical decoupling pulses not shown in logical circuit. (Software) state preparation includes putting the ancilla in a superposition state and compensating for previously measured bits of the phase using the gate Z_{ϕ_k} . The bulk of the circuit is the evolution of the system under a Trotterized Hamiltonian controlled by the ancilla. Bit j_k is determined by a majority vote of the ancilla state over 1000 repetitions".

Both VQE and PEA-Trotter algorithms have been implemented by O'Malley et al. "with a superconducting quantum system based on the Xmon, a variant of the planar transmon qubit, in

a dilution refrigerator with a base temperature of 20 mK. Each qubit consists of a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID), which provides a tunable nonlinear inductance, and a large X-shaped capacitor”.

Unitary coupled cluster (UCC) e Qubit coupled cluster (QCC)

Let us consider again VQE.

Ryabinkin, I. G., Yen, T. C., Genin, S. N., & Izmaylov, A. F. (2018). Qubit coupled cluster method: a systematic approach to quantum chemistry on a quantum computer. *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 14(12), 6317-6326.

“A unitary coupled cluster (UCC) form for the wave function in the variational quantum eigensolver has been suggested as a systematic way to go beyond the mean-field approximation and include electron correlation in solving quantum chemistry problems on a quantum computer.” Due to the problems of the method mentioned by the authors, not all the “quantum computing architectures” are able to make the calculus. To address the problems, the authors “introduce a qubit coupled cluster (QCC) method that starts directly in the qubit space and uses energy response estimates for ranking the importance of individual entanglers for the variational energy minimization”.

Equation (6) in the article is minimizing the energy through trial VQE. The parametrization of unitary operators from fermions to qubits is made by means of the UCC (unitary coupled cluster (UCC)) fermionic ansatz.

$$\hat{U}_{CC} = \exp(\hat{T} - \hat{T}^+)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{T} = \hat{T}_1 + \hat{T}_2 + \dots + \hat{T}_{N_e}, \quad \hat{T}_1 = \sum_{ia} t_i^a \hat{a}_a^+ \hat{a}_i, \quad \hat{T}_2 = \sum_{ijab} t_{ij}^{ab} \hat{a}_a^+ \hat{a}_b^+ \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_i, \dots$$

And we have already mentioned these operators. Authors stress that “at any rank greater than 1 the UCC ansatz is exponentially hard for a classical computer due to nontruncation of the Baker–Campbell–Hausdorff series.”

The Qubit Coupled Cluster method provides the Pauli strings, as we have seen before. The article is also giving some numerical examples. “We illustrate our developments by computing the ground-state potential energy curves for the H₂ and LiH molecules and a symmetric O–H stretching curve for the H₂O molecule within the QMF [qubit mean-field] and QCC approaches. H₂ and LiH were used previously to illustrate performance of quantum computing techniques, while the H₂O example is particularly interesting because it is a strong-correlation problem with more than one correlated pair of electrons, for which the traditional coupled cluster singles and doubles (CCSD) approach is known to fail giving energy below the exact value at large O–H distances.”

Hückel molecular orbitals in the IBM-Kawasaki

Yoshida, R., Lötstedt, E., & Yamanouchi, K. (2022). Quantum computing of Hückel molecular orbitals of π -electron systems. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 156(18), 184117.

The aim of authors is that of demonstrating an applicability of quantum computing to solve fundamental electronic structure problems of molecules. Researchers “describe the Hückel Hamiltonian matrix in terms of quantum gates and obtain the orbital energies of fundamental π -electron molecules (C_2H_4 , C_3H_4 , C_4H_4 , C_4H_6 , and C_6H_6) using a superconducting-qubit-type quantum computer (*ibm_kawasaki*) with a post-selection error mitigation method. We [the authors] show that the orbital energies are obtained with sufficiently high accuracy and small uncertainties and that characteristic features of the electronic structure of the π -electron molecules can be extracted by quantum computing in a straightforward manner”.

News, 27 July 2021, “Building Japan’s quantum future with IBM Quantum System One”, <https://research.ibm.com/blog/japan-quantum-system-one>

“Starting today, Japan’s best and brightest researchers now have special access to one the world’s most-powerful quantum computers: IBM Quantum System One in Kawasaki City. ... After launching a hub at Keio University in 2018, the University of Tokyo and IBM kicked off the Japan-IBM Quantum Partnership in 2019 to advance quantum computing across the country. As part of this partnership, researchers in Japan received an IBM Quantum System One, now installed in IBM’s facility at the Kawasaki Business Incubation Center, Kawasaki City. The aim of this partnership is to engage universities in Japan to accelerate quantum computing research and education, work with industry to advance research in practical quantum computing applications, and to research quantum computing hardware components”.

Let us consider again the orbitals of molecules.

“Describing the electronic structure of molecules composed of many electrons with high accuracy is one of the central themes in modern quantum chemistry. Thanks to the molecular orbital (MO) program packages, ... developed by the pioneering attempts made by quantum chemists in the past 50 years and to the emergence of the supercomputer technologies, researchers are able to calculate electronic structures of molecules and molecular complexes by including a large configuration-interaction space.” Even a small molecule, benzene for instance, has 42 electrons and the number of configurations is greater than 10^{20} ; also in the case “we assume a minimal basis set consisting of 72 spin-orbitals (one 1s orbital for H and 1s, 2s, and 2p orbitals for C)”, the number of configuration “is five orders of magnitude larger than the total memory size (5×10^{15} bytes) of Fugaku, the fastest supercomputer in the world.” [Yoshida et al.]

If we have quantum computers, possessing N qubits, we can describe 2^N superposition states. “In the Jordan–Wigner representation, the occupation numbers of N spin-orbitals are stored by N qubits”. Using $N = 65$ qubit IBM, “we can represent $N = 65$ active orbitals, corresponding to a total of about 2×10^{17} electron configurations in the case of benzene. This means that the MO calculation of benzene with an almost full-CI (configuration interaction) configuration space becomes, in principle, possible. If the number of qubits available on a quantum computer reaches 1,000, even an electronic structure of biomolecules can be calculated with a full-CI level” [Yoshida et al.]. But we are in the NISQ era and then some qubits are used for error correction.

In the study published in the Journal of Chemical Physics, the authors focused “on the electronic structure of small organic compounds having π -bonding and perform the quantum

computing by the Hückel molecular orbital (HMO) method, which has been known as a simple and fundamental MO method to describe the characteristic features of π -bonding systems. As the first step of the demonstration, we convert the Hückel Hamiltonian into quantum gates and describe orbital energies using quantum circuits, and then, we run the program constructed by the quantum circuits on a real device. We show that the orbital energy of HMOs can be obtained with sufficiently high accuracy for the fundamental π -bonding molecular species” previously mentioned, after the error mitigation. [Yoshida et al.] “It is true that the HMO method gives only semi-quantitative results, but the implementation of the quantum computing into the HMO method demonstrated in the present study will pave a way for the quantum computing of the electronic states of large π -bonding systems, such as linear and circular polyenes, fullerenes, carbon nanotubes, graphene, and graphite.” [Yoshida et al.]

Jordan-Wigner transformation

Sennane, W., Piquemal, J. P., & Rančić, M. J. (2022). “Calculating the ground state energy of benzene under spatial deformations with noisy quantum computing.” arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.05275. “In this manuscript, [the authors] calculate the ground state energy of benzene under spatial deformations by using a state-of-the-art quantum computing methodology - the variational quantum eigensolver (VQE).”

Authors are discussing the Jordan-Wigner transformation.

“Quantum computers are composed out of qubits, whose state is modified by rotations in Bloch sphere, which are performed by single qubit quantum gates. In order to be understandable by quantum computers, the second quantized Hamiltonian has to be transformed into a new form - obeying the fermionic algebra of electrons but also behaving to the SU(2) group behaviour of qubits. While the occupation number vector is quite easy to transform, by asserting a qubit to $|0\rangle$ if a spin-orbital is empty, and $|1\rangle$ if a spin-orbital contains an electron, the main problem is the conservation of the antisymmetric properties of the system. The Jordan-Wigner transformation converts the creation and annihilation operators, while preserving their antisymmetric properties”.

$$\forall i < N_{\text{qubits}}, \quad a_i^+ \rightarrow \left(\prod_{j < i} \sigma_j^Z \right) \frac{\sigma_i^X - i \sigma_i^Y}{2}$$

$$\forall i < N_{\text{qubits}}, \quad a_i \rightarrow \left(\prod_{j < i} \sigma_j^Z \right) \frac{\sigma_i^X + i \sigma_i^Y}{2}$$

$\sigma^Z, \sigma^X, \sigma^Y$ are the Pauli matrices.

“Finally, the Hamiltonian of the system can be written as a sum of Pauli strings”.

Authors are mentioning S. McArdle, et al., “Quantum computational chemistry”, Reviews of Modern Physics 92, 015003 (2020) e N. Moll, et al., “Quantum optimization using variational

algorithms on near-term quantum devices”, *Quantum Science and Technology* 3, 030503 (2018).

The transformation dates to 1928, published in the *Zeitschrift für Physik*, volume 47, pages 631–651, in the article entitled *Über das Paulische Äquivalenzverbot* by Jordan and Wigner. Zusammenfassung: Die Arbeit enthält eine Fortsetzung der kürzlich von einem der Verfasser vorgelegten Note „Zur Quantenmechanik der Gasentartung“, deren Ergebnisse hier wesentlich erweitert werden. Es handelt sich darum, ein ideales oder nichtideales, dem Paulischen Äquivalenzverbot unterworfenen Gas zu beschreiben mit Begriffen, die keinen Bezug nehmen auf den abstrakten Koordinatenraum der Atomgesamtheit des Gases, sondern nur den gewöhnlichen dreidimensionalen Raum benutzen. Das wird ermöglicht durch die Darstellung des Gases vermitteltst eines gequantelten dreidimensionalen Wellenfeldes, wobei die besonderen nichtkommutativen Multiplikationseigenschaften der Wellenamplitude gleichzeitig für die Existenz korpus-kularer Gasatome und für die Gültigkeit des Paulischen Äquivalenzverbots verantwortlich sind. Die Einzelheiten der Theorie besitzen enge Analogien zu der entsprechenden Theorie für Einsteinsche ideale oder nichtideale Gase, wie sie von Dirac, Klein und Jordan ausgeführt wurde.

Molecular Quantum Dynamics Perspective

“Molecular Quantum Dynamics: A Quantum Computing Perspective” by Pauline J. Ollitrault, Alexander Miessen, and Ivano Tavernelli, 2021.

In their article, authors “present a perspective on novel quantum computational algorithms, aiming to alleviate the exponential scaling inherent to the simulation of many-body quantum dynamics. In particular, we [the authors] focus on the derivation and application of quantum algorithms for adiabatic and non-adiabatic quantum dynamics, ... In a first application, we discuss a recently introduced quantum algorithm for the evolution of a wavepacket in first quantization and exploit the potential quantum advantage of mapping its spatial grid representation to logarithmically many qubits. For the second demonstration, we move to the second quantization framework and review the scaling properties of two alternative time-evolution algorithms, namely, a variational quantum algorithm (VQA) (based on the McLachlan variational principle) and conventional Trotter-type evolution (based on a Lie–Trotter–Suzuki formula). Both methods clearly demonstrate the potential of quantum algorithms and their favorable scaling compared to the available classical approaches”.

An example given by the authors has the Hamiltonian:

$$H = K \otimes I + V_0 \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0| + V_1 \otimes |1\rangle\langle 1| + C \otimes \sigma^x$$

“where K is the kinetic energy operator, V_0 and V_1 are the potentials of the first and second diabatic curves, respectively, and C is the coupling operator. ... For concreteness, we specialize to the Marcus model, which provides a simplified description of the electron-transfer reaction rate driven by collective outer and inner sphere coordinates.” The evolution of the system is obtained by means of Trotterization.

Ising Hamiltonian

When the D-Wave quantum computer has been illustrated, we have seen that the quantum annealing leads the set of qubits to the ground state of an Ising Hamiltonian. Is this Hamiltonian capable of simulating the dynamics of molecules? The answer is positive.

Xia, R., Bian, T., & Kais, S. (2017). Electronic structure calculations and the Ising Hamiltonian. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 122(13), 3384-3395.

Abstract tells: “The exact solution of the Schrödinger equation for atoms, molecules and extended systems continues to be a "Holy Grail" problem for the field of atomic and molecular physics since inception. Recently, breakthroughs have been made in the development of hardware efficient quantum optimizers and coherent Ising machines capable of simulating hundreds of interacting spins through an Ising-type Hamiltonian. One of the most vital questions associated with these new devices is: Can these machines be used to perform electronic structure calculations?”

The study shows the standard approach used by the annealing machines. It shows that it exists “an exact mapping between the electronic structure Hamiltonian and the Ising Hamiltonian”. Simulations by means of the corresponding Ising Hamiltonian for H_2 , He_2 , HeH^+ , and LiH have a good agreement with the numerical calculus. “This demonstrates that one can map the molecular Hamiltonian to an Ising-type Hamiltonian which could easily be implemented on currently available quantum hardware.”

In the article written in 2017 it is stressed that the “Modern quantum chemistry — faced with difficulties associated with solving the Schrödinger equation to chemical accuracy (~ 1 kcal/mole) — has largely become an endeavor to find approximate methods. A few products of this effort from the past few decades include methods such as: ab initio, Density Functional, Density Matrix, Algebraic, Quantum Monte Carlo and Dimensional Scaling. However, all methods hitherto devised face the insurmountable challenge of escalating computational resource requirements as the calculation is extended either to higher accuracy or to larger systems.” We have already told that the required computation saturates the classical computers. Xia et al. are mentioning R. Babbush, P. J. Love, and A. Aspuru-Guzik, *Adiabatic quantum simulation of quantum chemistry*, *Scientific Reports*, 2014, as the first attempt of using an adiabatic quantum computing model on D-Wave. “The fundamental concept behind the adiabatic quantum computing (AQC) method is to define a problem Hamiltonian, H_P , engineered to have its ground state encode the solution of a corresponding computational problem. The system is initialized in the ground state of a beginning Hamiltonian, H_B , which is easily solved classically. The system is then allowed to evolve adiabatically as: $H(s) = (1 - s)H_B + sH_P$ (where s is a time parameter, $s \in [0, 1]$). The adiabatic evolution is governed by the Schrödinger equation for the time-dependent Hamiltonian $H(s(t))$ ”.

The QPU of D-Wave is “essentially a transverse Ising model with tunable local fields and coupling coefficients. The governing Hamiltonian is given as”:

$$H = \sum_i \Delta_i \sigma_x^i + \sum_i h^i \sigma_z^i + \sum_{i,j} J_{ij} \sigma_z^i \sigma_z^j$$

Parameters Δ_i, h_i, J_{ij} are “the physically tunable field, self-interaction and site-site interaction. The qubits are connected in a specified graph geometry”.

The adiabatic evolution starts from $H_B = \sum_i \Delta_i \sigma_x^i$ and ends in:

$$H_P = \sum_i h^i \sigma_z^i + \sum_{i,j} J_{ij} \sigma_z^i \sigma_z^j .$$

For a calculus made by the D-Wave machine, we have to manage it as follow.

“Write down the electronic structure Hamiltonian via the second quantization method in terms of creation and annihilation fermionic operators; Second, use the Jordan Wigner or the Bravyi-Kitaev transformation to move from fermionic operators to spin operators; Third, reduce the Spin Hamiltonian which is a k -local in general to a 2-local Hamiltonian. Finally, map the 2-local Hamiltonian to an Ising-type Hamiltonian.”

We have already encountered the two initial steps, in the article by O’Malley et al., when we have described the calculus made by an array of quantum gates. Therefore, we have seen how to change the Hamiltonian into a set of Pauli strings; and now, we have to change the set of Pauli strings into an Ising Hamiltonian, limited to two-spin interactions.

Xia et al. “present a universal way of mapping an n qubit Hamiltonian, H , which depends on $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$ to an rn qubits Hamiltonian, H' , consisting of only product of σ_z . In this process we increase the number of qubits from n to rn , where the integer r plays the role of a "variational parameter" to achieve the desired accuracy in the final step of energy calculations”. We have to pass from space $|\psi\rangle$, with eigenstates of the Hamiltonian made by Pauli operators acting on qubits, to space $|\Psi\rangle$, with Hamiltonian H' . “The mapping state $|\Psi\rangle$ includes the r copies of the original n qubits. The mapping of Hamiltonian from H to H' can be written as”:

$$\sigma_x^i \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sigma_z^j \sigma_z^k \right) S'(j) S'(k) \quad ; \quad \sigma_y^i \rightarrow \frac{i}{2} \left(\sigma_z^k - \sigma_z^j \right) S'(j) S'(k)$$

$$\sigma_z^i \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(\sigma_z^k + \sigma_z^j \right) S'(j) S'(k) \quad ; \quad \sigma_x^i \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sigma_z^j \sigma_z^k \right) S'(j) S'(k)$$

$S'(j), S'(k)$ represent the sign of the new qubits. A figure from the article Xia et al., helps representing the map.

Caption tells that the figure is “A schematic representation of the mapping of σ_x^2 between different basis from a state

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|000\rangle + |111\rangle) \quad \text{to state} \quad |\Psi\rangle = |000010\rangle$$

where 0 represents spin up and 1 represents spin down. The spin operators act on the second qubit in the original Hamiltonian basis and on the second and fifth qubits in the mapped Hamiltonian basis.” On the left, we can find three qubits, the state of which is mapped into the state of six qubits.

Among the simulations discussed by Xia et al. we can find the hydrogen molecule, with the Hamiltonian that we have already seen in the article by O’Malley, Peter JJ, et al. “Scalable quantum simulation of molecular energies.” Physical Review X 6.3 (2016): 031007.

$$H_{H_2} = g_0 \mathbf{1} + g_1 \sigma_z^0 + g_2 \sigma_z^1 + g_3 \sigma_z^0 \sigma_z^1 + g_4 \sigma_x^0 \sigma_x^1 + g_4 \sigma_y^0 \sigma_y^1$$

acting on two qubits. “By applying the mapping method described above, we can get the Hamiltonian H' consisting of only σ_z (where i_1 and i_2 means the 1 and 2 qubits of i -th 2 qubits)”.

$$\begin{aligned} H' = & \sum_i g_1 \sigma_z^{i_1} + g_2 \sigma_z^{i_2} + g_3 \sigma_z^{i_1} \sigma_z^{i_2} + \sum_{i \neq j} [g_1 \frac{(\sigma_z^{i_1} + \sigma_z^{j_1})(1 + \sigma_z^{i_2} \sigma_z^{j_2})}{4} S'(i)S'(j) \\ & + g_2 \frac{(\sigma_z^{i_2} + \sigma_z^{j_2})(1 + \sigma_z^{i_1} \sigma_z^{j_1})}{4} S'(i)S'(j) + g_3 \frac{(\sigma_z^{i_1} + \sigma_z^{j_1})(\sigma_z^{i_2} + \sigma_z^{j_2})}{4} S'(i)S'(j) \\ & + g_4 \frac{(1 + \sigma_z^{i_1} \sigma_z^{i_1})(1 + \sigma_z^{i_2} \sigma_z^{j_2})}{4} S'(i)S'(j) + g_4 \frac{(\sigma_z^{i_1} - \sigma_z^{i_1})(\sigma_z^{j_2} - \sigma_z^{j_2})}{4} S'(i)S'(j)] \end{aligned}$$

See please also the discussion by Streif, M., Neukart, F., & Leib, M. (2019, March), in “Solving quantum chemistry problems with a d-wave quantum annealer”.

DiVincenzo's words and current trend

We have analyzed the machines and the different simulation systems based on qubits and qumodes. For superconducting qubit systems, the approach with the quantum gate array and the adiabatic one with annealing have been discussed in detail. We have seen how to pass from the Hamiltonian of the system to be simulated, written in the second quantization, to the Hamiltonian of the qubit system, written with the Pauli operators, and then how to further arrive at the Ising Hamiltonian of the quantum annealing.

We might ask ourselves which is the best approach? Which technology will be the winner?

“So, what is the “winning” technology going to be?” - DiVincenzo told in 2000 – “I don’t think that any living mortal has an answer to this question, and at this point it may be counterproductive even to ask it. Even though we have lived with quantum mechanics for a century, our study of *quantum effects in complex artificial systems* like those we have in mind for quantum computing is in its infancy. No one can see how or whether all the requirements above [i criteri di DiVincenzo] can be fulfilled, or whether there are new tradeoffs, not envisioned in our present theoretical discussions but suggested by further experiments, that might take our investigations in an entirely new path. Indeed, the above discussion, and the other chapters of this special issue, really do not cover all the foreseeable approaches”.

Starting from these words by DiVincenzo, we can return to the article on January 2022, in the Sole 24 Ore, where the strategy of the quantum advantage is highlighted. The current trend, waiting for a better performance of machines, is to find applications and build the IT environment where to make the most of what DiVincenzo calls the "quantum effects in complex artificial systems".

More than twenty years have passed since DiVincenzo wrote the criteria for these artificial systems. Someone might think that, today, everything has been done, both in terms of technology and simulation. It is not so. Qubit systems are difficult to scale, due to the "rat's nest" of the required cables, and both Microsoft and Intel are working hard to solve the problem. As for what concerns software, let us take the example of simulations in chemistry. The simulated molecules are small. Switching to the simulation of larger molecules requires not only a machine with a larger number of qubits, but a series of algorithms that facilitate the transition from the Hamiltonian of the system to that of the qubits, with related mapping.

The abstract of “Emerging quantum computing algorithms for quantum chemistry”, Mario Motta and Julia E. Rice, IBM Quantum, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2109.02873.pdf>, tells that “Digital quantum computers provide a computational framework for solving the Schrödinger equation for a variety of many-particle systems. Quantum computing algorithms for the quantum simulation of these systems *have recently witnessed remarkable growth, notwithstanding the limitations of existing quantum hardware, especially as a tool for electronic structure computations in molecules.*” The review continues descriptions “*emerging algorithms* for the simulation of Hamiltonian dynamics and eigenstates, with emphasis on their applications to the electronic structure in molecular systems”.

It is clear that we are still in the phase of emerging algorithms and not of algorithms which have been consolidated in software packages to be applied to the desired molecule. But this is what the quantum advantage is now driving: to have roads, traffic lights, service stations, even before the high-performance machine leaves the research centers.

The prospects in computational molecular biology

Outeiral, C. et al. (2021). “The prospects of quantum computing in computational molecular biology”. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews.

“Quantum computers can in principle solve certain problems exponentially more quickly than

their classical counterparts. *We have not yet reached the advent of useful quantum computation, but when we do, it will affect nearly all scientific disciplines*". The review is discussing the algorithms today available, and how they can "revolutionize computational biology and bioinformatics. There are potential benefits across the entire field, from the ability to process vast amounts of information and run machine learning algorithms far more efficiently, to algorithms for quantum simulation that are poised to improve computational calculations in drug discovery, to quantum algorithms for optimization that may advance fields from protein structure prediction to network analysis. However, these exciting prospects are susceptible to "hype," and *it is also important to recognize the caveats and challenges in this new technology.*" The aim of this review is to "introduce the promise and limitations of emerging quantum computing technologies in the areas of computational molecular biology and bioinformatics". [Outeiral et al.]

In the review it is told that "The technical challenges of building quantum computers have not stopped the development of quantum algorithms. Even in the absence of hardware, algorithms can be analyzed mathematically, and the emergence of high-performance simulators of quantum computers, as well as early prototypes in the last few years, have enabled further investigation. Some of these algorithms have already shown promise for applications in biology. For example, the quantum phase estimation algorithm allows exponentially faster eigenvalue calculation [Kitaev, arXiv], which can be used to understand large scale correlation between portions of a protein or determine centrality in a biological network. The Harrow–Hassidim–Lloyd (HHL) quantum algorithm [<https://arxiv.org/abs/0811.3171>] can solve certain linear systems exponentially faster than any known classical algorithm, and so could power statistical learning techniques that can be trained more quickly and manage more data. Quantum optimization algorithms have potential in the field of protein folding and conformer sampling, and across problems that involve finding minima or maxima [Albasha T, Lidar DA., 2018]. Finally, technology to simulate quantum systems has been developed which promises accurate predictions of drug–receptor interaction [Cao, Y. et al., 2018] or insight into chemical mechanisms such as photosynthesis [Wang, B. X., et al., 2018]. Quantum computing has the potential to change the way we do biology much as classical computing did." [Outeiral et al.]

For the photosynthesis Hamiltonians, see please

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41534-018-0102-2>

"Efficient quantum simulation of photosynthetic light harvesting"

Regarding the simulations in chemistry, physics, biology, is everything already done? No. It's all to be done. And what about commercial applications?

First commercial applications?

Let us consider again news from press and web sites.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20220629120939/https://www.digital4.biz/executive/innovation-management/computer-quantistico-quantum-computing/>

"Il computer quantistico arriva nel business. Ecco cos'è, come funziona e quali sono le prime applicazioni commerciali", by Patrizia Licata (15 February 2022). "Il quantum computing,

benché agli albori, già esiste ed è utilizzato: dai modelli finanziari alla medicina – inclusa la ricerca per il Covid-19 -, dalle previsioni meteorologiche alla crittografia.”

And also: "Il quantum computing ha già degli early adopters. Uno studio di Reply, realizzato grazie alla piattaforma proprietaria di rilevamento e monitoraggio delle tendenze “trend SONAR”, ha individuato i settori in cui si sta sviluppando il maggior numero di applicazioni commerciali: Informatica, Servizi finanziari, Logistica e trasporti, Cybersecurity."

If it is as Feynman told, that the quantum computer is used for quantum physics simulations, how can it be applied to supply chains and transportation?

Here an example from the news

<https://www.volkswagenag.com/en/news/stories/2021/08/volkswagen-takes-quantum-computing-from-the-lab-to-the-factory.html>

"Volkswagen takes quantum computing from the lab to the factory". "Using the D-Wave quantum computer, Volkswagen is researching the future potential for quantum computing. Researchers believe quantum computers could tackle challenges that even the most powerful traditional computers struggle. While quantum computers are still highly experimental, a global race to develop new machines has started, and companies have begun finding ways to apply them to real-world challenges. In the automotive industry, Volkswagen Group has led the way, launching a dedicated team for quantum computing research in 2016."

The research is detailed by Neukart, F., Compostella, G., Seidel, C., Von Dollen, D., Yarkoni, S., & Parney, B. (2017). in their "Traffic flow optimization using a quantum annealer". *Frontiers in ICT*, 4, 29.

οἶδα δ' ἐγὼ ψάμμου τ' ἀριθμὸν καὶ μέτρα θαλάσσης
I can count the grains of sand and measure the sea

Oracle

A possible answer, useful to understand the role of quantum computation in logistics, is provided by the following example. Suppose that you know a telephone number and you want to search for the owner's name in a telephone directory; what we can do classically is to scroll through the list. On average, with a classical algorithm, half of it must be scrolled. In 1996, however, an algorithm was proposed, today known as the Grover algorithm, and this algorithm changed the way of doing the search.

Before discussing the Grover algorithm, it is necessary to introduce the "oracle".

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oracle_machine

“In complexity theory and computability theory, an oracle machine is an abstract machine used to study decision problems. It can be visualized as a Turing machine with a black box, called an oracle, which is able to solve certain problems in a single operation. The problem can be of any complexity class. Even undecidable problems, such as the halting problem, can be used.

On the oracle in quantum computation: “Work with and define quantum oracles”, link <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/quantum/concepts-oracles> (*Archive*)

Grover algorithm

The following link <https://qiskit.org/textbook/ch-algorithms/grover.html#introduction> is about the “Unstructured Search: Suppose you are given a large list of N items. Among these items there is one item with a unique property that we wish to locate; we will call this one *the winner* w .” The web site uses an example where we have many boxes, and among them, the purple one is the winner. “To find the purple box using classical computation, one would have to check on average $N/2$ of these boxes, and in the worst case, all N of them. On a quantum computer, however, we can find the marked item in roughly \sqrt{N} steps with *Grover's amplitude amplification trick*. A quadratic speedup is indeed a substantial time-saver for finding marked items in long lists. Additionally, the algorithm does not use the list's internal structure, which makes it generic; this is why it immediately provides a quadratic quantum speed-up for many classical problems.”

The algorithm starts from the creation of the initial state and of an “oracle”.

And here an example of the creation of an oracle. If we have 3 qubits, we have the list of the following states: $|000\rangle$, $|001\rangle$, ..., $|111\rangle$ (i.e. of the states $|0\rangle \rightarrow |7\rangle$). “Grover’s algorithm solves oracles that add a negative phase to the solution states. I.e. for any state $|x\rangle$ in the computational basis:

$$U_{\omega}|x\rangle = \begin{cases} |x\rangle & \text{if } x \neq \omega \\ -|x\rangle & \text{if } x = \omega \end{cases}$$

This oracle will be a diagonal matrix, where the entry that correspond to the marked item will have a negative phase.” (see please qiskit.org and the corresponding matrix).

Note that the winner is $x = \omega$.

“What makes Grover’s algorithm so powerful is how easy it is to convert a problem to an oracle of this form. There are many computational problems in which it’s difficult to find a solution, but relatively easy to verify a solution.” Then the web site proposes a detailed discussion of the general case and provides the code.

A description of the algorithm is given also by Azure, “Theory of Grover's search algorithm”, <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/quantum/concepts-grover>

Any search task can be expressed with an abstract function $f(x)$ that accepts search items x . If the item x is a solution to the search task, then $f(x) = 1$. If the item x is not a solution, then $f(x) = 0$. The search problem consists of finding any item x_0 such that

$f(x_0) = 1$. In fact, the task that Grover's algorithm aims to solve can be expressed as

follows: given a classical function $f(x): \{0,1\}^n \rightarrow \{0,1\}$, where n is the bit-size of the search space, find an input x_0 for which $f(x_0) = 1$.

Azure explains the complexity of the algorithm. Then we can find the Outline.

Suppose there are $N = 2^n$ eligible items for the search task and they are indexed by assigning

each item an integer from 0 to $N-1$. Further, suppose that there are M different valid inputs, meaning that there are M inputs for which $f(x)=1$. The steps of the algorithm are then as follows:

1. Start with a register of n qubits initialized in the state $|0\rangle$.
2. Prepare the register into a uniform superposition by applying H to each qubit of the register:

$$|\text{register}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} |x\rangle$$

3. Apply the following operations to the register N_{optimal} times:
 - a. The phase oracle O_f that applies a conditional phase shift of -1 for the solution items.
 - b. Apply H to each qubit in the register.
 - c. A conditional phase shift of -1 to every computational basis state except $|0\rangle$. This can be represented by the unitary operation $-O_0$, as O_0 represents the conditional phase shift to $|0\rangle$ only.
 - d. Apply H to each qubit in the register.
4. Measure the register to obtain the index of a item that's a solution with very high probability.
5. Check if it's a valid solution. If not, start again.

Let's follow the mathematical transformations of the state of the register for a simple case in which there are only two qubits and the valid element is $|01\rangle$. The register starts in the state:

$$|\text{register}\rangle = |00\rangle$$

Let us apply H on each qubit.

$$|\text{register}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} \sum_{i \in \{0,1\}^2} |i\rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle + |01\rangle + |10\rangle + |11\rangle)$$

The, we use the oracle:

$$|\text{register}\rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle - |01\rangle + |10\rangle + |11\rangle)$$

We apply again H on each qubit.

$$|\text{register}\rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle + |01\rangle - |10\rangle + |11\rangle)$$

Then, we apply the

conditional phase shift on each state, but not on $|00\rangle$:

$$|\text{register}\rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle - |01\rangle + |10\rangle - |11\rangle)$$

Again H on each qubit. We find:

$$|\text{register}\rangle = |01\rangle$$

And this is the state we searched for. Only one iteration was enough to find the state. If we have N qubits, iterations are \sqrt{N} .

At the page docs.microsoft.com/it-it/azure/quantum/tutorial-qdk-grovers-search we have the Grover algorithm in Q#.

Therefore, if you have to solve a search problem for a supply chain or for transportation, this problem can be approached using a "Grover's like" scheme, therefore with an approach based on the new way of quantum computing.

Multis annis post Romulum, Prisco regnante Tarquinio, quis veterum scriptorum non loquitur quae sit ab Atto Navio per lituum regionum facta discriptio? Qui cum propter paupertatem sues puer pasceret, una ex iis amissa, vovisse dicitur, si recuperasset, uvam se deo daturum, quae maxima esset in vinea; itaque, suae inventa, ad meridiem spectans in vinea media dicitur constituisse, cumque in quattuor partis vineam divisisset trisque partis aves abdixissent, quarta parte, quae erat reliqua, in regiones distributa, mirabili magnitudine uvam, ut scriptum videmus, invenit. Qua re celebrata, cum vicini omnes ad eum de rebus suis referrent, erat in magno nomine et gloria.

Tullius Cicero, De Divinatione, Libro I.

Algorithms having Ising Hamiltonian

By means of the adiabatic calculation we can study problems concerning the “covering” and the “packing”, which are related to logistics. Let us consider again the thesis “Solving NP-Hard Problems on an Adiabatic Quantum Computer”, October 2014, by Dan Padilha.

The thesis is proposing experimentation of different algorithms, such as partition problems, referring to the article “Ising formulations of many NP problems”, by Andrew Lucas. Of this article, abstract tells: “We provide Ising formulations for many NP-complete and NP-hard problems, including all of Karp’s 21 NP-complete problems. This collects and extends mappings to the Ising model from partitioning, covering and satisfiability. In each case, the required number of spins is at most cubic in the size of the problem. This work may be useful in designing adiabatic quantum optimization algorithms.”

In a section of the article, Lucas discusses for instance, “another simple class of mappings from NP problems to Ising models: “covering” and “packing” problems. These problems can often be thought of as asking: how can I pick elements out of a set (such as vertices out of a graph’s vertex set) so that they “cover” the graph in some simple way (e.g., removing them makes the edge set empty). In this class of problems, there are constraints which must be exactly satisfied. ... We conclude the section with the minimal maximal matching problem, which is a slightly more involved problem that has not been discussed in the AQO [adiabatic quantum optimization] literature before. These are, by far, the most popular class of problems discussed in the AQO literature.”

Graph partitioning and QUBO

Ushijima-Mwesigwa, H. et al., 2017, “Graph partitioning using quantum annealing on the D-wave system”.

“Graph partitioning (GP) applications are ubiquitous throughout mathematics, computer science, chemistry, physics, bioscience, machine learning, and complex systems. Post Moore’s era supercomputing has provided us an opportunity to explore new approaches for traditional graph algorithms on quantum computing architectures”. In their article, the researchers “explore graph partitioning using quantum annealing on the D-Wave 2X machine. Motivated by a recently proposed graph-based electronic structure theory applied to quantum molecular dynamics (QMD) simulations, graph partitioning is used for reducing the calculation of the density matrix into smaller subsystems rendering the calculation more computationally efficient. Unconstrained graph partitioning as community clustering based on the modularity metric can be naturally mapped into the Hamiltonian of the quantum annealer. On the other hand, when constraints are imposed for partitioning into equal parts and minimizing the number of cut edges between parts, a quadratic unconstrained binary optimization (QUBO) reformulation is required.” Details in the article by Ushijima-Mwesigwa, H. et al., 2017.

“Often the quantum unconstrained binary optimization (QUBO) representation with it’s 0/1 - valued variables is more natural than the Ising $-1/+1$ -valued variables. The QUBO objective function is shown in Eq.(*), where Q is an $n \times n$ uppertriangular matrix of coupler strengths and x is a vector of binary variables (0/1). Q_{ii} is an analog to the Ising h_i , as are Q_{ij} and J_{ij} . The Ising and QUBO models are related through the transformation $s = 2x - 1$.”

D-Wave quantum machine allows for either form. Here one of them:

$$O(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{x}) = \sum_i Q_{ii} x_i + \sum_{i < j} Q_{ij} x_i x_j$$

The future

Preparing the future

And here, let us see what we can find in the abstract of “Quantum Chain of Things (QCoT): A New Paradigm for Integrating Quantum Computing, Blockchain, and Internet of Things”, by Younan, M, et al. 2021.

“Recently, Internet of Things (IoT) and Blockchain (BC) are coupled to present smart and secure applications. Quantum Computing (QC) is a new paradigm that imposes itself as a main technology in the near future, especially in the 6G era, due to its powerful computations. As a result, immigration of the IoT and BC to the QC has to be studied and prepared. This paper provides a brief review of relevant recent work to identify opportunities for optimal integration. Besides, a new paradigm called Quantum Chain of Things (QCoT) is proposed and its perspective architecture is presented and verified into two parts: (a) BC-IoT using Arduino, and (b) QC-IoT using IBM Qiskit simulator. Finally, presented knowledge such as current challenges, threads, and integration opportunities could help researchers to investigate new trends and future directions.”

Also the article “Quantum Computing for Supply Chain Finance”, Griffin Paul eand Ritesh Sampat, 2021, is considering the use of the quantum computing. In this case, it is the trade finance which is considered. “This paper shows an implementation of two quantum optimization algorithms applied to trade finance portfolios and compares the selections to those chosen by experienced underwriters and a classical optimizer. The method used is to map the financial risk and returns for a trade finance portfolio to an optimization function of a quantum algorithm developed in a Qiskit tutorial. The results show that whilst there is no advantage seen by using the quantum algorithms, the performance of the quantum algorithms has no statistically significant degradation.” In the future, with new machines and increased speed, the quantum computation “will also be applicable to trade finance.”

Change is the law of life. And those who look only to the past or present are certain to miss the future.

John Fitzgerald Kennedy

Communication

Quantum communication

In 2000, DiVincenzo wrote the “desiderata for quantum communication”.

After the statement and discussion of the five desiderata for computation alone, DiVincenzo proposed the criteria for quantum communication. “But the advantages of quantum information processing are not manifest solely, or perhaps even principally, for straightforward computation only. There are many kinds of information-processing tasks, ... that involve more than just computation, and for which quantum tools provide a unique advantage. The tasks we have in mind here all involve not only computation but also communication. The list of these tasks that have been considered in the light of quantum capabilities, and for which some advantage has been found in using quantum tools, is fairly long and diverse: it includes secret key distribution, multiparty function evaluation as in appointment scheduling, secret sharing, and game playing”. “When we say communication we mean quantum communication: the transmission of intact qubits from place to place. This obviously adds more features that the physical apparatus must have to carry out this information processing.” [DiVincenzo]

DiVincenzo gives the two following desiderata:

6. *The ability to interconvert stationary and flying qubits*
7. *The ability faithfully to transmit flying qubits between specified locations*

DiVincenzo mentions the “flying qubits”, “which has become current in the discussions of quantum communication. Using this term *emphasizes* that the optimal embodiment of qubits that are readily transmitted from place to place is likely to be very different from the optimal qubits for reliable local computation. Indeed, almost all proposals assume that photon states, with the qubit encoded either in the polarization or in the spatial wavefunction of the photon, will be the flying qubit of choice, and indeed, the well developed technology of light transmission through optical fibers provides a very promising system for the transmission of qubits”. And DiVincenzo adds further considerations.

Flying qubit

<https://quantumcomputing.stackexchange.com/questions/8900/what-is-a-flying-qubit> (Archive).

“So, what exactly is a flying qubit, and how is it related to and different from a normal qubit? Please help understand more. I am undertaking Delft University's course in EdX on Quantum Internet and Quantum Computers.”

For short, these are the differences.

“Stationary qubits need to: Be able to store quantum information reliably on a timescale of $\tau \sim ms$; Perform calculations: various gates/operations need to be reliably performed on them. This includes an operation that moves/converts the information to a flying qubit ; Be able to be measured/read out reliably ; Be able to be highly entangled.

Flying qubits, however, need to: Be send over macroscopic distances while keeping their encoded (quantum) information intact ; Be operational on a macroscopic temperature scale (i.e. about room temperature); Perform only one single operation reliably: converting into stationary qubits ; Be able to be entangled.”

Moreover, it is stressed that “there exist myriad different implementations of stationary qubits that all have their advantages and disadvantages; it is still an open question what the final 'go to' stationary qubit design (if any) will be. For flying qubits, there is one clear design which is the most promising: *the photon*.”

"The photon travels very fast, and has a straightforward two-level system (namely, its polarization). Also, this polarization can be conserved at higher temperatures. Note that other encodings of the qubit into the photon are also possible, for instance the time-bin encoding. Note that it is highly unlikely that stationary and flying qubits will be based on the same physical principle or design. That is to say, stationary qubits will most likely be based on an entirely different physical phenomenon than stationary qubits (e.g. Ion traps, superconducting qubits/transmons, quantum dots, other confined electron systems etc. for stationary qubits.) There are, however, designs for a quantum computer (with stationary qubits) based on the use of photons; only time will tell what actual implementation of stationary and flying qubits will prevail.”

A quantum communication explainer

“Explainer: What is quantum communication?”, “Researchers and companies are creating ultra-secure communication networks that could form the basis of a quantum internet. This is how it works.”di Martin Giles, February 14, 2019, MIT Technology Review, <https://www.technologyreview.com/2019/02/14/103409/what-is-quantum-communications/>

“Today, sensitive data is typically encrypted and then sent across fiber-optic cables and other channels together with the digital “keys” needed to decode the information. The data and the keys are sent as classical bits And that makes them vulnerable. Smart hackers can read and copy bits in transit without leaving a trace. Quantum communication takes advantage of the laws of quantum physics to protect data. These laws allow particles, which are typically photons of light for transmitting data along optical cables, to take on a state of superposition, ... The beauty of qubits from a cybersecurity perspective is that if a hacker tries to observe them in transit, their super-fragile quantum state “collapses” to either 1 or 0. This means a hacker can’t tamper with the qubits without leaving behind a telltale sign of the activity.” [Giles]

It has been undertaken the creation of networks with the ability to transmit “highly sensitive data based on a process called quantum key distribution, or QKD. In theory, at least, these networks are ultra-secure.” [Giles]

First: what is a quantum key distribution or QKD? QKD is a protocol which is sending

encrypted data as classical bits over networks, while sending the keys, required to decrypt the information, encoded and transmitted in a quantum state using qubits.

Among QKD protocols, according to Giles the best known is the BB84.

"One of the processes involved in the protocol is the "key sifting". Since qubits suffer from decoherence while traveling to their destination, a further process is that of "key distillation," "which involves calculating whether the error rate is high enough to suggest that a hacker has tried to intercept the key".

Giles wrote in 2019 that "We're already starting to see more QKD networks emerge. The longest is in China, which boasts a 2,032-kilometer (1,263-mile) ground link between Beijing and Shanghai. Banks and other financial companies are already using it to transmit data. In the US, a startup called Quantum Xchange has struck a deal giving it access to 500 miles (805 kilometers) of fiber-optic cable running along the East Coast to create a QKD network. The initial leg will link Manhattan with New Jersey, where many banks have large data centers."

[Giles]

Although the QKD network is rather secure, it would be even better if it had a quantum repeater. "What is a quantum repeater? Materials in cables can absorb photons, which means they can typically travel for no more than a few tens of kilometers."

Repeaters exist in classic networks to compensate for losses. "QKD networks have come up with a similar solution, creating "trusted nodes" at various points. The Beijing-to-Shanghai network has 32 of them, for instance. At these waystations, quantum keys are decrypted into bits and then reencrypted in a fresh quantum state for their journey to the next node." This step requires security protocols too.

Giles is mentioning another issue with QKD protocols. The key is quantum transmitted but the underlying data is transmitted as encrypted bits across conventional networks. "This means a hacker who breached a network's defenses could copy the bits undetected, and then use powerful computers to try to crack the key used to encrypt them. The most powerful encryption algorithms are pretty robust, but the risk is big enough to spur some researchers to work on an alternative approach known as quantum teleportation." [Giles]

Researchers are trying to implement a teleportation-based network. "Researchers in the US, China, and Europe are racing to create teleportation networks capable of distributing entangled photons. But getting them to scale will be a massive scientific and engineering challenge. The many hurdles include finding reliable ways of churning out lots of linked photons on demand, and maintaining their entanglement over very long distances—something that quantum repeaters would make easier." [Giles]

Giles discusses the quantum internet. About this subject, see please Krenn, M., Malik, M., Scheidl, T., Ursin, R., & Zeilinger, A. (2016). Quantum communication with photons. *Optics in our Time*, 18, 455.

Recent News

Qudit and trapped ions

ANSA – 22 July 2022 . ([Archive](#)) “Sbloccata la potenza di calcolo dei computer quantistici. Pronto il primo dispositivo che va oltre 0 e 1”. “Lo ha messo a punto il gruppo dell'Università austriaca di Innsbruck guidato da Martin Ringbauer, che ha pubblicato il risultato sulla rivista Nature Physics”.

Ringbauer, M., Meth, M., Postler, L. et al. A universal qudit quantum processor with trapped ions. Nat. Phys. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-022-01658-0> disponibile a <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2109.06903.pdf>

“Today’s quantum computers operate with a binary encoding that is the quantum analog of classical bits. Yet, the underlying quantum hardware consists of information carriers that are not necessarily binary, but typically exhibit a rich multilevel structure, which is artificially restricted to two dimensions. A wide range of applications from quantum chemistry to quantum simulation, on the other hand, would benefit from access to higher-dimensional Hilbert spaces, which conventional quantum computers can only emulate. Here we demonstrate a universal qudit quantum processor using trapped ions with a local Hilbert space dimension of up to 7. With a performance similar to qubit quantum processors, this approach enables native simulation of high-dimensional quantum systems, as well as more efficient implementation of qubit-based algorithms”.

Qudit-based quantum processor in silicon-photonic integrated circuits

Article published in Nature 04 March 2022. “A programmable qudit-based quantum processor”. Yulin Chi, et al. Nature Communications volume 13, Article number: 1166 (2022). Authors “have reported a proof-of-principle experimental demonstration of a programmable qudit-based quantum processor in photonic integrated circuits, and implementations of several generalised d-ary quantum Fourier transform algorithms in the d-QPU chip. ... experimental results show that qudit-based quantum computation with integrated photonics can enhance quantum parallelism in terms of the computational capacity, accuracy and efficiency, in comparison with its qubit-based quantum computing counterpart. The computational capacity of the two *ququart* quantum processor is equivalent to that of a *four-qubit* processor, thus allowing the implementations of the Deutsch’s algorithms for a function with longer-string. Keeping the same number of photons n but encoding each qudit in a dimension d , not only gives a larger Hilbert space, but also significantly improve the detection rate of photons. We obtained the detection rate of about 6 orders brighter than that in another device with the same Hilbert space”.

Alibaba fluxonium

News: “An alternative superconducting qubit achieves high performance for quantum computing”, Ingrid Fadelli, Phys.org, 27 July 2022, <https://phys.org/news/2022-07-alternative-superconducting-qubit-high-quantum.html>

The researches of Alibaba Quantum Laboratory, in the DAMO Research Institute Alibaba Group, have created a QPU based on fluxonium qubit. The researchers published in the Physical Review Letters their work demonstrating the potential of fluxonium to create superconducting circuits. Bao, F., Deng, H., Ding, D., Gao, R., Gao, X., Huang, C., ... & Deng, C. (2022). Fluxonium: an alternative qubit platform for high-fidelity operations. Available in arXiv <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2111.13504.pdf>

Yaoyun Shi, Director Alibaba's Quantum Laboratory, told Phys.org that “relatively new type of superconducting qubit could go much further than transmon.” “Fluxonium qubits have two characteristics that set it apart from transmons: their energy levels are far more uneven (i.e., "anharmonic") and they use a large inductor to replace the capacitor used in transmon. Both contribute to fluxonium's advantage, at least theoretically, in being more resilient to errors, leading to better "coherence," i.e., holding quantum information for a longer time, and "higher fidelity," i.e., accuracy, in realizing elementary operations.”

It is explained that, in the case of transmons, a “call” for the transition between the first two energy levels (states "0" and "1"), can accidentally cause transitions between the second and third level. This takes the state out of computational space, causing what is referred to as a “leakage error”. “In fluxonium, on the other hand, the distance separating the second and third energy "steps" is greater, which reduces the risk of leakage errors.”

The design of a fluxonium is simple. The fluxonium is a "Josephson junction shunted with a large inductor, which is similar, in fact, to that of a transmon, which is a Josephson junction shunted with a capacitor," says Chunqing Deng. And also: "The large inductor is often, as in our case as well, implemented by a large number (in our work, 100) of Josephson junctions."

We can go back to the D-Wave tables. The Pegasus P16 is seen to have 5640 qubits and 1030000 Josephson junctions. So Josephson junctions are not used just for qubits, they are needed for the circuit elements of the computer.

“Replacing the capacitor with an inductor in fluxonium removes the "islands" resulting from the electrodes and the source of "charge noises" caused by electron charge fluctuations, thus making fluxonium more error-proof. This is, however, at the expense of much more demanding engineering, due to the large array of Josephson junctions.”

“In initial tests, the quantum platform designed by Chunqing and his colleagues was found to attain an average single-qubit gate fidelity of 99.97% and a two-qubit gate fidelity of up to 99.72%. These values are comparable to some of the best results achieved by quantum processors in previous studies.”

Chunqing hopes the published research will increase interest in fluxonium, “so that its full potential can be unlocked to achieve a significantly higher performance in fidelity, which will in

turn significantly reduce the overhead of realizing fault-tolerance quantum computing. What this means is that, for the same computational task, a higher-fidelity fluxonium quantum computer may need significantly fewer number of qubits."

GRAPE

Being able to optimize the program, which describes the sequence of logic gates to be applied to qubit registers, reduces the problem of decoherence.

"New method to systematically find optimal quantum operation sequences for quantum computers", National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT). 2 Settembre 2022. <https://phys.org/news/2022-09-method-systematically-optimal-quantum-sequences.html> (Archive).

"Japan's National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, Keio University, Tokyo University of Science and The University of Tokyo succeeded for the first time in developing a method for systematically finding the optimal quantum operation sequence for a quantum computer. In order for a quantum computer to perform a task, one needs to write a sequence of quantum operations. Until now, computer operators have written their own quantum operation sequences based on existing methods (recipes). What has been developed this time is a systematic method that applies optimal control theory (GRAPE algorithm) to identify the theoretically optimal sequence from among all conceivable quantum operation sequences."

The article by Ashhab, S., et al. (2022). Numerical analysis of quantum circuits for state preparation and unitary operator synthesis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2204.13524, has been published in Physical Review A.

One of the main problems for quantum computation is that the quantum state is very sensitive to noise, and consequently it is difficult to maintain it stably for a long time in a coherent quantum state. "In order to obtain the best performance, it is necessary to complete the operations within the time that the coherent quantum state is maintained. There was a need for a method to systematically identify the optimal sequences".

Appendix: Some algebra

Suggested reading "Principles of Quantum Communication Theory: A Modern Approach", by Sumeet Khatri and Mark M. Wilde, November 11, 2020.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2011.04672>

The algebra is based on Hilbert spaces. Let us consider only finite-dimensional Hilbert spaces, denoted by H . A d -dimensional Hilbert space ($1 \leq d < \infty$) is defined to be a complex vector space equipped with an inner product. We use the notation $|\psi\rangle$ to denote a vector in H . Inner product is a function $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle : H \times H \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ that satisfies the following properties: non-

negativity, conjugate bilinearity, and conjugate symmetry. Notation: a^* is the complex conjugate of a .

All d -dimensional Hilbert spaces are isomorphic to the vector space C^d equipped with the Euclidean inner product. Note that C^d is the vector space of d -dimensional column vectors with elements in C . Let us assume the set $\{|i\rangle\}$, with i from 0 to $d-1$, as the orthonormal basis, also known as the standard basis or computational basis. Vectors can be represented as:

$$|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \dots, \quad |d-1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The inner product gives: $\langle i|j\rangle = \delta_{ij}$ (Kronecker delta function).

(See also [Bra-Ket Notation\(Bra space\)](#))

Given two vectors $|\phi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} \alpha_i |i\rangle$; $|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} \beta_i |i\rangle$, we have $\langle \psi|\phi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} \beta_i^* \alpha_i$.

The Euclidean norm is: $\|\psi\|_2 = \sqrt{\langle \psi|\psi\rangle}$. It holds also the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality.

From [Bra-Ket Notation-Expectation Values](#)

Expectation values. Consider an ensemble of microscopic systems prepared in the same initial state $|A\rangle$. Suppose a measurement of the observable ξ' is made on each system. We know that each measurement yields the value ξ' with probability $P(\xi')$. What is the mean value of the measurement? This quantity, which is generally referred to as the expectation value of ξ' , is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \xi \rangle &= \sum_{\xi'} \xi' P(\xi') = \sum_{\xi'} \xi' |\langle A|\xi\rangle|^2 \\ &= \sum_{\xi'} \xi' \langle A|\xi\rangle \langle \xi'|A\rangle = \sum_{\xi'} \xi' \langle A|\xi|\xi'\rangle \langle \xi'|A\rangle \end{aligned}$$

which reduces to $\langle \xi \rangle = \langle A|\xi|A\rangle$.

Tensor product of vectors: for two Hilbert spaces H_A and H_B with dimensions d_A and d_B , respectively, along with associated orthonormal bases $\{|i\rangle_A\}$ and $\{|j\rangle_B\}$, the tensor product vector $|i\rangle_A \otimes |j\rangle_B$ is a vector in a $d_A \times d_B$ -dimensional Hilbert space with a one

in its $(i \cdot d_B + j + 1)^{th}$ entry and zeros elsewhere.

$$\text{For instance: } |i\rangle \otimes |j\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |2\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ 0 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Generally:

$$|\psi\rangle_A \otimes |\phi\rangle_B = \sum_{i=0}^{d_A-1} \sum_{j=0}^{d_B-1} \alpha_i \beta_j |i\rangle_A \otimes |j\rangle_B.$$

The example given above, with $d_A = 2$ and $d_B = 3$, can be calculated by a generalization of the “stack-and-multiply” procedure:

$$|\psi\rangle_A \otimes |\phi\rangle_B = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 \\ \alpha_1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \end{pmatrix} \\ \alpha_1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 \beta_0 \\ \alpha_0 \beta_1 \\ \alpha_0 \beta_2 \\ \alpha_1 \beta_0 \\ \alpha_1 \beta_1 \\ \alpha_1 \beta_2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The tensor-product Hilbert space $H_A \otimes H_B$ is defined to be the Hilbert space spanned by the vectors $|i\rangle_A \otimes |j\rangle_B$ defined above, with an inner product defined as:

$$\langle \langle i|_A \otimes \langle j|_B \rangle \langle i'|_A \otimes |j'\rangle_B \rangle = \langle i|i'\rangle \langle j|j'\rangle = \delta_{i,i'} \delta_{j,j'}$$

Abbreviations: $H_{AB} \equiv H_A \otimes H_B$, $|i, j\rangle_{AB} = |i\rangle_A \otimes |j\rangle_B$.

The direct sum of H_A and H_B , denoted by $H_A \oplus H_B$, is defined to be the Hilbert space of vectors

$$|\psi\rangle_A \oplus |\phi\rangle_B :$$

$$|\psi\rangle_A \oplus |\phi\rangle_B := \begin{pmatrix} |\psi\rangle_A \\ |\phi\rangle_B \end{pmatrix}.$$

that is:

$$|\psi\rangle_A \oplus |\phi\rangle_B = |0\rangle \otimes |\psi\rangle + |1\rangle \otimes |\phi\rangle,$$

where we can find the standard basis of a 2-dimensional Hilbert space.

If $\{|i\rangle_A\}$ and $\{|j\rangle_B\}$ are orthonormal bases for H_A and H_B , respectively, then

$$\left\{ \begin{pmatrix} |i\rangle_A \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} : 0 \leq i \leq d_A - 1 \right\} \cup \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ |j\rangle_B \end{pmatrix} : 0 \leq j \leq d_B - 1 \right\}$$

is the orthonormal basis of $H_A \oplus H_B$, with inner product:

$$(\langle i|_A \oplus \langle j|_B)(|i'\rangle_A \oplus |j'\rangle_B) = \langle i|i'\rangle + \langle j|j'\rangle = \delta_{i,i'} + \delta_{j,j'}.$$

$H_A \oplus H_B$ has dimension $d_A + d_B$. One of the simplest examples of a direct-sum Hilbert space is $C \oplus C = C^2$. More generally, the d -fold direct sum $C^{\oplus d}$ is equal to C^d .

Let us assume a Hilbert space H_A with dimension d_A and a Hilbert space H_B with dimension d_B , a **linear operator** $X : H_A \rightarrow H_B$ is defined as

$$X(\alpha |\psi\rangle_A + \beta |\phi\rangle_A) = \alpha X|\psi\rangle_A + \beta X|\phi\rangle_A$$

for all $\alpha, \beta \in C$ and vectors $\in H_A$. Sometimes notation $X_{A \rightarrow B}$ is used to explicitly indicate the input and output Hilbert spaces of the linear operator X .

The set of all linear operators from H_A to H_B is $L(H_A, H_B)$. This set is itself a $d_A d_B$ -dimensional vector space. The standard basis is defined as:

$$\{|i\rangle_B \langle j|_A : 0 \leq i \leq d_B - 1, 0 \leq j \leq d_A - 1\}.$$

Using:

$$|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \dots, \quad |d-1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

we can find that the operator $|i\rangle_B \langle j|_A$ has a matrix representation as a $d_B \times d_A$ matrix with the $(i + 1, j + 1)$ -th entry equal to one and all other entries equal to zero, i.e.,

$$|0\rangle_B \langle 0|_A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |0\rangle_B \langle 1|_A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \dots,$$

$$|d_B - 1\rangle_B \langle d_A - 1|_A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

With this basis:

$$X_{A \rightarrow B} = \sum_{i=0}^{d_B-1} \sum_{j=0}^{d_A-1} X_{i,j} |i\rangle_B \langle j|_A = \sum_{i=0}^{d_B-1} \sum_{j=0}^{d_A-1} \langle i|_B X |j\rangle_A |i\rangle_B \langle j|_A$$

Given two operators X,Y their tensor product is:

$$(X \otimes Y)(|\psi\rangle_A \otimes |\phi\rangle_A) = X|\psi\rangle_A \otimes Y|\phi\rangle_A,$$

Here an example obtained by means the e “stack-and-multiply” procedure:

$$\begin{aligned} X \otimes Y &= \begin{pmatrix} X_{0,0} & X_{0,1} \\ X_{1,0} & X_{1,1} \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} Y_{0,0} & Y_{0,1} & Y_{0,2} \\ Y_{1,0} & Y_{1,1} & Y_{1,2} \\ Y_{2,0} & Y_{2,1} & Y_{2,2} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} X_{0,0} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} Y_{0,0} & Y_{0,1} & Y_{0,2} \\ Y_{1,0} & Y_{1,1} & Y_{1,2} \\ Y_{2,0} & Y_{2,1} & Y_{2,2} \end{pmatrix} & X_{0,1} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} Y_{0,0} & Y_{0,1} & Y_{0,2} \\ Y_{1,0} & Y_{1,1} & Y_{1,2} \\ Y_{2,0} & Y_{2,1} & Y_{2,2} \end{pmatrix} \\ X_{1,0} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} Y_{0,0} & Y_{0,1} & Y_{0,2} \\ Y_{1,0} & Y_{1,1} & Y_{1,2} \\ Y_{2,0} & Y_{2,1} & Y_{2,2} \end{pmatrix} & X_{1,1} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} Y_{0,0} & Y_{0,1} & Y_{0,2} \\ Y_{1,0} & Y_{1,1} & Y_{1,2} \\ Y_{2,0} & Y_{2,1} & Y_{2,2} \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} X_{0,0}Y_{0,0} & X_{0,0}Y_{0,1} & X_{0,0}Y_{0,2} & X_{0,1}Y_{0,0} & X_{0,1}Y_{0,1} & X_{0,1}Y_{0,2} \\ X_{0,0}Y_{1,0} & X_{0,0}Y_{1,1} & X_{0,0}Y_{1,2} & X_{0,1}Y_{1,0} & X_{0,1}Y_{1,1} & X_{0,1}Y_{1,2} \\ X_{0,0}Y_{2,0} & X_{0,0}Y_{2,1} & X_{0,0}Y_{2,2} & X_{0,1}Y_{2,0} & X_{0,1}Y_{2,1} & X_{0,1}Y_{2,2} \\ X_{1,0}Y_{0,0} & X_{1,0}Y_{0,1} & X_{1,0}Y_{0,2} & X_{1,1}Y_{0,0} & X_{1,1}Y_{0,1} & X_{1,1}Y_{0,2} \\ X_{1,0}Y_{1,0} & X_{1,0}Y_{1,1} & X_{1,0}Y_{1,2} & X_{1,1}Y_{1,0} & X_{1,1}Y_{1,1} & X_{1,1}Y_{1,2} \\ X_{1,0}Y_{2,0} & X_{1,0}Y_{2,1} & X_{1,0}Y_{2,2} & X_{1,1}Y_{2,0} & X_{1,1}Y_{2,1} & X_{1,1}Y_{2,2} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

In **Principles of Quantum Communication Theory**, by Sumeet Khatri and Mark M. Wilde, please find the definitions of Image, Kernel, Rank, and Support.

Trace of the linear operator: $Tr[X] = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} \langle i|X|i\rangle$.

The trace satisfies the cyclicity property: $Tr[XYZ] = Tr[YZX] = Tr[ZXY]$.

The transpose of X: $X^T = \sum_{i=0}^{d_B-1} \sum_{j=0}^{d_A-1} X_{i,j} |j\rangle_A \langle i|_B$.

The conjugate transpose of X, also known as the Hermitian conjugate or the adjoint of X:

$$X^+ = \sum_{i=0}^{d_B-1} \sum_{j=0}^{d_A-1} \bar{X}_{i,j} |i\rangle_A \langle j|_B$$

The adjoint of X is the unique linear operator satisfying:

$$\langle \phi|X\psi\rangle = \langle X^+\phi|\psi\rangle$$

for all $|\psi\rangle \in H_A$ and $|\phi\rangle \in H_B$.

Many other definition and properties in Principles of Quantum Communication Theory, by Sumeet Khatri and Mark M. Wilde, 2020.

Let us stress here the **Spectral Theorem**.

Given a linear operator $X \in L(H)$ acting on some Hilbert space H, if there exists a vector $|\psi\rangle \in H$ such that $X|\psi\rangle = \lambda|\psi\rangle$, then $|\psi\rangle$ is said to be an eigenvector of X with associated eigenvalue λ . The set of all eigenvectors associated with an eigenvalue λ is a subspace of H , called the eigenspace of X associated with λ , and the multiplicity of λ is the number of linearly independent eigenvectors of X that are associated with λ (in other words, the dimension of the eigenspace of X associated with λ). The eigenspace of X associated with λ is equal to $\ker(X - \lambda I)$.

The spectral theorem allows us to decompose every normal operator X, i.e., an operator that commutes with its adjoint, so that $[XX^+ - X^+X] = 0$, in terms of its eigenvalues and projections onto its corresponding eigenspaces.

The Spectral Theorem: For every normal operator $X \in L(H)$, there exists $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that :

$$X = \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \Pi_j \quad (*)$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n \in \mathbb{C}$ are the distinct eigenvalues of X and $\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \dots, \Pi_n$ are the spectral projections onto the corresponding eigenspaces, satisfying $\Pi_1 + \Pi_2 + \dots + \Pi_n = I_H$ and $\Pi_i \Pi_j = \delta_{ij} \Pi_i$. Decomposition (*) is unique and it is the spectral decomposition of X . The spectrum is $\text{spec}(X) = \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n\}$.

Let us use the orthonormal base of the eigenvalues:

$$X = \sum_{k=1}^d \lambda_k |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k| \quad \text{(spectral decomposition)}$$

The spectral theorem tells us that every normal operator can be unitarily diagonalized. Indeed, if we consider the spectral decomposition, and we define the unitary operator U :

$$U = \sum_{k=1}^d |\psi_k\rangle\langle k-1|,$$

then $X = U D U^+$, where $D = \sum_{k=1}^d \lambda_k |k-1\rangle\langle k-1|$ is a diagonal operator.

Note that in the spectral decomposition the numbers $\lambda_k \in \mathbb{C}$ are not all distinct because the eigenspace associated with each eigenvalue can have dimension greater than one. Also, note that the spectral decomposition is generally not unique because the decomposition of the spectral projections into orthonormal vectors is not unique.

Please see all other details in the suggested reading.

An important fact is that every Hermitian operator X has real eigenvalues. We can thus split every Hermitian operator X into its positive part, denoted by X_+ and its negative part, denoted by X_- , so that $X = X_+ - X_-$.

$$X_+ = \sum_{k:\lambda_k \geq 0} \lambda_k |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k| \quad ; \quad X_- = \sum_{k:\lambda_k \leq 0} |\lambda_k| |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k|.$$

Such a decomposition of a Hermitian operator X into positive and negative parts is called the Jordan–Hahn decomposition of X .

Using the spectral decomposition, we can define the notion of a function of Hermitian operator .

Let us assume:

$$X = \sum_{k=1}^d \lambda_k |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k|$$

we have:

$$f(X) = \sum_{k:\lambda_k \in \text{dom}(f)} f(\lambda_k) |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k|$$

Power function:

$$X^\alpha = \sum_{k=1}^d (\lambda_k)^\alpha |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k|$$

$$X^{-\alpha} = \sum_{k=1}^d (\lambda_k)^{-\alpha} |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k|$$

$$X^0 = \sum_{k:\lambda_k \neq 0} |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k|$$

Logarithm:

$$\log_b(X) = \sum_{k:\lambda_k \neq 0} \log_b(\lambda_k) |\psi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k| .$$

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